

Challenges influencing Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK

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Submitted by

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DECLARATION

I, Ribitri Maharjan, declare that this thesis presented for the degree of Doctorate in Business Administration is of my own work and investigation and no material that has been submitted, in whole or in part, previously for any other academic degree. Except where states otherwise provided references or acknowledgement, the work presented is entirely my own. (Turn it in report is in Appendix).

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Date: 1 June 2021

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Abstract

The research mainly aims at identifying the factors influencing start-up of Nepalese entrepreneurship and challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating their businesses in the UK. Although Nepalese entrepreneurs are able to set up their own businesses, they find it difficult to grow and sustain their businesses. Hence it would be important to study the factors that pose the main challenges for the growth and success of such businesses embedded with external factor of the UK.

In the literature section, definition of entrepreneurship and types of entrepreneurships are discussed. In addition, various models and theories associated with entrepreneurship has been showcased. The study contributes to the entrepreneurship literature by giving new insights into immigrant entrepreneurs with specific focus on those with Nepalese origins. The study shows that presently Nepalese entrepreneurs are facing different challenges while operating their businesses in the UK. The challenges include financial and funding problems, lack of training and skills development programmes from government, culture and language barriers, networking and contacts and increasing competition from new entrants.

In the methodology section, primary qualitative data has been used so that first-hand data can be collected that are reliable and authentic. Qualitative approach is advantageous as face-to-face interviews help researcher observe the body language of the respondents which secondary data fails to provide. Researcher has interviewed 20 Nepalese entrepreneurs with an idea of acquiring appropriate information for the research. Semi- structured interview questionnaire has been used by researcher for the depth study.

The findings revealed the fact that immigrant entrepreneurs from Nepal had been facing many challenges in contrast to the native entrepreneurs in the UK. For example, they find it more difficult to arrange for funds and resources to start off with their business ventures and to keep it going at the same time. Particularly the Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs tend to face many challenges such as difficulty to access finance; many of them are not too comfortable in speaking English and also face stiff competition from large scale businesses.

The original contribution of the research is, it sheds the light on knowledge of Nepalese entrepreneurship which is often unseen and overlooked in the academic field. The study also provides practical implications to Nepalese entrepreneurs to expand their network with other ethnic groups rather than over lying on co- ethnic network. The study concluded that presently

Nepalese entrepreneurs are facing different challenges while operating their businesses in UK. The challenges include financial and funding problems, lack of training and skills development programmes from government, language barriers, networking and contacts and increasing competition from new entrants. The policy makers should appreciate the contribution of ethnic entrepreneurs and work on its rules and regulations to promote healthy and sustainable environment for entrepreneurs. This is necessary since such entrepreneurial ventures form a significant part of the country's economic growth.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter will provide study context, justification for research undertaking, the aims and objectives, research methodology used and structure of the study. Business organizations are always challenged by the external environment in which they operate. This is not only true for small and medium enterprises but also for multinational companies (Bruhn and Schoar, 2018). However, the capital investment and the huge back up plans of multinational companies make them less vulnerable to these factors but at the same time small businesses face major challenges due to the external environmental conditions (Carragher and Paridon, 2015). There has been growing interest and considerable recognition in entrepreneurship in recent years. All financial institutions, political institutions, sociologists and global business corporations have shown extensive interest in ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK (Ram and Jones, 2018). There are about 456,073 migrant entrepreneurs in the UK which makes about almost 14.5% of all other businesses of the UK providing more than £25 billion significant contribution to the UK economy (Ullah *et al*, 2016). It shows that ethnic minority businesses have significant economic role in the UK. Asian entrepreneurs have made substantial transition to large scale owners and highly profitable businesses from just shopkeepers. This has been area of subject attracting the media attention but has been neglected in academic research (Basu and Goswami, 2010). Hence, this research will examine the study and explanation of the challenges of the external factors that influence ethnic minority, Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK with the aim to shed the light on overlooked and under researched Nepalese entrepreneurship.

Even a few years ago socio- economic data of Nepalese population in UK was not available easily. They formed a part of the ethnic minority in the country and very less data was available about the Nepalese population living in the UK. They referred to as “Other Asians” living in the UK. This was majorly because of the fact that information about the Nepalese population was under reported in the census and was identified on the basis of the country of their birth (Rangaswamy and Gandhi, 2017) However, recent surveys conducted from 2008 onwards shows a rise in the Nepalese population in the UK and by the end of 2008 the number of Nepalese population in the UK was about 72,173 (Sigona *et al*. 2015). Since 2008 there has been a growth in Nepalese immigration in the country which highlights the need for further studies into the community and their mode of earnings while staying in the country (Sunam and McCarthy, 2016). There are several factors affecting the growth and sustenance of a business in a particular

business environment. Business entrepreneurs are always on the lookout for opportunities that would help them to enter a market and establish their business and at the same time grow and sustain their business (Kesting and Gunzel-Jensen, 2015). Although business prospects in the UK are bleak for the Nepalese community but people belonging to this community are trying to establish a strong foothold in the business environment in the country with their innovative ideas (Edwards and Gaventa, 2014). Many Nepalese entrepreneurs have set up food business in the country and with good reviews about Nepalese cuisine it could be said that there are good chances for growth in the food industry by Nepalese entrepreneurs (Randolph and Agarwal, 2017). Thus, with the growth of Nepalese community in the UK there has also been rise in entrepreneurial ventures undertaken by the community to enter the UK business environment. Although the UK business environment is suitable for the growth and success of small and medium size business, but cultural elements play a crucial role in determining growth in the business environment. Entrepreneurs from Nepal agree that there is the difference between doing business in Nepal and UK as many elements have to be taken care of; for example, health and safety laws and other rules and regulations are very strict in UK (Xenetiet *al.*, 2017).

Although faced with these external environmental challenges, Nepalese entrepreneurs are doing quite well in the country and have also been able to provide support and employment to the Nepalese population and specifically the students belonging to their community (Tietenberg and Lewis, 2016). The Nepalese community in UK has developed a Nepalese business association in the country in order to form an umbrella organization to help and support the Nepalese businessmen operating in the UK (Blaikie, 2016). This body also engages in providing awards and recognition to businessmen in order to motivate them for better performance in the future (Pfeffer, 2014).

Since 2008 there is a change in migration trend with more people from Nepal migrating to UK for the purpose of work, studies etc. Many among them have invested in entrepreneurial ventures given the vast opportunities prevalent in the country for start-up business enterprises (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015). Although the Nepalese community engaged in businesses providing significant economic contribution in the UK, they are challenged by the new rules and regulations in the country but they are consolidating their business in the country with hard work and better business policies. Hence in this thesis while studying the business challenges for entrepreneurs in the UK business environment will mainly focus on the Nepalese business community which was earlier regarded as a minority community in the country (Sepulveda *et al.*, 2018), engaged in small and medium sized business in the UK.

1.2 Research Background

The study examines the challenges of Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK exploring reason to start and develop their businesses in the UK. Although UK business environment is good for the growth of SMEs in the country many challenges exist in the business environment for starting up a business by people who have immigrated to the country (Simpson, 2017). Britain is open for business and has been attracting talent from across the world to come to the country for starting up business in the country and has also been providing Tier 1 entrepreneur visa to those who wish to start up a business in the country (Wilson, 2018). But the major problem for obtaining this visa for starting up a business in the country or for expanding one's business relates to the needs to show enough capital in order to obtain the Visa. An entrepreneur needs to have £50,000 in capital from a registered venture capital firm for obtaining the Visa (Wilson and Testoni, 2014). However, acquiring so much capital is difficult for small and medium sized businesses that mostly depend on funds from their family members and friends for starting up their business. But despite these challenges the number of UK start-ups has risen to new records in the country. As per government records migrants are setting up new start-up companies in the country in different segments (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015). One in every seven, UK Start-up Company is said to be established by an immigrant from another country (Burns, 2016). Official records reveal that more than half a million people in the country who have emigrated from around 155 countries have set up business in the country and have been contributing to the revenue of the UK (Hist *et al.*, 2015). The current trading revenue undertaken by these companies surpasses that of £1m which the amount is contributing towards the economy of the country (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015).

Research also prove that immigrants involved in start-up businesses in the UK are hyperactive and significantly contribute to the economy of the nation which in itself is a great thing (Favell, 2016). Research based on filings at companies' house highlight that entrepreneurial activity among the business community in the country is more prevalent among the immigrants as compared to individuals who are born and brought up in the UK (Addo, 2017). According to statistics immigrants from other countries have launched more entrepreneurial business in the UK (17.2%) as compared to individuals born in the UK (10.2%) (Clark *et al.*, 2017). But the lack of entrepreneurial skills, communication gap and access to easy finance for immigrants make it difficult for entrepreneurs to often sustain and grow in the UK business environment. Immigrants from other countries have set up more start-ups than UK nationals in face of tough challenges while starting up business in the country. Almost 14 percent start-ups in the UK were

founded by entrepreneurs who are immigrants. According to a report for 2014, there are 456,073 immigrant entrepreneurs who work in the UK and have founded 464,527 business organizations which employ more than 8.3 million people (Kamall, 2021). For instance, the founder of the company DueDil, which is a due diligence tool and platform for business information that provides information about companies that are registered in UK and in Ireland and other 20 European countries, is an American-born immigrant (Carter *et al*,2015).

Immigrants from the Asian countries face more challenges as compared to immigrants from other western countries while operating their business within the business environment of the UK (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015).Some of the challenges faced by immigrants while setting up new business in the country is cultural and language barriers and access to finances etc (Laczko, 2018).All kinds of major business and their allied decision-making protocols come with hurdles but international expansion comes with its own unique set of obstacles. Language and cultural barriers is the most crucial obstacle that the authorities of the enterprise face while building up international domains of their business in the global market outside the regional demographics. The co-founder and CEO of Cellairis, Taki Skouras, had stated that the recruitment of bilingual experts is effective for organizations and to carry out progressive working practices in international grounds. The difference in the tax codes and compliance issues along with other issues regarding business regulations and packaging standards are the second concern for international expansion of business. Overseas business accomplishment and gaining enough expected profit is a matter of time, patience and hard work (Shammiet *al.*, 2017). There is indeed another restriction faced by overseas business and that is competition from the local business persons. Moreover, the consumers of that particular region being inclined towards the local business practices is also another restriction towards the progressive growth of the overseas business enterprises as the former possess more face value and brand image in the domestic market.

Nepalese immigration is on a rise in the UK since 2008 and a majority of the population is situated in Southeast part of the UK. Nepalese population has reached major parts of the country and a large number of the population is engaged in small and medium sized enterprises (Avgerou and Walsham, 2017). A Community Network Services (CNS) UK survey conducted in the year 2008 shows that almost 7 out of 10 Nepalese people living in the UK are born in Nepal and later on immigrated to UK for better education and financial opportunities. According to Nepalese community fact sheet of Embassy of Nepal in the year 2021, about 80,000 Nepalese populations born in Nepal are living in the UK (Embassy of Nepal, 2021). With such huge

immigration from Nepal and other countries the Nepalese population explored different opportunities to satisfy their financial needs (Van Naerssen and Asis, 2016). The external business environment in the UK is supportive of the growth and development of SMEs which has given rise to numerous SMEs in the country (Veronica *et al.*, 2020). Surveys conducted in the country shows that the Nepalese population is taking active part in opening up small and medium sized businesses in the country (Maksimov *et al.*, 2017).

The growing Nepalese population in the country has led to the growth of start-up businesses by the Nepalese population and mostly they engage in food start-up business as Nepalese food is highly in demand not only among the Nepalese population in the UK but also from other communities (Freund, 2016). There is huge competition in the food industry with large number of Nepali food joints operating in the UK. Young Nepalese population is engaged in the food industry in the country where they are bringing in new and innovative ideas to cater for the people in the UK (Adhikary *et al.*, 2018).

Hence, it would be important to study these factors that cause main hindrance and challenges for immigrant entrepreneurs to succeed. However, the main focus would be on the Nepalese community considered as ethnic minority since there has been an influx of Nepalese immigrants in the country since 2008 and also being under researched in the academic field (Pariyar and Lovett, 2016).

1.3 Research problem

There has been general literature on the challenges SMEs in the UK face (Masood and Sonntag, 2020). Other studies have focused on entrepreneurship challenges in general (Kumar and Singh, 2017). Few studies have explored entrepreneurship challenges among immigrant communities (Bhachu, 2017). Whilst some studies have grouped Asian immigrants together (Clark *et al.*, 2019) with others grouping African immigrants (Kulu and Hannemann, 2019) with yet others that focus on the Indian or Chinese communities, there is a lack of studies that pay significant attention to the Nepalese entrepreneurs.

This study focuses on the challenges faced by immigrants who engage in start-up businesses. Here, in this research the emphasis will be laid on the Nepalese community. Although this community fell into the minority section in the earlier part of the last decade, records since 2008 highlights that there has been a significant rise in the number of Nepalese immigrants in the country of which a large number of the population has been engaging in startups (Adhikary *et*

al., 2018). Thus, the research problem that this specific study would be pointing at is the challenges faced by immigrants and especially the Nepalese population while operating entrepreneurial ventures in the country.

1.4 Aims and objectives

The research mainly aims at identifying the reason to start the business in the UK and challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating their business in the UK. Although immigrant entrepreneurs set up their business but at the same time, they find it difficult to grow and sustain their business. Hence it would be important to study the factors that pose main challenges for the growth and success of such businesses (Cecelja *et al.* 2015).

- To explore the reason for Nepalese Entrepreneur to start business in the UK.
- To understand the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs for the growth and development of their business in the UK.
- To find out if Nepalese Entrepreneurs are obtaining significant help and support for start up and the smooth operations of their business in the UK.

1.5 Research questions

The research would aim to address the following research questions based on the above objectives:

Is the business environment of the UK conducive of the growth and sustain of small and medium sized businesses owned by Nepalese entrepreneurs?

However, in order to address this main question, it would be important to address other sub questions which are as follows-

- 1) Why Nepalese entrepreneur choose to start their business in the UK?
- 2) What are the main challenges faced by the Nepalese community in conducting business in the UK?
- 2) How do Nepalese Entrepreneurs obtain and utilise human, social and financial capital for start up and smooth operation of the business.

1.6 Research Gap and Rationale for the Research:

According to Carter *et al.* (2015), The Ethnic Minority Businesses (EMBs) are mainly victims of political and diplomatic struggles which affects the overall management of their business as well as it cripples the economy as it is not allowing the potential contributors to the economy a chance to work their way which would directly help the country. Although ethnic minorities are numerically impressive but they have been less effective in performance because they have to face restrictions in number of domains that restrict their business growth. Even though there have been policy developments for the ethnic minorities to encourage them in the business it is important to analyse to what extent challenges impact the growth of Nepalese business and Nepalese entrepreneurship (Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). Ethnic minorities play a crucial role in the growth and development of a country. It cannot be denied that these communities if provided a platform could help the country to move forward. These communities are highly focused on contributing towards the overall growth and development of the economy but due to the restrictions such as visa status, funding, and other resources, they cannot clearly implement their plans and strategies. There has been hardly any opportunity for the ethnic business owners like the Nepalese because of their small numbers. The UK Government has to be more focused on enhancing the relationship between the ethnic minority groups like the Nepalese to drive them to contribute to the growth of the country (Nathan, 2014). Hence, the present research will take an opportunity to shed light on the different challenges and factors facing the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK which would help to draw proper conclusion on the situation of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the country so that accordingly strategies could be made to make sure the Nepalese entrepreneurs are provided an effective platform which would help them to operate their businesses properly.

There have been significant talks about immigrants as well as researches which clearly talk about the availability of opportunities for the ethnic minorities like Nepalese. The Young Nepalese generation residing in the UK is visionary and wants to do a lot of things to enhance their careers (Storey, 2016). Right from making schools and colleges and to developing restaurants and other businesses they have done it all and hence this shows the constructive mind-set of the Nepalese entrepreneurs hence, it becomes extremely important to influence them properly to make sure they put constant effort to evolve as a successful community contributing to the growth and development of the economy. It cannot be denied that there has been potential isolation of the

ethnic groups in the country (Carragher, 2015). The present study stands to be significant because this will focus on improving the understanding as to what challenges that the Nepalese entrepreneurs have to face while operating their business and what factors promote or hinder their business in the UK market. Apart from the market factors like competition there are several other factors which promote or hinder businesses and hence it is important that these factors and challenges are effectively understood which would help these Nepalese entrepreneurs to promote their business properly (Wright et al., 2015).

The Nepalese people are a minority in the UK but have stayed in the country for a long period of time. The Nepalese have served for the British army even 200 years back and hence the relationship of the Nepalese with the UK has been there for a long time (Ceceljaet *al.* 2015). Living in the country for a long period of time the Nepalese have kept a low profile in the UK. The Nepalese people have played an important role in the history of Britain where Gurkhas and Lepchas have worked in the British army which means the Nepalese living in UK embrace it as their own country and hence, they are interested to perform positive actions which would help them to become responsible citizens (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015). The in-depth study of the Nepalese population in the UK has been found to be small which creates interest among the researchers. The UK Government is focused on enhancing the living standards of the people in the UK and hence the government is aiming to especially take special interest on the business opportunities in the country. There are number of different ethnic groups in the country who have been promised equal opportunity in the field of business, but it has not been the case. In the recent past from the study on the Nepalese population it has been found out that the exact number of Nepalese people staying in the UK is still not confirmed (Wang and Altinay, 2012). There are extensive studies on various entrepreneurial activities of diverse ethnic minority groups in the UK such as Chinese, Indian, Turkish, Bangladesh etc (Altinay and Altinay, 2006). However, existing research doesn't include Nepalese ethnic minorities in the UK. The Nepalese community has been overlooked and neglected and there is indeed very little literature available or can say invisible in academic literature about Nepalese entrepreneurship (Dana, 2014, p.225). According to Ram and Jones (2018), there is a research gap in new communities entrepreneurial activities and this community is interesting not only because of under researched group but also because, even though migration of Nepalese is comparatively new phenomenon in the UK, Nepalese are fast growing ethnic minorities and rapidly growing their businesses in the UK. Hence, it becomes extremely important that the research analyses the movement of the Nepalese

population in terms of doing business and what are the common challenges and factors facing by the Nepalese entrepreneurs.

Since the Nepalese are minority in the country they tend to live together and work together and this has been the primary strategy of their stay in the UK. Whatever these people do they do it together which helps to promote the community overall. The minority in the UK tend to focus on the contribution towards the economy which is a major plus for the community to stay in England (Brunswick and Vanhaverbeke, 2015). The new Nepalese young generation has come up with the business ideas to establish themselves as responsible citizens of the country which has created a significant change among the Nepalese community. For example, a group of Nepalese entrepreneurs opening a restaurant together in North London has been an effective step in their evolution as citizens of the country. The restaurant has been effective making sure that people notice Nepalese contribution which would help the community to not only evolve as an important part of the country but to also establish themselves professionally (Carter et al., 2015).

There have been significant factors and challenges for the Nepalese communities in the UK. It is extremely important that the Nepalese community have been able to consolidate in the market effectively which is a good sign for the community but for the young entrepreneurs and it is important that they get proper foothold which is really important in the UK market (Carragher, 2015). The main issue for the Nepalese entrepreneurs is that they are working in a highly competitive market which would directly affect their overall plan and programmes. Hence it is very important that the young entrepreneurs to analyse the possible challenges that they would face while operating in the market and are able to cope with the highly competitive market. It cannot be denied that the retail sector of UK is congested with small and medium scale businesses as well as top players playing for the highest market share and hence in this scenario the main issue for the Nepalese entrepreneurs stands to be how to strategize their overall business program which would help them to ensure success in the business (Connolly, Marino and Lucio, 2014).

In the recent past the interest of the British Government over ethnic minority businesses has grown rapidly so it is extremely important to be analysed properly. Immigrant entrepreneurship issues naturally emerge when minorities emphasise on doing businesses (Cecelja et al. 2015). Even though there are regulations which help the organisations to effectively flourish, but there are also certain key issues which discourage the Nepalese entrepreneurs to do business. In addition, previous study illustrates that critical restraint for growth of ethnic businesses are

highly dependent on ethnic community which includes factors such as inability to attract customers beyond ethnic group, poor advice, limited finance, limited capital from friends and families, limited advice from co-ethnic sources, reliance only on co-ethnic labour (Basu and Altinay, 2002) The characteristics of an entrepreneur, his/ her social and cultural factors have fundamental role in entrepreneurial activities development and survival of ethnic minority businesses (Altinay and Altinay, 2006). In this context, this research aims to develop more understandings on the challenges as of how social, cultural and environmental factors, individual characteristics influence Nepalese entrepreneurs to engage in start-up business and its survival in the UK. Also, this study will focus on how ethnic Nepalese entrepreneurs obtain social, human and financial capital for their businesses. The rationale of the research lies in the fact that there has been emergence of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the market which is a good indication for the government as the minorities like Nepalese coming into the picture for the overall good of the UK economy.

1.11 Research Methodology, Approach and Design

The concerned research study, aims to investigate the aspects and factors that influence the business start-ups as well as the development of Nepalese entrepreneurship through determining the opinions, views and interpretation of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. The study is collectively based on the qualitative data collection method of 20 interviews with Nepalese entrepreneurs, residing in the UK. The sampling of the Nepalese entrepreneurs was done through utilising personal contacts and then the method of snowball sampling. The study used semi-structured interviews with a series of open-ended questions in order to provide a better and in-depth understanding.

1.12 Structure of the Research

The research paper consists of six consistent chapters, which provide thorough and intricate details on the chosen study area. The Introduction Chapter sets forth the basic information and structure of the chosen topic and plans for an integrated composition of the research process, through the help of setting out research background, aims, objectives, research questions, research gap and rationale and research methodology. The introduction chapter also provides a brief profile of the country, Nepal along with its various associated aspects like communities, organisations, migrants of Nepal that have been seen to reside in the UK. Chapter 2 focuses on the different reviews of literature sources, relevant to the chosen topic. The literature aims to review the previous literature that has the collection of associated and reliable data with relatable

theories boxed on the ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK. On the other hand, Chapter 3, Research Methodology, speaks about the detailed process through which the research has been conducted. It duly consists of the approach, design, philosophy, data collection techniques, data analysis. Sampling techniques and population size, the sources included and excluded and also the strategy amended for intricate research. This chapter sets out the methods for the conduction and successful completion of the study complying with the research aims, objectives and questions. Moreover, through this chapter, the validity and reliability issues along with the ethical considerations are also reflected widely. Chapter 4 represents the findings of the research that are gathered from various first-hand sources through the form of interviews, where 20 Nepalese entrepreneurs have been interrogated for satisfactory data collection. Chapter 5 provides an intricate and summative discussion of the findings through analysing them thoroughly and integrating them with that of the recent thesis. This chapter therefore, compares contrasts and discusses the gathered findings from interviews with 20 respondents, linking them with the aspects covered in the literature review. Chapter 6 predominantly concludes the facts and findings through making a summary of each point and research objectives and aligning them with that of the collected data. The chapter finally portrays and discusses limitations and recommendations based on the research for future scope.

1.13 Conclusion

The first chapter of this research project deals with introducing the common idea behind this project. In this chapter, the background of the main subject, the issues faced by Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs while entering a larger foreign market of United Kingdom. The background details provide a vast idea about the basic assumptions regarding the topic of the research. The aims and objectives of this research project are stated in a clear manner so that the reader gets a brief idea about the same. Other sub points such as research rationale, research questions and significance of the research and methodology are also discussed. Research rationale deals with the need for conducting this particular research conveniently. The significance of the research holds all the important points related to the importance of the research and its effect on the business. This chapter reflects a background detailing of the assessments which are coming in the upcoming chapters of this research project. This chapter thus helps in explaining the topic in details and identifying the aims, objectives, research gap and rationale of the research.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Chapter Introduction

In this chapter the student has reviewed existing literature related to entrepreneurship focusing on entrepreneurial ventures in Nepal and the UK. Firstly, the literature covers the overview of the concept of entrepreneurship and its different types. This chapter has also highlighted factors that influence start-up and development of ethnic minority businesses by reviewing existing theories and knowledge. This chapter has ensured the relevance of the research questions formed while focusing upon carrying out the research on entrepreneurship challenges faced by ethnic entrepreneurs in the UK while rolling out new ventures. The significance and relevance of entrepreneurship in the context of Nepal along with the challenges and opportunities available to individual entrepreneurs in that country are also analyzed and reviewed. The concept of growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) along with the governing factors in the external environment of business have also been evaluated through effective review of literature. This chapter has also reflected upon the business context in the UK including the challenges and opportunities of entrepreneurial ventures. A comparison analysis of entrepreneurial context between both of the nations of Nepal and the UK has been carried out through the literature review chapter to focus on formulation of effective methods for carrying out the research and to address the research questions promptly.

2.2 What is Entrepreneurship?

Entrepreneurship is an idea of starting a new business. Business plans, designs, ideas, innovations are necessary for starting a new business. Following these innovative ideas business related problems can be solved. Sometimes people take risks to start a new idea for business, which has high possibility of failure because of the innovative ideas. But it has another side that is the products and services which are launched by entrepreneurs can create a good market and new opportunities (Newman *et al.*, 2017).

Entrepreneurial trend is growing across the globe with various changes taking place. There have been significant changes in the business trends of the organisations in the United Kingdom as well. Trend of entrepreneurship is globally growing all over the world. But the business environment of the country is not motivating enough to let the entrepreneurship spirit flourish at its potential. So, in these entrepreneurial studies help in growing the business on a large scale. Entrepreneurs are individuals who innovate ideas to run their own business. The primary focus

on entrepreneurship is to generate revenue for the business and to establish their business in the competitive marketplace.

While penetrating into a new business environment, there are two crucial yet powerful factors which can affect the progress of the business. One is the hindrances or drawbacks of the business environment which turns into an obstacle in the path of the seamless functioning of the business operations (Wynarczyk *et al.* 2016). And the other is the beneficial factors affecting the business which can trigger the growth of the business to a greater extent. At the initial stage of a business, these two factors should be kept in mind as they are considered as the most effective components of the business industry. The first factor is considered as challenges of a business, and with proper research and analysis the challenges of a business can be identified and preventive measures can be taken as quickly as possible (Hillary, 2017).

In business world the accuracy in determining the preventive measures for the potential business challenges is a must, but it has to be time consuming as the lesser time it will take, the more time will be allotted for other operational tasks related to business. For small and medium scale entrepreneurs establishing a new business in a more developed country is very tough as they face different kind of problems. These problems affect the initial, at times, overall growth of a business (Maksimov *et al.* 2017). In this study, it will be assessed that what kind of obstacles the small and medium scale entrepreneurs while starting a business in a large developed country. Every new business requires certain favorable factors in order to establish their business and ensure sound and seamless business operations. With all those factors being in United Kingdom, small and medium scale entrepreneurs are interested in setting their business there.

Although United Kingdom has more than 90% small and medium scale enterprises, it is never an easy task to establish a new business in the market. Large countries are having larger business-related issues which need to be addressed first before going to enter the business market of United Kingdom (Teepapal, 2018). This research throws light on those sensitive areas where a small and medium scale entrepreneur from Nepal should be giving full concentration in order to establish a new business in United Kingdom and make it profitable enough. From the findings and results obtained from this study, the challenges faced by Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs in the market of United Kingdom and the measures to tackle those threats and ensure a seamless business operation.

United Kingdom is a business hub and also a home to numerous budding business enterprises. Seeing the way all the entrepreneurial ventures are flourishing in the fulfilling business

environment of United Kingdom, more entrepreneurs are showing interest in expanding their business in the market of United Kingdom (Lee *et al.* 2016). People from developing countries like Nepal are also focusing to enter the business market of United Kingdom by establishing their new business ventures there. As the business market of United Kingdom is mostly filled with small and medium scale businesses, the Nepalese entrepreneurs are seeing it as a positive aspect to start their business in UK. As for Nepal, it is a developing country and the small and medium scale entrepreneurs are striving hard to enter foreign market to earn profit in foreign currencies (Lee *et al.* 2016).

As entrepreneurship requires lots of determination and also involves a number of risk factors. Entrepreneurs are always on a look-out for new business environment in which their business operations can be incorporated seamlessly to draw bigger profits. The Nepalese entrepreneurs are trying hard to make their ground strong at the most popular UK business arena as United Kingdom is considered to have one of the most efficient and profitable market for the budding entrepreneurial ventures (Giaoutzi *et al.* 2016). A business market consists of two integral components; scope or opportunity and threat or challenges. In order to explore the scopes or opportunities the small and medium scale entrepreneurs of Nepal should combat the threats or challenges of UK business market.

From the perspective of economic and industrial background, it can be assessed that the growth rate of a company is always skewed. As the growth of a business organization depends upon certain factors from different business aspects, the companies are always focused on drawing the most beneficial result out of all the given situations. Through assessment of all the relevant factors, favorable condition to start a new business in a foreign land can be obtained (Kumar *et al.* 2015). A new enterprise, irrespective of its size, would always want to gain profits from the business operations of the same. While small and medium scale entrepreneurs try to enter a new foreign market, certain risk factors and challenges will always be there (Berisha *et al.* 2015). Through implementation of effective measures and techniques, these obstacles can be overcome at ease.

A lot of small and medium scale entrepreneurs try to enter the markets of larger countries each year, but a handful of them manage to succeed. These businesses access the factors that are related to run the business in an enhanced manner to eliminate the different issues and challenges. Entrepreneurs develop new businesses, and new businesses increase jobs opportunities following intensive competition, huge productivity and also some technological

changes. A high measured level of entrepreneurship is directly related to high economic growth. However, in reality, if entrepreneurship allows inclusion of any type of informal self-employment, then it can be increased the rate of profit of a company. Under these circumstances, high levels of entrepreneurship would correlate with slow economic growth and lagging development. A new business should follow certain guidelines in accordance with the market it is planning to enter. In the case the United Kingdom the business objectives need to be met positively to ensure a sound and seamless flow of business operations (Rostami *et al.* 2015). Through empirical findings it has been found that the small and medium scale entrepreneurial ventures succeed more than the large-scale entrepreneurial ventures in a new business environment (Rostami *et al.*, 2015).

2.3 Different type of Entrepreneurships

An entrepreneurship manages many things taking some risks. There are different sectors present to look after managements, planning, and calculations. They introduce the business with new people, advanced tools and technology. Entrepreneurial venture can be classified into the following types:

Small business Entrepreneurship:

In this type of business, the owner earns all the profit on their own. All the family members, friends and relatives are engaged with this business. The types of small business are very common like grocery shops, garment shops, tour agencies, retail shops, restaurants, cafes, confectionery shops and so on. The core motive of this kind of entrepreneur is to make profit from the business and feed their family. (Arregle *et al.*, 2015) The meaning of success to them is to lead a well-being life along with family. They collect funds from their family and friends, bank loans, loans from debtors etc. Small entrepreneur business reflects the passion of a person and self-inspiration plays the potential role in leading the firm to success (Rizos *et al.*, 2015). For SMEs, there are various opportunities in the UK. The governments as well as the financial institutes of the UK have been creating opportunities for the SMEs to grow and develop in the nation. The growth and development of the SMEs is encouraged in the UK as these business organizations contribute to the GDP of the economy. Opportunities to enable the SMEs to develop is a means to promote overall economic growth. If this section of trade grows, it will be able to transform the overall economic scenario of the country (Rizos *et al.*, 2015).

Scalable Start-up Enterprise:

In order to create a business plan for this kind of business the entrepreneurs need a scalable business model. They basically gather all the funds from their financial investors. The owner launches the business through market analysis and accepts the fact that the business plan will be changed according to the market requirement (Aithal, 2015). This kind of enterprise is able to build a small number of entrepreneurs. They start the business with all types of threats in the invested capital (Linder and Williander, 2017).

Large Scale Company:

Large scale companies have a number of stakeholders like employees, shareholders, suppliers, distributors etc. This type of business has got a limited amount of life. Large enterprises introduced new products and services in order to meet the consumer's needs. (Witkowski, 2017) The main motive of these companies is to identify the product demands in the market and satisfy the customers by meeting their demands in order to gain profit. These entrepreneurial companies grow rapidly through their innovation, adoption of new technology and compete with competitors (Nambisan *et al.*, 2018).

Social firms:

The core motive of the social firms is to create products and services for the benefit of the society. These enterprises are sometimes chargeable and sometimes non chargeable. The entrepreneurs of the social firms come up with an innovative idea where they wish to change the world in a positive way without making money from the founders.

It is evident that the small and medium scaled enterprise has played a crucial role in contributing to the economy and facilitating substantial growth in United Kingdom. Within business market of UK, it can be seen that the emerging businesses tend to engage in healthy competition. Thus, these businesses tend to strive for overall enhancement of organizational development, which eventually is contributing to the economic growth (Piperopoulos and Dimov, 2015). With increasing financial independence and stability in the market, it is more likely that these set of businesses will contribute towards the overall growth of the particular country.

2.4 Concept of Ethnic Entrepreneurship:

According to Zapata-Barrero and Rezaei (2020), ethnic entrepreneurship refers to the initiation of new business ventures by individuals of different nationality in a specific region or country that

integrates traditional and cultural values and ethical standards of the different nationality into that business environment in the respective country. Through ethnic entrepreneurship individuals from common nationality and demographic backgrounds interact with each other sharing their migration experiences and roll out new business ventures in another country (Zapata-Barrero and Rezaei, 2020). As opined by Mosbah *et al.* (2020), ethnic groups are termed as group of individuals who belong to a specified community being a part of the larger societal context sharing common origin and tradition among themselves that reflect through the cultural segmentation of their socio-economic context. Ethnic entrepreneurship can also be termed as immigrant entrepreneurship that includes immigrants to a specific country since the last few decades (Mosbah *et al.*, 2020).

Immigrant entrepreneurship does not take into consideration the ethnic minority group of people residing in that nation for centuries. It only focuses on the immigrants who have travelled to the country leaving their own native nations for the purpose of developing career perspectives as an entrepreneur in the host country. According to Ram *et al.* (2017), ethnic entrepreneurship focuses upon development of small and medium sized enterprises and businesses in the host countries after immigration from their native nations integrating co-ethnic human resources and traditional values that they have carried from their native culture. The concept of ethnic entrepreneurship has been gaining significant attention during the recent period of time due to globalisation and international immigration (Ram *et al.*, 2017). According to Moghaddam *et al.* (2018), globalisation has facilitated immigration of large number of individuals to different nations for the need of enhanced quality of life and career perspectives. The societal context in the UK has been an integration of diverse cultures and demographic factors like age, race, religion, ethnicity, language and socio-economic contexts. The cultural context in the UK has been a blend of different ethnic groups that have emigrated from various countries throughout the last few decades (Moghaddam *et al.*, 2018). The culture of the UK has been referred to as “super diverse” due to the existence of ethnic integration in the community. According to Pires and Stanton (2018), ethnic entrepreneurship in the UK has facilitated significant development of local community through the provision of employment opportunities in the small and medium sized enterprises. It has been observed through various researches that around one million individuals residing in the UK have been employed by the ethnic entrepreneurs (Pires and Stanton, 2018).

Ethnic entrepreneurship has also boosted the economic development of the country. London being the center of economic development in the UK has been a significant destination for entrepreneurial ventures carried out by ethnic groups emigrated from different countries. Ethnic

enterprises in the UK have covered a market share of 14.5% out of all the business ventures existed in the country that reflects the growth of ethnic entrepreneurship in the country. Ethnic minority groups in the UK have been perceived to be more self-dependent and self-employed rather than getting into an employment option (Dana and Morris, 2021). There has been a significant gap in the literary evidence regarding the context of Nepalese entrepreneurs. The ethnic entrepreneurs bring the traditional and cultural values from their origin nationalities to the host nations and facilitate a complete blend of different cultures into their new ventures (Gangadhar, 2018). There has been significant lack of evidence related to Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK context. The regional background and socio-cultural impact on the Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK have not been analysed in details in the existing literary resources related to ethnic entrepreneurship (Arrighetti *et al.*, 2019). According to Shneikat and Alrawadieh (2019), ethnic entrepreneurs are often referred to the sole owner and proprietor of their individual enterprises being the leader and manager of the firm who employs different resources to control the process and functioning of the venture to attain a common objective. This research has focused upon analysing the challenges of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK context only to bridge the gap of literature analysis among the existing literature. Nepalese have been one of the fastest growing entrepreneurs in the UK who have integrated traditional cultures of Nepal in the societal context of the UK. Ethnic entrepreneurship is termed as a situational context in the business scenario where new ventures are initiated by the immigrants or ethnic groups in a country location for fulfillment of the need of financial prospect of the individuals belonging to that group (Shneikat and Alrawadieh, 2019).

2.5 Analysis of ethnic entrepreneurship theories and models

Ethnic entrepreneurship has been a key area of study for the researchers highlighting upon its structural framework that has included different theories and models. There exists significant gap in the existing theoretical evidences related to ethnic entrepreneurship models and theoretical perspectives. As per Bhachu (2017), the continuous rise in the proportion of ethnic entrepreneurs in the Western nations especially in the UK has driven the initiation of the analysis of models related to ethnic entrepreneurship. The key models that have been the basis of ethnic entrepreneurship have been referred to as the social embedded theory, the interactive model and mixed embeddedness theory. All these models are fundamental constituents of the ethnic entrepreneurship based on the concept of culturalist and structuralist approaches (Bhachu, 2017).

2.5.1 The culturalist perspective:

According to Yamamura and Lassalle (2020), cultural perspectives in the entrepreneurial ventures have been a key consideration by the ethnic groups to integrate traditional touch along with being updated with the practices in the host nations to sustain in the highly competitive marketplace. Cultural aspects have been influential in defining the customer purchase intentions along with creating demand and requirement of specific products and services within the community (Yamamura and Lassalle, 2020). The ethnic entrepreneurs take into consideration the cultural and ethical standards of the society, cultural characteristics and development of cultural network among the co-ethnic community residing in the host nation. The cultural perspective of the ethnic groups of entrepreneurs reflects the ethnic characteristics like being dedicated towards work, hardworking, accepting calculated risks, loyal and personal integrity. Ethnic groups have been culturally and traditionally oriented towards being self-employed that have been a key driver behind rising numbers of ethnic entrepreneurs in the UK (Bashir, 2019).

As opined by Churchill (2017), the ethnic groups have always been focused upon developing ethnic community networks within the societal context in the host countries along with maintaining favourable relationships with the social people giving importance to the social values. The ethnic entrepreneurs have often come across numerous incidents of social discrimination that have been required to cope up with through their leadership capabilities and individual integrity (Churchill, 2017). This theory has been a basis of the concept that Asian origin entrepreneurs have been more successful in comparison to that of the other nations like African or Caribbean despite of the facts that they have come across similar type of ethnic discrimination contexts in the Western nations. The socio-economic uncertainty has been a driving force behind the formulation of entrepreneurial ventures in the Western countries that have often suppressed the cultural values and ethical standards of other ethnicities. The impact of the family aspects of the individuals belonging from the ethnic groups along with their social networks have often influenced the strategy formation for the ethnic entrepreneurial ventures (Mickiewicz *et al.*, 2019).

2.5.2 The structural Materialist perspective:

As opined by Ramadani *et al.* (2019), the structural perspective of the social embedded theory has been based upon social and racial discrimination of ethnic minority groups in the developed nations all over the world. The ethnic groups have come across significant limitations in the societal context facing serious discriminations according to their race, religion and ethnicity.

These groups have been provided with little or no access to the adequate education and healthcare system to meet their basic need of living (Ramadani *et al.*, 2019). In the workplace contexts, the ethnic groups experience significant discrimination as compared to their non-ethnic counterparts along with getting less access to recognised educational settings. This has been a key driving force behind selection of their choice to become self-employed and entrepreneur to initiate their own business ventures in the host countries. Discrimination in the wage structure and job description along with additional benefits has forced the ethnic groups to become more oriented towards entrepreneurship (Nazareno *et al.*, 2019).

According to Lam *et al.* (2019), in the Western nations, the ethnic minority groups have been significantly discriminated according to their cultural and socio-economic background. Language barrier has been another key consideration by the ethnic entrepreneurs in taking up sole-proprietorship ventures rather than getting into employment sector. The structural barriers of the individuals due to their lack of proficiency of English language and non-availability of recognised academic affiliation have been one of the main reasons behind the ethnic entrepreneurship in the western nations like the UK (Lam *et al.*, 2019). The employment scenario in the Western countries has facilitated selection of non-ethnic groups imparting biasness to the specific religions and ignoring the others irrespective of their talent and knowledge. Ethnic entrepreneurship has been focused and more oriented towards its own ethnic groups. In the highly competitive market scenario, the ethnic entrepreneurs have often come across significant challenges in the developed nations. Due to the rising number of ethnic entrepreneurs, it has been highly competitive to offer wide varieties of consumer goods and services. The focus of the ethnic entrepreneurs has been to extend their business ventures into non-ethnic market beyond the limitation of the existing market (Pires and Stanton, 2018).

2.5.3 The Interactive Model:

According to Ramadani *et al.* (2019), the interactive framework of ethnic entrepreneurship has been a significant theoretical perspective that stresses upon the fact that the economic activities have been an outcome of interactive consequences of the effective utilisation and mobilisation of resources in accordance with the ethnic community perspectives taking into account relevant historical contexts. The interactive model of ethnic entrepreneurship refers to the interaction and co-ordination of specified opportunities and the integrated resources to develop business strategies for the entrepreneurial ventures. Various governing factors existing in the external market context that are referred to be the macro factors including the socio-economic status of

the host nations, government policies and legislations, political factors and technological advancement (Ramadani *et al.*, 2019). The ethnic entrepreneurs have been oriented towards integrating social, cultural and economic perspectives to their entrepreneurial ventures. The key opportunities for the ethnic entrepreneurs have been the availability of co-ethnic human resources along with integrating their skills, knowledge, experience and competencies. Identification of major financial resources to meet the economic requirements of their entrepreneurial ventures has been key consideration of the ethnic groups to start up their new ventures.

The interactive model has been based on the interaction of various resources required by the ethnic entrepreneurs that are adequately available in the business environment (Dang, 2021). As per Szkudlarek and Wu (2018), the ethnic entrepreneurs are required to remain updated with the new techniques and strategies being applied in the present industrial context. The interactive model has been developed on the basis of three interactive components including structure of opportunities, group dynamics and business strategies that take into consideration mobilisation of resources which is complex interactions of the entrepreneurial resources (Szkudlarek and Wu, 2018). This model has been highly significant in analysing the opportunities of Nepalese entrepreneurship in the perspective of Western nations and developed countries. This model has often perceived to have limitations due to non-availability of detailed analysis the socio-political and economic context of the developed nations where the ethnic entrepreneurial ventures aim to develop (Honig, 2020).

2.5.4 Mixed Embeddedness:

As opined by Ratten (2017), the concept of mixed embeddedness has been developed on the basis of the context of migrant entrepreneurs who have been migrated from their native nations to the host countries for the enhanced economic perspectives. The mixed embeddedness model takes into consideration the focus market segment, new locations, sector preferences along with impact of respective traditions and cultures of the ethnic groups. Mixed embeddedness framework of ethnic ventures has been developed on the basis of the interactive model taking into account the opportunity structures (Ratten, 2017). The entrepreneurial ventures in the new countries have been required to be based upon the legislative regulations and economic conditions. The ethnic ventures have been oriented towards developing business contexts where the influence of the ethnic groups through community networks has been strong enough. Mixed embedded approach of ethnic entrepreneurship has integrated socio-cultural, economic and political aspects of the host country (Yamoah and Johnson, 2020). According to Ojo (2019), this

approach has been relevant in analysing the individual factors along with group dynamics in the ethnic community aspects along with highlighting on the macro factors of the business environment of the host nations. The social factors like support from the family members, emergence of social networks and adequate availability of the co-ethnic human resources at a comparatively less cost have been influential in penetrating into the new market segment by the ethnic entrepreneurial ventures.

The local community in the host countries have also been provided with significant opportunities for economic development through the incorporation of new business ventures by the ethnic groups (Ojo, 2019). In the context of this research, the mixed embeddedness approach has been significantly relevant to reflect on the Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK context analysing the opportunities of the new ventures undertaken by the Nepalese ethnic groups in the UK. As opined by Cederberg and Villares-Varela (2019), the opportunities for the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK market to grow and earn profitability through offering varieties of products and services to the target market segment have been conceptualised by the mixed embeddedness approach. The legislative context along with the socio-economic scenario of the UK have been a key driving force behind formulation of business strategies of the entrepreneurial ventures by the ethnic groups (Cederberg and Villares-Varela, 2019). The socio-economic context in the UK has come across different instances of racial and economic discriminations for the ethnic groups that have forced them to initiate self-employment and entrepreneurship ventures to sustain in the highly competitive market. These instances are for example closure of the Turkish clothing industry based in Amsterdam has forced the ethnic groups to carry out ventures on their own to survive in the UK market. The social and ethnic impacts on the communities of the ethnic groups in the developed nations like the UK have been influential factors to impart the concept of mixed embeddedness in the context of immigrant entrepreneurship (Pasillas *et al.*, 2017).

According to Barberis and Solano (2018), in the business context in the UK, ethnic entrepreneurs have often come across significant challenging aspects related to recruiting of human resources, their training and developmental aspects along with utilisation of the resources like capital, human and material in optimum manner to maintain profitability (Barberis and Solano, 2018). The prospected stakeholders of the new ventures formulated by the ethnic groups including customers, employees, suppliers and competitors along with the society as a whole have been required to be taken into consideration by the ethnic entrepreneurs while developing the business plans. As per the mixed embeddedness model, the ethnic entrepreneurs have not

been confined to the limits of their own ethnic community groups but rather focused on penetrating the markets of non-ethnic classes of the society in the host countries (Ojo, 2018). As per Kwieciński and Matusz-Protasiewicz (2017), there have been certain limitations of this model also referring to the inappropriate evidence of the facts of imparting different responses and reaction of the individuals to the identical context in the opportunity structure within the business and entrepreneurial context. The academic experts have argued for the extension of the mixed embeddedness approach of ethnic entrepreneurship to include additional perspectives of decision making and initiation of relevant actions in accordance with the situational demands. Ethnic diversity has been the key focus of the study of mixed embeddedness model focusing on a specific ethnic group of the societal context (Kwieciński and Matusz-Protasiewicz, 2017).

2.6 Ethnic entrepreneur of first generation

The current study describes about the behaviour of the first-generation entrepreneur which are mostly based on the culture and beliefs of the specific management methods to maintain comfort and security. Here the ethnic entrepreneur is the Nepalese who are young entrepreneur and the first-generation entrepreneur. In order to work in UK, Nepalese usually has to migrate to the UK for better future or establish his business in order to get recognition in different country well. As per Hussain *et al.* (2011), Nepalese has a record of around 5,943 during 2001 in UK and then it reaches to around 150,000 in present scenario. This rise occurred huge during the period of 2009 when the UK government has allowed Nepalese dependent with the Nepalese student in the country. It is interesting to find that the Nepalese entrepreneurs are the first young generation and mostly migrate to pursue for higher studies in the UK (Khadria, 2001). However, According to Dhaliwal (2018), the first-generation entrepreneurs in the UK are mostly from China, India, Pakistan, Sri-Lanka, Bangladesh and from other Asian countries within 1960s to 1970s. It is clear that Nepalese entrepreneur is different from other countries within Asia.

According to Gbadamosi (2015), the ethnic entrepreneurship theory indicates that the first generation does not have much experience and knowledge about the management and when the Nepalese arrive at the UK, they had a career objective and education to have an experience and knowledge to gain experience from the UK. It has been noted and observed that the education by the Nepalese section has been priorities the education in the UK and is considered to be most crucial section of the employees' opportunities. In Nepal the UK degree matters a lot and they are famed and recognized due to their success, employment and education field and opportunities. In the UK only the educated people and good financial background people can

sustain after migration because the uneducated person or a normal person who do not have any knowledge are not getting any pass or visa or entry for the UK, as to get an entry in the UK, the person has to have an adequate knowledge as per requirement without that a person cannot meet its expenses after he migrated to the UK (Pasillas *et al.*, 2017). They even cannot depart from that place without showing proper documents and reason. It is very important for the most educated person to have a financially strong background to meet its expense in day-to-day life in UK. For that individual it has been a proud period to proof its decision and these activity and behaviour of the entrepreneur has influenced many new and young generation to take a better step and inspired them to do something from staying outside and gather knowledge, education and employment experience (Veronica *et al.*, 2020).

Some report says during 2018 that the international student contributing around £ 20 billion to the UK government and the educational institution and to stay in UK. Increase in the student immigration has definitely increased the economic and the social structure in the UK and that will increase the benefits of the UK government and economic system. During 2019 it has been reported that more than 750000 international students has migrated to the UK every year to complete their studies and get employment opportunity. It also seen that some of the student also stay in the host country even after completing the studies to get a good opportunity or create something after gathering knowledge and studies (Christopher, 2015). Some of the authors has mentioned that the first-generation Ethnic entrepreneur and the young entrepreneur after completing their studies or within their study period they form a business through which they can understand the system of business inside the UK market. the young entrepreneur who studied in the UK and form a business inside the place has gathered necessary information to create business in the UK which required the information of business start-up registration process, tax payment facilities and policies, procedures, rules and regulations to understand the business structure level and to learn to speak the English language which is very essential in terms of communication and doing business to attain success (Morita, 2015).

The young entrepreneurs from Nepal come to the UK for study and education purpose has entry into the business with certain motive to understand the business criteria and also other ethnic group of Nepalese does have other intention or motives to enter a business in UK. In case of Fernández-Reino, (2016), it has been seen that many Nepalese or young Nepalese who come for study purpose has various other motives to either start a business along with other minority or other community or to go by own to a single start up business or join an employment within staying the country. For some of the Nepalese young ethnic entrepreneur it become important to

start up business with more facilities inside the business and that includes more value-added activities which includes more minorities individuals there has been a study which is conducted among some students these are 24 students of young Chinese. As per the research author Gates (2018), immigrant entrepreneur without revealing the person is educated in the London universities they still holding the culture and values of their community and belief to starting up business and adopt into the culture of the British.

There are certain barriers they face in starting business is the difficulty to understand the language English and due to which they have to suffer and also has to suffer when they had no experience and understanding of laws and legislations and unaware of the country they residing and no financial support and from there the entrepreneur drive their business to reach to success (Maksimov *et al.*, 2017). They might have to face conflicts due to from the other religion or from other region and from the beginning they might get influenced by the other from other college or universities to pursue higher studies and gather experience from other source which increase knowledge as well as it helps to collect money for initiating new business or start-ups. It illustrates that first-generation Nepalese entrepreneur, however, are young and are might have graduated from UK universities and achieve professional status. They are involving in a multicultural society and might have different entrepreneurial behaviour (Fernández-Reino, 2016).

In addition, Smith (2014) shows the first-generation entrepreneur related model, which can be used to study about first generation Nepalese entrepreneurs. The Figure 1, below, shows an overview of the storyline model for primarily first-generation entrepreneurs (Smith, 2005; 2009; 2014) which can be used to represent the nature of Nepalese entrepreneurs.

Figure 2. 1: First Generation Entrepreneur Storylines Source: Smith (2005; 2009; 2014)

According to Dana and Morris, 2007, it is crucial to know that entrepreneurs are one of the important parts of the entrepreneurship. Fig 2.1 shows the outline of stories of first-generation entrepreneur which are constructed around recurring and common themes and cliched storylines (Smith, 2005). It shows an impression of how stories of first generation are constructed under heroic acclamations in which adversities are overcome by mainly male entrepreneur to achieve success. The entrepreneurial identity of Nepalese entrepreneurs can be understood by mapping the Nepalese entrepreneur's stories into the literature review of classic entrepreneurial narratives. The entrepreneurial narrative approach helps to understand their entrepreneurial identity by allowing freedom to craft and map the stories. The stories and narrative orientation of entrepreneurs are constructed socially which can be presented in the storylines form (Smith and Anderson, 2004; Smith, 2009).

The first- generation entrepreneur are raised generally on the middle- class and working families. These entrepreneurs show a stereotypical storyline of overcoming adversity, hard work, started from nothing and poor-boy-made- good. The main reason of these kind of heroic stories is to praise the first- generation and celebrate their success and achievement by raising their social status. The previous studies (including Dhaliwal, 2008) focuses the 'rags and riches' storylines and views the Asian entrepreneurs as a role model. However, other researchers have questioned the Asian entrepreneurs being a corner shop struggling for survival due to low barriers to entry. Entrepreneur's stories play an important part in authoring their own stories being the individualistic stories (Down and Hughes, 2009).

Dhaliwal (2008), states that there is a strong connection between the first-generation entrepreneurs and their business deriving from the push and pull factors for starting the business. Therefore, push and pull theory is highly prevalent in study of ethnic entrepreneurship business start-up and development. The author also finds out that one of the main reasons to start the business by first generation is also due to the push factors such as economic necessity and unemployment. The push and pull factors (Reynold et al., 2001) is used by the study to identify the motivation of business among first- generation Nepalese entrepreneurs to start the business. Thus, this study shows the push and pull factors as a motivation among ethnic entrepreneurs to start the business.

2.7 Ethnic entrepreneur business motivation

The business motivation of entrepreneurs comes from different aspects, influence and knowledge and intention. Each entrepreneur engages in entrepreneurship activities by getting motivated and by getting proper knowledge of entrepreneurship. To understand the level of motivation of an entrepreneur it is essential to understand the opportunity and requirement that drives the motivation of the entrepreneur into the entrepreneurship activities (Dehart, 2020). Opportunities of entrepreneur show a start-up motivation to take advantage of a business activity and whenever necessary for the entrepreneurship by making the difference in the pull and push motivational factors in the global entrepreneurship monitor concept. It is very difficult to separate to the extent in which the entrepreneurs are getting pushed and pulled to begin the new business. This pull and push difference the factor of motivation which factors get multi-valued by the combination of both factors of pull and push.

One of the factors like self-employment which reduce the factor of unemployment in the minority part which initiate the work with innovation and motivation. It is very essential to understand the starting of self-business and for the entrepreneur business it is very essential among the Nepalese. Nepalese stress on starting on self-business rather than doing a job. They find it as self-opportunity to explore in front of the outer world to prove it identify and make the ethnic people proud and motivate top start over a new business without any issues and hurdles (Wilkinson, and Kleinman, 2016). They emphasis on starting a new business because the ethnic entrepreneur enters in a group of entrepreneurship minorities as they being treated as a labour and due to the troubles caused by the labour market and they are being discriminated as a labourer. pull factors has a benefit in the way of cultural and regional influence and access to the informal sources that this reason has informed about the creating new business by an entrepreneur mostly young generation entrepreneur those are Nepalese.

Sociology, management and psychological points there are various forms of motivational activities that are studied and examine by these different disciplines. According to Allen and Busse, (2016),there are various studies which is related to the factor which informs about the independence and achievement includes the factors of personal psychology, discrimination and mobility blocked factor determined by the structural factor, cultural and tradition and mobilization resource factors includes the cultural factor and last one is the laws and legislation, rules and regulation includes the institutional system factors which determined by the ethnic minority entrepreneurship factors.

Clark and Drinkwater (2010), highlights on the motive of ethnic minorities to start their business. To understand the Nepalese entrepreneur's entrepreneurial behaviors, it is very essential to determine the motivations for starting their own business.

Figure 2. 2: Opportunity and Necessity-driven motives into entrepreneurship
Source: (Reynold et al., 2005).

This section helps to develop the conceptual framework of this study by providing the critical analysis of previous studies. The recent study of Dabić *et al.*, (2020) explains three main influential factors for engaging in entrepreneurial activities among ethnic minorities.

These factors include labour market characteristics, individual characteristics, cultural and social resources in the host countries. This section main purpose is to do the literature review on the factors inducing start- up business and development of ethnic entrepreneurship. Initially, micro level factors comprising the individual motives, skills and values of the ethnic entrepreneur are inspected as an influencing factor in starting their businesses. It is followed by inspecting meso level influencing factors such as socio- economic and socio- cultural factors. Then the environmental factors as at macro level are inspected to address Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK context. This section examines the empirical and theoretical literature on motivation for own business start-up ownership for ethnic minorities businesses.

2.7.1 Ethnic influence

This part includes the sociological and cultural section to analyse the role and responsibilities of the social and the cultural factor of the Nepalese in the UK in starting the entrepreneurship or business. This includes various factors like social values, norms, belief and shape of social and economic relation in entrepreneur. The ethnic resources and the co ethnic employment resources are the essential part of entrepreneurship which the Nepalese e to earn profits and return from the investments (Dana and Morris 2007). The ethnic has a specification which influences the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK to have an understanding in depth. This is depending on the family background, childhood activities and regional and cultural phase which propagate and nurture the values in relation to their environmental context and where it takes its enterprise to grow Gbadamosi (2015).

2.7.1.1 Cultural values and regional beliefs

Cultural values and regional belief are section where some section of people belief that outsider turning their cultural belief when the entrepreneur working with certain other minority people to start up their business. Various previous researches have shown the significant influence of cultural values on the ethnic minorities' businesses. The entrepreneurial behaviour of ethnic minority entrepreneurs is largely determined as they undertake the business activities that are valued, popular and widely accepted in their back home. Dana and Morris (2007) also suggest that values play an essential role, especially for the ethnic entrepreneurs who have a value set deeply tied to his/her ethnic background. For instance, the cultural characteristics such as hard work and long working hours, strong work ethics, and family labour are some of the factors influencing for success for the first-generation entrepreneur (Thieme, 2006).

Nepal is a small country having area 147181 square km and population about 30 million with the annual population growth rate of 2.37 percent. Nepal is surrounded by China in the north and India in the south, east and west. It is a developing country in the world having small size of the economy about Rs 550 billion GDP and \$ 561 per capita income in FY 2009/10 (Alvarez-Garrido and Dushnitsky, 2016). The gross domestic savings and investment are about 7 % and 5 % respectively, which are very low compared to other nations. One third of the population live Nepal is a small country having area 147181 square km and population about 30 million with the annual population growth rate of 2.37 percent. Nepal is surrounded by China in the north and India in the south, east and west. It is a developing country in the world having small size of the economy about Rs 550 billion GDP and \$ 561 per capita income in FY 2009/10. The gross

domestic savings and investment are about 7 % and 5 % respectively, which are very low compared to other nations. One third of the population live below poverty level. So, it needs economic support from Abroad to survive those peoples. Lack of infrastructure, small domestic market, and limited natural resources are other major problems for Nepal. As a developing nation, Nepal has been facing several challenges in the path of economic development below poverty level (Alvarez-Garrido and Dushnitsky, 2016). So, it needs economic support from Abroad to survive those peoples. Lack of infrastructure, small domestic market, and limited natural resources are other major problems for Nepal. As a developing nation, Nepal has been facing several challenges in the path of economic development.

According to Mihaylov and Perkins (2015), Entrepreneurship is one of the important ways that can move on economic growth and compete with the fast-changing global marketplace. In this scenario Nepal is doing well because they are young and have full on energy, for any new start. Future of Nepal is not dependent on foreign aids and money for a sustainable economic growth, enough support and suitable environment for new entrepreneurship and innovations are mandatory. Entrepreneurship is important because it not only creates new employees but also makes a positive impact on youth generations. Gbadamosi, (2015) states that very young and energetic population who live in Nepal, they search for job opportunities and in this case SMEs are helping them a lot. This innovative idea is building hope, dignity, self-esteem and positive culture in their mind. In this case entrepreneurship must flourish in sustainable way.

2.7.1.2 The role of Family:

This section shows the importance of family values and families for entrepreneurial activities. Bourdieu (1996, p.19) states families as "*sets of interrelated individuals connected either by alliance (marriage) or attachment, or, less commonly, by adoption (legal relationship), and living under the same roof (cohabitation)*". According to Pant (2016), the role of the family plays some role as the influential factor in Nepalese becoming entrepreneurs. Families are also vital for entrepreneurial behaviour as it also provides financial, social and human resources for start-up business and development. It is mentioned that the parental profession of Nepalese entrepreneurs has a role in development of entrepreneurship in Nepal. Specially, the role of the father, who has strong influence in choosing the profession of their children and also acts as a role model in the family. Likewise, Kharel (2016) states the substantial role of friends and family networks among Nepalese entrepreneurs to attain rising mobility in Japan. These prior studies shows that there is a vital role of family for Nepalese entrepreneurs in Japan and Nepal. Thus, family role is observed as one of the

substantial cultural features in this study.

Dhaliwal (2008) states the importance of family among Asian first-generation entrepreneurs. The author describes that Asian entrepreneur establish their businesses as a unified family strategy. Nepalese society depend on their family members and based on a joint family system. According to Pant (2015), Nepalese main cultural values are familistic and collectivism that has a significant impact on the decision to start-up. Collectivistic supports to the goals of group and mainly use the groups as analysis unit (Hofstede, 1980). Familism is a fundamental cultural value where family undertakes the ascendancy position over interest of individual due to strong ties and deeply commitment (McGoldrick et al., 1996). In UK context, most Nepalese families are living nuclear together i.e., husband, wife, and children. According to CSNUK study of Nepalese population 48.45% are single, 49.99% are married, and the divorced rate is just below one percent. This shows stable Nepalese families. They usually compromise and settle due to which divorce is very rare. These characteristics might show Nepalese community has the unique family relationships which might accomplish distinct advantages in entrepreneurial behaviour. The loyalty, trust and strong ties are often seen among Nepalese community which can be advantageous characteristics for entrepreneurial activities. Smith (2009) states about successful entrepreneurs who gets support and help from their families. Contrarywise, Janjuha-Jivraj and Woods (2002) highlights the businesses in the case of British Asian firms are negatively affected by the emotional and confusing bonds between the families.

Furthermore, decision to start-up business is often significantly influenced by the family background. Smith (2009, p.28) explains the entrepreneurial family as *“a family element oriented toward success irrespective of whether the siblings or parents are or become entrepreneurs. It has more to do with being enterprising and productivity than with entrepreneurship”*. The entrepreneurial decision may be influenced by certain entrepreneurial values of an individual born and raised in the entrepreneurial family. Basu (2004) has stated the family background as the mix of complex cultural tradition rooted in the concept among the Hindus caste and occupational caste. This definition given by him is more related to the family background concept for the study on Nepalese entrepreneurship. Klandt (1984, pp.236-41)describes that a business entrepreneurs larger ratio come by a chance that has come from a business-owning families However, Basu (2004) states that the entrepreneurial orientation is influenced by the family background but not completely determine it. Basu adds further that the business-orientation might

or might not aspired by an individual belongs to a business family but more inspired by the acquisition of human capital. In Addition, Smith (2005) explains that through social learning theory, the parent can act out as a positive role model for motivating his/her child and assisting them for an insight into networking. According to Anderson and Miller (2003) Smith (2005), the background of entrepreneurial family impact on accessing of capital. Aldrich and Cliff (2003) states that children gain and influenced by the family member experience where families act out as a prevalent element for entrepreneurial behaviour.

2.7.1.3 The level of education:

According to Ramadani et al. (2014), there is a stereotype that most of the ethnic entrepreneurs are with lower levels of education. However, as discussed earlier that education has been the main concern amongst the Nepalese community in the UK. Dhungel (1999) states that only the financially capable and educated people can migrate to the UK. Thus, it is interesting to find out that entrepreneurial behaviour is influenced by the level of education of entrepreneurs.

According to Smith (2006, p. 102), The system and level of education is significant social institution. Smith further explains about relationship between educational qualification and ethnic class where individual with higher class can pursue the higher education. There will be separation of castes at education level where the structure of society is based on the caste composition, The higher level of education can be accessed by the entrepreneurs of higher caste. Therefore, it is interesting to examine either the optimistic motivation factors such as a experience of group's background engaging in entrepreneurial activities and skills and education along with the cultural traditions are major factors, or whether negative factors such as ethnic group discrimination in the labor market or blocked mobility plays a major role. Canado *et al.* (2014) states that the impact of skills and level of education for the success and start-ups of ethnic minority enterprises has been emphasized by the several studies. Altinay and Altinay (2008) illustrates the positive impact on the growth of the business due to the entrepreneur's educational level. The authors further explains that the entrepreneurs who experienced higher education has lower barriers for their entry and growth in business. This component improves entrepreneurial judgement by delivering the individuals' managerial and analytical abilities, entrepreneurial abilities, which helps in control and planning, recruitment of staff and developing strategy (Casson, 1991). Thus, well-educated individual is more likely to involve in entrepreneurial activities by gaining skills and information provided by the education. According to Metcalf et al. (1996), Indians are more successful in

comparison of Pakistanis in the growth of the enterprise due to the strong impact of level of education. It also indicates that even if this element does not have direct significant impact, it may promote to the growth and success in the other ways.

For example, it enhances the entrepreneurs' communication skills with the host country including suppliers, clients, bank, and other external financial resources which reduces barriers and constraints for the business growth (Basu and Goswami, 1999 pp. 259). In order to get start-up loans, business advice and to attract customers it is very essential to have skill to communicate in English for the ethnic Nepalese entrepreneurs. Thus, there will be positive impact on productivity and socio-economic integration with better communication (Altinay and Altinay, 2008). According to Clerk and Drinkwater (2000), the labour market discrimination existence, such as wages discriminatory in the job, lead into entrepreneurial activities by the ethnic minorities. Additionally, a minority tended to be lower in self-employment due to disadvantage in the English language.

2.7.1.4 Ethnic social networks:

Social relationships and social networks play an important role in accessing resources. The information and advice can also be gathered by the ethnic networks. There is the vital role in ethnic networks with the social network of friends, family and community advisors. According to Dhaliwal (2008), the ethnic entrepreneurs stay away from outsiders and heavily rely on advice from co-ethnic professionals such as lawyers and accountants followed by friends and family and advice from their community. Dhaliwal, 2008 states that the young generation are more hostile and resistant as they are often graduated from British universities whereas, the first-generation constraints a link within the community. Similarly, there has been much more debate on the Asian community ethnic networks (Basu and Goswami; Ram and Jones, 1998). According to Dhaliwal (2008), "productive diversity aspect" where businesses of ethnic minority are now identifying the economic benefits and opportunities that lie in multiculturalism. They can achieve competitive gain by capitalizing on their cultural knowledge, communication skills and developing business networks of ethnic communities.

2.7.2 The opportunity in the host country:

The young generation are inspired by Western practices who have been educated in the UK and are incorporated with the broader population of the host country. They are more advanced with improved communication skills. The previous study amongst Asian community indicates that the younger generation is retaining a more importance on the opportunities that exist within the UK for start-up and growth of businesses instead of escaping from discrimination and unemployment (Dhaliwal, 2004). The younger generation is more diversifying and dynamic by identifying the opportunities that is present within the host country They are diversified into various sectors by serving wider population through break out from serving co-ethnic group (Dhaliwal 2004). According to Dhaliwal (2008), times have shifted on to new sectors, especially within high technology areas and a high growth. The Asian ethnic entrepreneurs have shown lustiness compared to the micro traditional business. This finding is applicable to the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK as many young Nepalese entrepreneurs achieve their higher studies in the UK. They are more likely to be greatly integrated and educated with a wider population. For example, in the context of Australia, there are Nepalese entrepreneurs in significant numbers involving in the educational sector. According to Ojha (2014), It is astonishing to know that Mr. Shesh Ghale, an entrepreneur of Melbourne Institute of Technology, one of the Nepalese entrepreneurs, is one of the 200 wealthiest Australians.

The above section is about the literature review on start-up business and development on motivational factors for the ethnic entrepreneurship. It illuminates push and pull motivational factors at different level for ethnic entrepreneurs to start- up and grow their own business. The push and pull theory fail to identify the acquiring strategies and utilisation of resources even though it can identify the motivational factors. Thus, to identify the acquiring of strategies and resources utilization such as, human, social and finance, the next section will investigate the literature on resources access and utilisation for business start-ups and development.

2.8 Business environment of UK:

There have been an increasing number of challenges faced in the form of global economic turmoil and economic instabilities that are embodied within the paradigm of Europe. Despite all such challenges and critical situational factors, it is likely that positivity is obtained on the part of the

business environment of UK. Along with being positive they are also regarded to be forward looking as they show openness towards the business. The UK government is likely to expect extreme level of commitment to establish a supportive environment for the business. This is likely to give rise to stability towards the business enterprises as it helps in the process of economic recovery (Gërguri-Rashitiet *al.* 2017). Till the 2012 there were a number of barriers which imposed instability towards the UK markets. UK is understood and analyzed to be the easiest places to be treated as prospective business locations specially to seek openness for the new entrepreneurship. UK market place is appropriate to support all sorts of business establishments. They are capable of helping businesses of all sizes and attract the investors and entrepreneurs. A profitable yet competitive market is provided towards the new business prospects. It is necessary that a constructive planning for growth is expected to be incorporated to be able to cut the corporate tax rates, investing upon the infrastructure, developing the skills, controlling the regulations and limiting the planning burdens. These are essential include once the competitive platform is created for them. UK is identified as one of the most promising business conducting locations as it is considered as top 3 destinations where inward investment on a global platform. The financial services, information and communication technologies are the typical sectors that are targeted within the region of New York (Rasmussen and Wright, 2015). In addition to them, pharmaceuticals, life science, energy and environment along with creative media shall incorporate within the business sphere of the UK. High value with opportunities to explore is provided in the form of program where intensive support is possible so that the larger companies are in search of winning the big contacts. The major supply chains can be necessarily identified to cover the operations of the SMEs across the range of diverse sectors operating in the UK.

Organizations do business to make profit and to offer employment opportunity. The business is usually done in a way that will increase profitability. In recent times, maintaining a substantial position in business is needed to attain success in any business in the long run in any business environment of a particular country such as United Kingdom. Therefore, irrespective of the size and scope of any organisation, it is very much essential that substantial innovativeness should be added in its functioning that would set the organisation& helps to make a proper position in terms of reputation apart from the competitors in the existing market of that particular field. And for this reason, effective entrepreneurship is being widely recognised in the business environment of UK which also includes immigrant entrepreneurs along with the existing challenges that they have to face with their entrepreneurship skills which is growth oriented for the purpose of business in

order to establish business in transient market, innovation is considered as the key (Schaperet *et al.*, 2014).

In order to explain the environment of business in United Kingdom in this context of entrepreneurship and the growth-oriented business organization it refers to the small and medium enterprise business presents in UK as of now. The government of UK is also focused on the high level of growth of mainly the innovative small and medium-sized enterprises. The government of United Kingdom is giving opportunities in terms of support which provides high value for the entrepreneurs who might be immigrant in UK also for example we can consider the financial service providing business, information and communication technology, creative and media sector etc. as United Kingdom is a home to a vast number of business organizations. By following their footsteps, a huge number of start-ups have also joined the already flooded business industry. In this competitive market, business organizations are striving hard to remain in their positions. Adoption of the new technologies will ensure better results for the business organizations in United Kingdom. The influence behind this entrepreneurship in the environment of the business of UK is generated based on the level of unemployment in UK as we know the business can able to reduce the level of unemployment within a country and its reflection can be seen in the economic structure of the country such as UK. And for this reason, the government has taken steps by giving support to the entrepreneurs of new business organization which basically includes the small and medium scale enterprise (Piperopoulos and Dimov, 2015). UK government has also generated a relationship between the rate of unemployment and the rate of new business as well.

These above-mentioned different organizations have different kinds of sizes and scopes and these scopes and sizes are two most crucial factors that can create difference in various companies. However, the scope of a company refers to the business scopes and the procedure taken by the organization to elevate the level of profitability. Better the scope of an organization, better the chances of success for the organization. Companies act for the increase of their scope of doing business in market as it increases growth and development of the organization by increasing the profitability and productivity (Ho *et al.*, 2014).

It is evident that the small and medium scaled enterprise has played a crucial role in contributing to the economy and facilitating substantial growth in United Kingdom. Within business market of UK, it can be seen that the emerging businesses tend to engage in healthy competition. Thus, these businesses tend to strive for overall enhancement of organisational development, which eventually is contributing to the economic growth (Piperopoulos and Dimov, 2015). With increasing financial

independence and stability in the market, it is more likely that these set of businesses will contribute towards the overall growth of the particular country. In accordance with the report of House of Commons, it is estimated that 99% of business is the responsibility of the small medium enterprises.

However, the social relevance of these businesses can be majorly attributed to the job scopes which are being available. With more and more small and medium business enterprises being introduced, it is becoming essential that standard workforces are hired to meet the organisational needs and requirements in the most suitable manner. In addition to this, it is likely that more restrictions on hiring employees from outside the country are imposed, leading to better opportunities for the local individuals to attain job scopes. Thus, the rate of unemployment can state to be addressed with growth in this respect. This kind of a business referred to those organization or the companies which has started newly along with having a workforce of less than 250 individuals and the annual turnover is lesser than £25m in UK particularly (Carragher *et al.*, 2015). When a specific business environment is analysed, the major focus is given towards large scale organisations. However, it is needed to be noted that the small and medium scale organization in this context where the entrepreneurship skills is connected. According to recently accumulated data, it has been noted that the numbers of these kind of business organization have considerably increased over a very short duration of time. The growth can note to be evident as the fact is that the small and medium enterprises are responsible for more than 99% of private business sector (Carragher *et al.*, 2015).

Additionally, an approximate of 15.7 million individuals was employed in various departments of small businesses in the year of 2016. The figure is almost 60% of the total employment in UK as per the record. In addition to this, the annual turnover of these small business combined was that of approximate of £1.8 trillion, which is almost close to 46% of total private turnover (Gibson, 2017). Thus, it can be undeniably stated that these organizations are majorly responsible in affecting the overall financial condition of the UK. This research work has enlightened those sensitive areas of small and medium scale entrepreneur before going to enter to the large-scale business market of United Kingdom.

As United Kingdom is a hub of different kinds of business companies by having numerous growing business enterprises and these small enterprises helps to offer different kinds of employment opportunities (Lee *et al.*, 2016). In this context of business environment of UK, UK has the highest rate of growth in terms of the number of increasing small and medium enterprise

which is up to 6% and also helps to create different kind of jobs in the United Kingdom. The growth-oriented enterprise is growing at the rate of more than 20% by hiring greater than 10 employees (Storey, 2016). The applicants or people who were still unemployed and could not managed to get any better job used to start start-up businesses now & this kind of businesses are started to increase the amount of income as profits as much as possible. Working from home has turned into different kinds of new business. People who are able to discover the source of money disagree to go out and earn (Westhead and Solesvik, 2016). Thus, home makers are making much more small-scale businesses as of now in UK. Approximately, 1.5 million people do not go out and work from home and on in its ground and the rest 3.5 million people start their business from home and make it as the main base. Globalization is quite feasible for this kind of small enterprises in the UK (Hillary *et al.*, 2017).

Many researchers have done on small and middle-sized businesses. And as per those researches work it can be said that the small-scale businesses which have sales in international markets are the main causes if the rise in economy in the country. Previous estimate was quite less and now this is 1.5% in the first quarter of the year in terms of providing GDP than any other industries (Botha *et al.*, 2014). 74% of the businesses are quite Size zero business and it means that they do not have any employees. Therefore, they run the business on their own, so these businesses are the setback of the society as they can employ any other person, then the employment will be increased. So, these businesses should increase in order to provide employment to others. In this way the socio-economic conditions can be increased. As of now United Kingdom has 7.2 million businesses among which 90% are based on small & medium scale business (Hillary *et al.*, 2016).

From the above discussion we can get an overview of the environment of the business in UK which is as much as important in terms of the contribution of entrepreneurship. By inserting this within the environment of business a change into the contemporary environment in terms of economy for a country has been pointed out here in this context.

2.8.1 Opportunities for SMEs in the UK:

For SMEs, there are various opportunities in the UK. The governments as well as the financial institutes of the UK have been creating opportunities for the SMEs to grow and develop in the nation. The growth and development of the SMEs is encouraged in the UK as these business organizations contribute to the GDP of the economy. Opportunities to enable the SMEs to develop is a means to promote overall economic growth. If this section of trade grows, it will be able to

transform the overall economic scenario of the country (Rizos *et al*, 2015). According to reports (25th May, 2018), in context of creating opportunities for the SMEs, the National Westminster Bank (NatWest) which is a major retail and commercial bank in the United Kingdom pledged to fund an amount of £1 billion to the SMEs of the country. Over the time period of the next year, the NatWest bank has decided to lend an extra amount of £1 billion to the SMEs in order to enable them to grow and develop their businesses thus creating an opportunity for them (smallbusiness.co.uk). The NatWest bank had been planned and designed in order to help the UK business organizations to invest in manufacturing of goods and services, in technology and development as well. The banking sector of the nation is of the opinion that the SMEs are an integral part of the economy and more opportunities are required to support them. By lending funds to the SMEs, the banks and other financial institutions are providing these SMEs with financial resources and thus preventing financial crises in the businesses. Lack of funding may create financial hindrances for the SMEs which is the most difficult to overcome and may result in the liquidation of the business. Thus, the financial sector of UK is trying to help the SMEs survive in the competitive market (Lazaris and Freeman, 2018).

In the UK, the SMEs are considered to be the lifeblood of the British economy. As per the statistics of the Federation of Small Businesses, in the year 2016, 99.3% of all private firms in the UK were SMEs and these business organizations earned more than £1.8 trillion as their revenues which accounts for 47% of the turnover of the private sector in the UK. A number of small and medium sized businesses get registered in the UK and the economy helps in fostering this industry. Though there are challenges faced by the SMEs which are generally caused by the socioeconomic and political changes in the country such as the impact of late payments and the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) (www.dnb.co.uk). In addition to the opportunities that are received by the SMEs, Brexit will open new global opportunities for the SMEs. These business organisations are trying to create advantage out of the weakening value of pound and exploring the other markets such as Australia, Canada, India, Singapore etc. As the value of pounds have decreased the British products and services has become more affordable for the international consumers which is the reason why the small and medium sized enterprises should focus more on exports. Increasing the exports will ensure the growth of the business organizations and contribute to the overall growth and development of the economy as well (Ekberg *et al*, 2016). The opportunities and challenges for the SMEs after Brexit will depend on the economic scenario of the country and also on the Brexit negotiations between the UK and the European Union. However, although these SME organizations face challenges in the business, they also receive

support for the government of the UK as it contributes to the economy to a great extent (Buchanan *et al*, 2016).

According to a conducted survey of 500 SME entrepreneurs, the majority of them are of the opinion that The UK is great for small businesses as it provides the required support and helps in development of the SME sector (www.dnb.co.uk). The economy of Nepal is highly dependent on the agricultural sector. The agriculture industry employs about more than 78.1 per cent of the total workforce in Nepal and contributes to about 39 percent in the GDP of the economy. The manufacturing industry is rapidly growing in the country. However, there are not many opportunities for the small and medium sized enterprises. But though the opportunities are limited in the country, the contribution of SMEs to the economic growth and development cannot be denied (Das and XiaoFeng, 2017).

The SMEs in the economy of Nepal is an integral part of the country. These business organizations have played an important role in the industrialization of the country. The development of the economy stands as a barrier for the SMEs to receive proper opportunities to grow and develop. The economy of Nepal suffers from many disadvantages which act as obstacles for the country to grow its sector of SMEs as well as the economy as a whole (García-Cabrera *et al*, 2016). There are certain reasons behind the slow growth of the economy which is why there are less opportunities for the SMEs in the country of Nepal. These reasons can be discussed as under:

Low savings- The low savings of the economy is a reason behind the slow economic growth in Nepal. The expenses and the incomes are either equal or the expenses tend to exceed the incomes which does not leave any scope for savings for the people. As a result, planning of SME by the interested people gets delayed period after period.

Low investment- Due to the low savings, there is less amounts of money to be invested in the SME business which hinders the growth of the business.

Low capital formation- If the income of the people do not rise to a certain level there will be no savings and capital formation as of to start a small business or invest in the business for its growth (Wellalage and Locke, 2017).

Besides the reasons that have been mentioned here there are several other reasons such as political instability in the country which hampers the growth of the SMEs. Then there is lack of education or opportunities for education, unequal distribution of health, i.e. the government does not

provide much of awareness in context of health. These reasons contribute to the lack of growth in the economy (Paudel and Tiwari, 2017). As the sector of SMEs do not grow and develop, the country suffers from lack of industrialization as well as lack of employment opportunities for the people. Industrialization and employment are interlinked and in order to bring about growth in both the sectors the government is required to take necessary steps.

As per the official statistical reports of Nepal, by the Department of Cottage and Small Industries (DoCSI). economy's cottage, small and medium enterprises have boomed in the previous decade. By the end of the fiscal year 2015-2016, the number of cottages, small and medium enterprises surged by a percentage of 360.89 to 320,000 which is a significant leap compared to the decade back of fiscal year 2005-2006 which was 69,431. However, there have been many international investors who have cancelled or shunned potential projects in the economy of Nepal because of the unfavourable business environment in the country (thehimalayantimes.com).

This indicates that the growth in the industries as per the data is slow in comparison with the rest of the countries in the world. However, the government is making certain efforts to develop the SMEs in the country with through the implementation of various policies. Also, the country has an increasing number of returnee migrants who possess necessary skills and the capital to invest. This can be considered as a major cause for the fast growth of the small and medium sized industries as well as the cottage industries (Anand, 2015).

2.8.2 Growth of SME from the perception of individual economy, industrial capital & governance:

Entrepreneurs develop new businesses, and new businesses increase jobs opportunities following intensive competition, huge productivity and also some technological changes. A high measured level of entrepreneurship is directly related to high economic growth. However, in reality, if entrepreneurship allows inclusion of any type of informal self-employment, then it can be increased the rate of profit of a company. Under these circumstances, high levels of entrepreneurship would correlate with slow economic growth and lagging development. SMEs contribute to job creation and economic growth which may reduce poverty in developing countries. Maximum job openings are increasing in small scale Industries. Due to increasing number of people, most of them are working from home and thus developing a number of life style businesses. The small-scale businesses which have sales in international markets are the

main cause of the rise of the economy. Manufacturing and construction industries are giving more GDP than any other industries. The increasing rate is more or less 1.4% to 1.5% in the first quarter of the year (Fouzdar and Sachdev 2017).

Small businesses present new employment opportunities and serve as the building blocks of the largest corporations. Small business provides growth innovation to the economy and also helps to stimulate economic growth by providing employment opportunities. Small Enterprises are the base of private sectors as well as the source of innovation and diversification. Small and Medium sized company can provide employment and taxes. When SMEs is a part of private sector, public and private policy supports them. SMEs plays an important role in Economy and society. They have massive involvement in economic growth, community organization, employment, innovation and skills and development which act as catalyst of any company (Azarloo *et al.* 2017). 95% of enterprise and 60%-70% of employment are under Small medium entrepreneurship and it sharing new job offers to the Organisation for economic Co-operation and development economies. (OECD) The importance and contribution of small firms enhances as the economies of scales reduces. Some problems like lack of funding or credit availability, problems in utilization of technology, constrained managerial capabilities, regulatory weight down and low yield, they face frequently. So, government help is necessary to flourish these organizations. They have been taken various steps towards SMEs. The SMEs has been supported and encouraged by government policies following terms and conditions, infrastructure support, technology up-gradation, preferential access to credit, preferential policy support, etc. GDP of SMEs is significant in terms of its share in case of total value added (Azarloo *et al.* 2017). SMEs reduce the problem of imbalance in the balance of payment accounts through its export promotion. The mottos of SMEs are equal distribution of income and wealth to the employee. Small sector sometimes provides opportunities to a large number of capable and potential entrepreneurs who are deprived of appropriate opportunities. SMEs can reap the benefits of lean production and can find new cost-efficient techniques of lean production. They also use small capital towards productive use as small units can use resources with full of efficiency. SMEs more resources will be employed by large number of labour force (Felzensztein *et al.* 2015).

The success and steadiness in the small and medium scale entrepreneurs are directly linked to sustainability. The random factors are responsible for this sustenance of the small and medium scale entrepreneurs, although this can be explored further for deeper understanding regarding the same. The implementation of the law of proportional effect cannot be implemented in a

convenient way so that it could bring out the most effective outcome (Felzensztein *et al.* 2015). As per as the economic point of view is concerned, it can be assessed that a subsequent investment in the area of human capital interplays with the increment related to growth and competitiveness. The development in the investment within the human capital takes place through the labour supply and physical capital (Azarloo *et al.* 2017). The small and medium scale entrepreneurs face many difficulties while implementing numerous ideas, techniques and loads of uncertainties and challenges in the context of the market of United Kingdom. A large-scale entrepreneur does not face such uncertainties and threat because the large-scale entrepreneurs are well-equipped enough to tackle those issues and have suitable damage control methods (Brunswicker and Vanhaverbeke, 2015). GDP growth rate of a particular country is boosted as the earnings of the small and medium scale enterprises contribute the biggest portion of the economy in market of United Kingdom. Two significant determinant factors are size and tenure which determines how a small and medium scale enterprise will perform under the pressure of the existing challenges and the potentiality of the business to utilize upcoming and existing opportunities to allow sustainable growth of a small and medium scale enterprise in local as well as foreign market (Colombo *et al.* 2014). This also enables the efficiency of a small and medium scale entrepreneur to start a new business in an entirely new business environment.

In this research project, the boundaries regarding a new business by Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs in a larger market like that of United Kingdom will be explored. The factors influencing the new business venture by Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs in United Kingdom will be identified and assessed well. The ways, through which small and medium scale entrepreneurs can enter foreign markets having larger business arena as United Kingdom, will be studied well to find the advantages and disadvantages of the same. Two most important attributes of a new business, scopes and challenges, need to be understood well to implement better ideas (Colombo *et al.* 2014).

To make sure the business is performing well and the business operations are seamless, the most necessary and significant factors namely education and training are required. The significance of these two factors is important enough to ensure proper flow of business operations within the organisation (Trianni *et al.* 2016). Through training and education, the employees from different levels of the organisation becomes efficient enough to handle business related issues and ensure smooth flow of work. The development and research process require a certain cost which are facilitating nature and initiates innovation as well. The access upon new context is extended with

the help of the external consultations as well as other relevant activities. All these new as well as innovative ideas include knowledge transfer, cooperation, and exports (Kotelnikov, 2014).

2.8.3 Sustainable growth management among SMEs:

To establish sustainability and growth in small and medium scale entrepreneurs, suitable management process should be adopted to ensure accurate decision-making as well as problem solving abilities. Also, while implementing or revising the organisational structure of the small and medium scale entrepreneurial ventures, proper strategic configuration needs to be analyzed in order to obtain the desired outcome. Innovation, cooperation, education and export are important factors which are correlated with the idea of implementing new business in larger foreign markets (Herliana, 2015). All these aspects greatly affect the sustainability and growth rate of a business flourishing in an entirely new business environment. Both the management and government, which are important determinant factors of a business, are being interplayed by these four aspects of business.

To acquire sustainable business growth a business must conduct proper analysis and identify possible business challenges. Also, suitable preventive measures should be implemented and adopted by studying the challenges and the factors associated with it thoroughly. A business generally has a number of factors which influences the business in determining the rate of growth of the same. Proper assessment of those factors can lead to a better establishment process and maintenance of the business concerned (Legg *et al.* 2015). With selective business strategies and suitable techniques any business venture can achieve success and yield tons of revenues. To provide the business with proper strategy implementation platform, the concerned business environment should be favourable enough. When it comes to start business in a larger country, challenges faced by small and medium scale entrepreneurs are multiplied than the usual (Herliana, 2015).

The small and medium scale entrepreneurs belonging to developing countries, such as Nepal, find it hard to adapt to the changing much developed business environment having a superior and very much competitive business market (Ciravegna *et al.* 2014). Through this research project it can be assessed whether the current business scenario of United Kingdom is suitable enough for the new business ventures to grow, especially in the context of Nepalese entrepreneurs. The research project is focused on assessing factors related to business establishment by Nepalese entrepreneurs in foreign market, such as United Kingdom. From this research a deep understanding on the

relationship between the business environment of United Kingdom and Nepalese entrepreneurs will be obtained. Further research will be conducted to assess the identified issues of the matter concerned (Ciravegna *et al.* 2014).

Having a decentralized ownership structure is highly appreciable for a small and medium scale entrepreneurial venture. As the decentralized ownership structure is the most predominant one, a varied and wide range of owners and managers are involved in these organisations. However, achieving sustainable growth is difficult as it is having certain barriers such as, decisiveness of quality factors and the effectiveness of education (Bruhn *et al.* 2018). Both of these should be eliminated or reduced to greater extent in order to attain sustainable growth for the small and medium scale enterprises. Incorporating business consultation and receiving government support are two of the effective ways to combat with ineffectiveness of the small and medium scale businesses (Regnier, 2017). Rapidly fluctuating market demand and an overly competitive market of larger countries are major reasons of downfall of small and medium scale businesses.

2.8.4 Environmental factors that determine the impact upon SMEs:

By the term environmental factors, it is likely to be referred to as those external elements that tend to have a determining impact upon the business processes. There are many factors which play a significant role upon the business operations, some can be controlled through potential strategic processes and some are termed to be out of control (Welter *et al.* 2017). There are four different categories among which the environmental factors can be typically classified, the social, legal, political and economic elements. It is the small and medium sized business enterprises which get affected the most through the specified factors from diverse aspects.

Social:

Every business organization is established with a fundamental objective in mind to make their processes directed towards definite social surroundings. They intend to have a significant and strong impact through their business propositions which shall befall upon the societal environment. The social factors tend to play a huge role in the success and failure of the business establishment and its subsequent sustainability. The societal movements taking place in a particular demographic parameter shall have a direct impact upon the business operations. There are frequent transitions taking place in the morals, values and ethical basis of the people residing in a particular social paradigm. Such a significant change in terms of the public values shall impose a different attitude towards the business organizations (Burns, 2016). It is ultimately the

people's perception that matter and makes a significant influence upon the organization. It can be held as an instance that the practices of the people tend to influence the ideas and concepts developed and incorporated within the business and vice and versa shall take place as well. It is found that when a certain business intends to establish in terms of putting up a small casual dining restaurant, the social trends that seem to work upon them must be taken into consideration. The society is inclined towards consuming healthy and nutritious food and such habits are required to be fostered through the business practices. Hence while setting up the restaurant the first thing that is to be kept in mind is the trend and habit of the people which is likely to act as a determining factor. Incorporation of newness through innovative strategies might also be welcomed but it is necessary for the SMEs to be able to address the preferences of the people within the specific society to gain popularity and acceptance. A subsequent research work needs to be conducted so that the societal environment can be evaluated for understanding the tastes, preferences, likes and dislikes of the people. The business strategies shall be constructed following such guidelines. This shall help them to address the societal objectives correctly and also simultaneously allow the business organizations to adjust their operations (Blackburn, 2016). They are also able to promote alternative values to be able to fit into the current offerings rather than compensating with the trends. It is therefore necessary and recommended for every SME to carry an overall positive image to be able to grasp the ability to attract the local workers.

Political:

There are a number of significant factors that tend to have a strong impact upon the business strategies and the operations carried on. Keeping in context with the political paradigm, it is necessary for the small and medium sized companies to establish their interactions with local government and authoritative agencies. Every business organization wishes to have a healthy and positive working relationship along with the mayor and the city council members who are operating within the city or town. On establishing a positive hold among the supreme authorities and power-heads of the regional and local operation area it becomes extremely easy for the organizational managers to influence various operating aspects (McGowan *et al.* 2015). Having legal flexibility renders the business to run on a much smooth manner adhering to influence laws and codes that tend to impact upon the business. This helps the business to expand their reach and accessibility towards local funding and provision of tax subsidies where political interference is of much significance (McGowan *et al.* 2015).

Legal:

There is interplay of factors which tend to be intrinsically associated and interdependent on one another. The legislative aspects are bound to be related with those of the political factors. The political landscape tends to extend a great impact befalling upon the legal environment that is necessary to be encompassed by each SME. The laws or city ordinance getting altered in a particular place where the business is established is necessary to have a direct impact upon the business activities. For an instance there might be hindrances in running the business following stipulated objectives (Spigel, 2017). It might be possible that the target set by the business organizations is to incorporate the teens. A sudden requirement might be raised towards young people for joining the curfew that shall include people below the age of 18. Such a legislative action of keeping the youngsters within home by 11pm may tend to significantly impact the operation hours in a negative way. The health and safety regulations are found to have a direct impact falling upon the restaurants and the food vendors (Spigel, 2017).

Economic:

The economic condition that is prevalent within the local region of the business operations is likely to get hindered due to shift in the nature of the local economy (Williams and Vorley, 2015). It is necessary that purchasing behaviour is found to be prominent when the economic conditions are not that strong or the rate of unemployment is high. A greater buying tendency can be perceived if the sell-price is lowered and the goods are value priced in nature. In case of poor economies people tend to have increased concerns regarding the budget. The economic conditions need to be favourable for both the companies as well as the people who are targeted for the sales. The luxury goods and services are found to thrive more when the economies are in a good position. The employment of the people is necessary to sustain stability among the business conducts. The loan interest rates are likely to be changing in nature which abides by the banking regulations (Siegel and Wright, 2015). These tend to be the different economic factors that seem to have a strong impact befalling upon the small business. A poor economic condition can be noted to have greater adverse impacts upon the budget systems.

When small and medium scale entrepreneurs try to enter a larger market of a developed country, obstacles are bound to appear, and Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs trying to enter

the flourishing market of United Kingdom are no exception. There are certain determinants which are responsible for the success or failure of new business in the competitive market of United Kingdom. The environmental factors affecting the growth of small and medium enterprises has various dimensions which includes heterogeneity, dynamics, hostility and munificence, these are referred as external determinants (Lawal and Akingbade, 2018). The companies which are high than those of the strategic interventions and managerial motivations, are developing with the help of these external determinants. Centralized, formalized and separation kind of organisation structures are adopted. The pre-defined business strategies include two definite categories such as cost leadership strategies and focus strategies. The structure of the supply contains the configuration of power of the supplier as well as technological confusion (Khaliq *et al.* 2015).

One of the major determinant factors has to be the policies implemented by Government of the particular country, in this case United Kingdom. Government policies of tax kind, customs kind, financial kind and export incentive kind. The broader classification of determinants comes up with two factors such as internal factors and external factors (Chege *et al.* 2015). The internal factors include the marketing potentials, entrepreneurial characteristics, technical capacities and management capacities. There are several other important factors which contribute to the growth of small and medium scale entrepreneurial ventures in the market of foreign market, such as, cash flow, debt, the amount and intensity of research development and labour productivity. According to Parker (2018), there are four categories of the factors impacting upon the growth of small and medium enterprises – the growth motivation of the owner, growth management, the extent of access towards various resources and market demand. All these factors have great impact on determining the future of small and medium size businesses.

2.8.4 Impact micro businesses in the economy:

Williams and Vorley (2015), states that the annual turnover is almost 50 million in any small or medium sized company because a smaller number of people are employed and it is indeed independent and non-subsidiary firm. The number of employees is quite different in different places such as, USA there are no place to recognise SME. In terms of Europe less than 250 employees or workers work in a medium sized enterprise. In this the discussion is about the impact of SMEs on UK economy. However, in 2014 there were 5.2 million micro businesses in the UK and the rate of employment in SMEs was 15.7 million and this is actually 60% of all kinds of private sector's employment in the UK (Bertoni, et al; 2016). SMEs companies are now all around the UK, in the year 2005 the employment number was 3.5 million and now it reaches

about 5 million and there are only 6% of SMEs in UK that is growing in increasingly (Bertoni, et al; 2016). Past businesses are dropping in these present times and people are trying to develop new business that are increasing rapidly and the rate of profit is quite higher in terms of SMEs. Now these days people are working from home and making significant amount of money to maintain the standard of living. According to Williams and Vorley (2015), about 1.5 million of people are now able to work from and they earning indeed in a proper way and it is much better for Homemakers who do not go out for work and they are able to work from their house. Almost 3.5 million people managed to start their own business at home. Therefore, the SMEs, plays an important role in production network and in the growth and development of the economy. As a result, this can be helpful to encourage team spirit and to take better decision. SME companies create more employment opportunities than other companies in the UK.

2.9 The entrepreneurial challenge in UK:

2.9.1 The entrepreneurial challenge for Emerging Companies:

Entrepreneurship is that construct which tends to come along with an array of challenges. It can be rewarding as well as punishing in certain aspects. These are mostly found to be a combination of harsh as well as rewarding challenges. This is such a situational barrier which is experienced by most of the entrepreneurs who have been into the business for ages. It is itself a challenge to make the business earn profits by exceeding the competitors to be able to adjust and match up to established brands (Doherty *et al.* 2014). There are certain challenges which are faced especially by the newly emerging entrepreneurs which are difficult to be overcome. There is need to be cautious about the factors that shall affect the new entrepreneurs which shall become difficult to be overcome in certain matters. According to Chege *et al.* (2015), the determining factors are discussed as follows:

Abandonment of career options:

It is never possible to maintain all the business requisites in an effective manner and opt for other career options in a simultaneous manner (Frederick *et al.* 2015). For business to be carried out in a successful manner the entrepreneur is necessary to be possessing dedicated and determined state of mind. It is essentially possible for an enterprise to be nourished and monitored during its initial phase of operation. During inception of business projects, it is possible to take out time and give time for the career options other than business. It is therefore necessary to be kept in mind that if the business is expected to grow and prosper there needs to appropriate concentration and put the

unidirectional focus upon the project. It is often regarded as an unstable and insecure option of career when a stable job is being quit for establishing business especially in a different location altogether. The business prospects are considered to be unpredictable and uncertain in many cases which might carry scary results for the newly established entrepreneurs. It is therefore necessary that an in-detail study of the challenges that might up on the way of business operations need to be evaluated (Guerrero *et al.* 2015). A steady outcome can be received through long terms benefits if the opportunities are appropriately explored. Along with the empirical studies and a gross knowledge of the previous success tips for establishment of business it is also necessary to follow the instinctual logics in order to run a profitable entrepreneurship project.

Financing:

One of the major difficulty areas encompassed by the newly established entrepreneurs is the acquisition of the appropriate amount of funding. Experienced entrepreneurs are also unsure and hence hesitate to provide fund towards the newly established businesses (Schaper, 2016). The experienced entrepreneurs are expected to have a pool of capital from their previous ventures of business. They might have sold out some of the previous capitals and acquired steady stream of revenues which they can use to fund their newly established business in their cash flows.

With experience the business conducts are not completely in vain, as even if they undergo loses in their first attempt, they are likely to conduct investments, established contacts, connections with the clients (André and Pache, 2016). These factors shall lead to be determining agents to help them support their new business venture that they plan to establish. There are a number of hurdles that need to be overcome while starting as a new entrepreneur. They require beginning from the scratch and also need to involve themselves in elaborate networking processes. It is from the crazy efforts made by the new entrepreneurs that potential funding options can be explored to be able to get an idea to use them when needed (André and Pache, 2016).

Teambuilding:

As of a start it is although essential but extremely crucial as a point of determination to be able to prepare a team that can be relied upon for all the further ventures of business. It becomes equally crucial for the new entrepreneur to be able to choose the right personnel who can form the

effective team, however making the entire process much stressful and difficult. It is never enough to merely find the right people and pick them up to form the team by assigning them their specific job roles (Lee, 2014). It is therefore required on the part of the entrepreneur to judge their cost towards the business. The cultural fit needs to be assessed along with the impact they are likely to have upon the overall team. It imposes extreme pressure upon the entrepreneurs and aim to fill their positions as soon as possible.

Being the visionary:

After deciding upon becoming a competent business entrepreneur it is necessary to come up with different innovative ideas to establish a prospective business. However, on coming in terms with a competitor in the emerging market it is likely that certain crucial and responsible steps are necessary to be taken. It is possible to give rise to certain impenetrable obstacles which may cause hindrance towards the smooth functioning of the business proposition (Jones *et al.* 2014). On encountering with such obstacles, it is necessary to confront them with confidence. The entrepreneur is necessary to come up with potential alternative plan that shall help them to sustain and move further. It might seem as an oxymoron to show the extreme level of preparedness to be able to evolve with an instant creative thinking. However, this sort of readiness is quite expected along with the foresightedness that needs to be possessed by the entrepreneurs as they do not have the luxury to waste the time (Jones *et al.* 2014).

Handling the unknown:

One of the most uncertain aspects that cause fear to the new entrepreneurs is whether their business shall attain sustainability or not (Ácset *al.* 2016). Along with this the related aspects that are a matter of concern are the profitability yielded through their business. How accepting shall the customers be towards the new array of products introduced in the market by them is a matter of concern Shall the entrepreneurs be able to provide an appropriate level of pay check towards establishing steadiness within the business conducts Even if the business proposition initiates with a great idea and brilliant conception strategies it is most likely that no solid answer shall be acquired in response to the above stated questions. It becomes therefore a considerable challenge to be able to deal with volatility.

Loneliness:

The entrepreneurs are rarely associated with issues like loneliness and hence there is a scarce expectation for the same to take place. It is something that is least expected on the part of the

business owners to be able to possess the preparedness until it happens with them in person. Being an entrepreneur, itself makes them lonely. It is encompassed as a singular position hence there is no scope of getting teammates in the same contemporary stage (Ahmad, 2015). They need to rely upon themselves and the instinctual forces that tend to keep them alert about the anticipated threats and challenges that are likely to be encountered by them. The hours of toil are necessary to be much higher those of the employed workers. There shall be limited time left for the personal space and give time towards their families.

Rule-making:

It is fun to play the role of the powerhead and be the boss until there are serious responsibilities that one has to manifest. It is inevitable that one shall encounter with enforcing acts at some point of their business conducts. Sooner or later an entrepreneur is expected to come to terms with formulation of rules and regulations to implement appropriate strategies for the workers to follow. Such impositions are necessary to setup the climate for the prospective business. There is an extreme need for a standard protocol to be maintained while filing a complaint about the co-workers on the basis of which they shall be evaluated (Zapalska and Brozik, 2018). Such formulation of protocols which take the shape of rules and regulations are certainly not easy to be framed. However, they are such aspects of the business which are inevitable and have to be encompassed.

Decision-making:

Business is all about the interplay of correct decisions taken at the right point of time. While dealing with the increasing number of challenges on conducting the different business operations, decision making is encountered to be the stressful of all of them. It is necessary that each of the new entrepreneurs are made aware of the major obstacles that shall be impacting upon the business operations in a direct manner. An increasing number of decisions are necessary to be undertaken by the new entrepreneurs as they are yet going through the phase of instability and insecurity. Sometimes these decisions are not initiated intentionally but need to be encompassed forcibly (Muñoz and Kibler, 2016). These decisions are likely to range from the short-term to the long-term ones including the big ones and the minor impacting the company. In terms of encompassing the newly established enterprises it is most naturally expected to undergo a phenomenon such as decision fatigue.

Most of the new entrepreneurs are not found to be expected about the stress of handling the next level of evolution and hence become confronted with such a real-life phenomenon of decision fatigue. Initiating and running any successful business prospect is necessary to face challenges. It is therefore necessary that the owners consider a number of aspects by the owner of the enterprise (Regmi and Gautam, 2016).

An owner needs to be cautious about the challenges that might have significant implications acting upon the business. According to Regmi and Gautam (2016), The following challenges are encountered by the small business mostly which tend to have their impact befalling upon different sections of the business operations.

➤ Taxes:

Adhering to the small and medium business enterprises it is most likely that one of the single costs are associated with the tax issues. These single costs are necessary to be met by the SMEs. The entrepreneurs, business owners and sole traders are anxious about reducing the taxation amount as this shall implicate upon reduced liabilities, especially in a commercial environment which increasingly competitive in nature (Paudelet *al.* 2017). Tax is that inevitable aspect of the business processes which are viewed as not the most exciting part. It is rather perceived as a burden upon the small or medium sized business. They often seem to have a complaint that such businesses do not get the opportunity to take benefits of the tax breaks. This automatically gives rise to certain criteria that needs to be fulfilled to gain benefits and avoid loses in terms of taxation on business. It is required to fulfil whether the business project is set up using desired level of trading structures. It is simultaneously required to access if the owner is eligible to receive Research and Development in terms of tax relief for the running of the business. It is also required to ensure whether tax relief claims are possible in terms of purchasing the new machineries or business operation equipment's.

➤ Cyber security and data protection:

The small businesses are found to rely increasingly upon the technological assistances. It is likely that the data related with them are necessary to be reviewed adhering to data protection processes and implementations for right transitions to take place within the business operations. It is on the basis of the recent government estimates that breach of data cost an average amount of approximately £310,000 by the SMEs.

➤ Increase in wage rates and rising payroll costs:

With the emergence and implementation of National Minimum Wage, the small businesses are going to be the primary target which shall also be influenced by the introduction of the National Living Wage (Regmi and Gautam, 2016). Whatever sectors are included within the business they are likely to employ staffs who are working on the National Minimum Wage. Hence it becomes inevitable as a consequence that the payroll costs are raising in a significant manner in the recent months and years.

➤ Errors in payroll:

There are obvious areas where expenditures in the course of business processes are out of the control such as the incorporation of the National Living Wages along with the onset of the auto enrolment. However, there are many other aspects through savings can be restored. One of the key aspects includes the minimization of the number of payroll errors. The management of the payrolls are necessary to be conducted with respect to the daunting prospects. However, it is the payroll adhering to which the employers are necessary to get right. There are subsequent payroll mistakes which give rise to crackdowns which tend to affect the small business. With regard to providing compliance towards the employees there were researches conducted upon HMRC which yielded £737m collection as an outcome of investigations (Regmi and Gautam, 2016).

These are collections taken into the companies for tax avoidance and error correction. Taking to total UK payroll into consideration it is likely to take an account of 89% including both the small business as well as the larger businesses (Thapa, 2015). There is interplay of a number of interconnected factors which tend to determine the correct payroll position for the definite business. It becomes therefore difficult to adapt to the correct payroll position due to the complications incorporated within the process. There are casual workers, persistent form of changes taking place within the wage rates and the continued implementation of auto enrolment in terms of small business which are likely to of getting caught. There is a lot more scope for payroll errors to establish their implications which are expected to extend beyond the financial implications. The subsequent errors identified within the payroll can potentially cause detrimental impact upon the morale of the staffs, impact the range of productivity and ultimately expand their impact upon the business performances. It is to be regarded as the trigger point when the small business setup is dependent and remains obligatory towards employers (Kern and Müller-Böker, 2015). This may be considered as the point when payroll issues shall be necessitated to be outsourced. This is likely to be regarded as an affordable and effectual option for the business prospect.

2.9.2 Challenges faced by entrepreneur in growing a business in UK

With specific effect to the small and medium sized enterprises there are certain prominent challenges that are encompassed. These include the following aspects:

- **Funding:**

One of the common barriers that are faced in terms of carrying out the business operations is related to accessing funding. Many of the visionary entrepreneurs were trying to cite the issues concerning such matters (Coles *et al.* 2015). They have been noticing the change taking place in the last few years. Tracking the yearly records, it could be found that it was a tough time for the investment standpoint. Although an extremely supportive business environment can be created and established concerning the SMEs there are issues related to funding within the business communities.

- **Competition:**

The visionaries were also found to reflect upon the challenge faced in the form of competitors. It is found to be extremely challenging in the presence of the enormous competitive environment (Saarinen and Nepal, 2016). They tend reflect upon the changes that take place in the business strategies and plans that have to be laid down in order to incorporate different ideas with dynamic people. The products need to be innovative and hence help in the process of innovation. It is necessary that establishing success by striking a competitive advantage shall enable the companies to move ahead and faster by adhering to smarter avenues. After empirical research conducted to evaluate the greatest challenge faced by the SMEs the survey results indicate that it is the competitors that they consider as the greatest threat.

- **Recruitment:**

It is necessary for every start up business to have a strong base rather than aiming to spread their enterprise. In order to strengthen their foundation, the primary requisite seems to be the resource personnel. The employees of the firm are to be regarded as the greatest assets of the company. It is they who run the business and carry out business operations which yield success and profitability for the growth and development for the organizations. It is therefore indicated that there was a significant lack in employee resources which posed shortage in their abilities (Jha *et al.* 2017). There is considerable difficulty faced by the resources in getting the right skills. This can be resulting to cause big issues for the SMEs.

- **Leadership:**

Leadership is found to be that driving force which governs the business operations and keeps them in order. A business project which is led by expert and a skilful manager is likely to be gaining prosperity. Most of the SMEs are led by stringent leadership styles where the control is concentrated in the hands of the manager single handily. This is by far encountered as one of the most significant challenges to encompass the right measures in terms of governance, business operations and the related decision making. There are instances where the company is witnessed to suffer long-term loses just because of the wrong choice of leader and the subsequent inappropriate leadership styles. It can be understood that proper mentoring needs to be performed with adequate manifestation of management roles (Nepal and Jamasb, 2015). This shall allow the company from being affected by the heinous impact of “accidental leadership”. From the empirical surveys conducted for assessing the effectiveness of the employers by their employees it could be generated that adequacy of skills are not implemented. About 71% of the employees have clearly indicated that the employers could manifest a better performance in terms of playing the role of a manager and a leader. It can be understood that training for managers is equally essential as that of the employees.

- **International competitors:**

It is very obvious that while any business project is aimed to be expanded the level of complexity is likely to get widened. An entrepreneur who was easily dealing with the stakeholders in running his business operations have already established a known network (Spence *et al.* 2018). The entrepreneur is likely to come out of their comfort zone and operate in a challenging circumstance in order to endure the international level within the business operations. There are tough challenges and competitions faced from the competitors residing in the overseas. It is found that the British businesses are competing on the world stage and hence facing increased competition from dynamic Asian entrepreneurs. It is necessary for Britain to outgrow by stepping into the developed world which might include the US and Germany as well.

Entrepreneurship skills for growth-oriented business:

Entrepreneurial skill is a definite characteristic for SMEs creativity, ability to facing challenges, social skills are important to build an effective business plan. To be a good entrepreneur one should be disciplined, confidence, open minded, self-starter, competitive and also creative personality. These skills improve the career path, leadership capabilities and also the shape of individuals who

are engaged with their communities (Kimosop *et al.* 2016). A person needs entrepreneurial knowledge and improved personal capabilities to become a successful entrepreneur and this entrepreneur knowledge are essential for every people to become successful. It helps to recognise the success or failure of business development and the improvement of core competitiveness of enterprises. A successful entrepreneur helps to improve the economy in the country which creates success (Colombo *et al.*; 2014). In order to become a true entrepreneur person, need to work much harder, they are much focused in life and self-motivated and quite dedicated to the work.

The understanding of the skills related to the entrepreneurship skills in terms of growth with respect to the business is mainly referred to the small and medium Enterprises in terms of the development of the economy of a country which is not ignorable. At present days, various challenges related to the current economy has been faced by many countries around the world and for this reason entrepreneurial activity is increased in order to fulfil the goal of the government of nation (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Entrepreneurship is relevant to the economic development and it can be stated that, the education and the program of training which works as an opportunity which plays a key role in order to cultivate the future entrepreneurs and also helps to develop the capabilities of the existing one for the growth of the business to a greater extent in order to archive the level of success (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). This concept of the entrepreneurial business mainly promotes the activity of creation, development of the innovation which may be in terms of technology also which starts with a small and medium enterprise in general.

The government of UK and other countries across this world admit the positive effect of the creation of new businesses can lead to open up new levels of employment as well. By the same time entrepreneurship can able to provide benefits in terms of growth of social and economy, in terms of fulfilment of an individual by breaking all the barriers of class, age, gender, sexual orientation, and race at the present situation of the market (Mason *et al.*, 2014). It also enhances the knowledge about the perspective of entrepreneurship in terms of the development of the economy. The study of the required skills of entrepreneur helps to make various policies of business and also in others respective as well.

According to Kimosop *et al.*, (2016), In general, skills have been required in order to solve various problems in an efficient manner which should be effective for the growth of the business. These problems are the difficulties in the way of getting success which also categories into different factors such as external and internal barriers which are the results of various measurement that has been taken already. In external barriers, there are many obstacles which may arise in the smooth

way of business which is growth oriented. It basically includes condition of the market of labour, structure of the market in terms of competition, policies of the government, climate in terms of economy, rules and regulations and lastly the access of the market. And internal barrier includes some motivational factors which can able to help the growth of business, capability of management which is one of the most important factors, funds, depending upon the orders, capacity of marketing, sales and the service of the product along with the quality. In order to deal with these barriers, there is a need of some specific set of skills in an entrepreneur which are also known as entrepreneurship skills. It can be mainly divided into two categories; one is technical skills and another one is skills of management and both of them are equally important in order to resolve problem which are related to the growth of the business. The development of skills is a qualitative method not quantitative (Oecd.org., 2018). By considering all the review of literature which had been already published, we can make a required set of skills to be an entrepreneur. Many research workers had been working on it and they also presented some basic requirement which should be included in this set of skills.

Entrepreneurship skills include inner disciplines, the capability of taking risk, managing innovation, orientation of change and endurance. And these factors generated by the characteristics of the entrepreneur such as mental ability, having clear aim and objectives, ability of communication, self-confidence, having high level of energy etc. having a good mental ability means the person have a good level of intelligence which comprise creative thinking (Colombo *et al*; 2014). This creative thought helps to analyze various problem and situations as well in order to deal with them. Having a clear objective helps to assess the nature of the product in terms of quality and other aspects. In order to be a successful entrepreneur of growth-oriented business, aim and objective should be set before starting any kind of new things related to the product or service or in order develop the management procedure of it which also leads to the generation of inner disciplines within the work place. As an entrepreneur, the person requires lots of determination and also always in a look-out for new business environment in which their business operations can be incorporated seamlessly and can draw bigger profits. It is an undeniable fact that the entrepreneurial personality can be reflected in regards with motivation and mindset of the leaders. The individuals who tend to have abilities to propose business methods as well as innovative ideas to implement those are more likely to utilise their personality traits in order to provide their venture the required edge (Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). In addition to this, step by step consideration of fulfilment of specific targets was also done.

The good execution of numbers of techniques is another important point of consideration and a fact also that the communication skills possessed by both the business leaders are effective. It becomes evident by the standard relationships maintained by both the individuals not only within their respective business but also in proper sync with the individuals in external environment (Kimosop *et al.*, 2016). The responsibility of setting specific goals and craving the path of attaining the same are undertaken by the individuals is the one of the key parts of being an entrepreneur.

The other skills such as technical skill which also be necessary for the production in terms of business, management skills which is required in order to manage the day-to-day basis management of the workplace in terms of administration of the company, personal maturity skills which has an involvement of accountability, self-awareness and also the creativity skills. These skills are important in order to identify the ability of the labours and also help in assessment of the situation of market which defines the opportunity of the business as it is important to the growth-oriented business. It also helps in order to create a vision and the appreciation in the way of business as well as in the life of an entrepreneur (Colombo *et al.*; 2014). Technical skills mainly include specific operational skills to the industry, communication, designs, work related to research and development and the environmental observation. Whereas management skills basically include planning for the growth of business, procedure of decision making, motivating labours and employees of the business organization along with self-motivation, marketing and sales in order to grow the profitability of the business. As it is a growth-oriented business so, making profit should be one of the main objective of the entrepreneur which needs entrepreneurship skills as well and managing of finance of the business organization which is a vital thing for a small & medium enterprise (Lackéus *et al.*, 2015).

These unique skills of an entrepreneur of a particular business organization provide an overview of the climate of the business which helps to form a large picture of the existing business for the near upcoming future as well. There are various theories which can be adopted in order to manage the entrepreneurship skills for the growth of the business in any country around the world such as UK. There is a theory of “entrepreneurship with specialization and business transfer” which is developed by Holmes and Schmitz date mentioned the skill of working in a team is also plays a vital role in this respect in order to create a qualified system of management which provides the direction of the growth & success for the organization of business (Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). An entrepreneur is also a leader of the organization so with that respect he or she should also possess the leadership quality also.

On the basis of the discussion, it can be observed that the performances of the growth-oriented business organization in the country of UK or other around the world is dependent on the entrepreneurship skills highly by which despite of facing a lot of challenges or threats, the small and medium scale business ventures keep rising high & contributes a large amount of financial support to the economy of the particular country (Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). These are mainly responsible for determining the rate of growth and the rate of performance of a new small and medium size business in a larger and highly competitive market basically.

2.10 Immigrant entrepreneurs in UK:

Entrepreneurial skills are something which is not only beneficial for that particular person but also for the country where the person is residing in, as most of the time entrepreneurs aim to set up the business venture in their own area or country. But sometimes the entrepreneurs are interested in exploring the unexplored boundaries, in other words they try to enter a new foreign market. The reason is mostly giving their product or service a global recognition and also yielding more profits and taking foreign currency home. The entrepreneurs from developing as well as developed countries always try to enter a larger market in order to gain more customers and global recognition (Jones *et al.* 2017). The motivation working behind the entrepreneurs for entering a foreign market is as followed:

- To gain more profits
- Competitive pressures
- To introduce a unique set of products and services
- Production capacity
- To acquire more market opportunities
- Sales has declined in the home country
- Economies of scale
- Tax advantages
- Technology related advantages

When a business enters foreign market, it faces a lot of challenges to establish itself. Especially when the market is a larger one and the product or service does not belong to a unique category, hence, would be facing tough competition from already established brands. Thus, conducting a study on the foreign market, the entrepreneur is planning to explore, is a must.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Vinogradova and Jorgensen, 2017.

Fig 1: The reasons for foreigners to come to UK

Source: (Vinogradova and Jorgensen, 2017).

United Kingdom is a hub of small and medium scale entrepreneurial ventures, over 90% of the total businesses of the country is small and medium enterprises. Among all those enterprises, some of the enterprises are set up by immigrant entrepreneurs. In United Kingdom, there are approx 456,073 immigrant entrepreneurs, representing more than 155 countries around the world. They are responsible for implementing 464,527 businesses altogether within the country, positioned as founders' directors (Ram *et al.* 2017). A vast number of those immigrant entrepreneurs while working for an established company or having spent a large amount of time in such a company. So, it can be assessed that some immigrants who came to United Kingdom to look for a new job or after being posted from their office, eventually started their own business after sometime. It can be said that they utilised this time gap by researching the market of United Kingdom and analyzing the relevant factors in order to obtain a stiff ground before starting their new venture.

According to the surveys conducted on the immigrant entrepreneurs in United Kingdom, the immigrants are three times more equipped with entrepreneurial skills than that of the people born in United Kingdom (Vinogradov and Jørgensen, 2017). 15.4% of immigrant entrepreneurs are launching new business ventures in United Kingdom comparing to only 5.3% of lifelong residents of United Kingdom. The country is having two categories of people; one is UK-born people who never lived abroad and other one is people belonging to other countries are living in United Kingdom for job or study purpose. Within last three years it has been found that the new business ventures which have been launched in United Kingdom are mostly headed by the people from second category (Chavan and Taksa, 2017). Moreover, the highest level of TEA (Total Early-stage Entrepreneurial Activities) is shown by the immigrants living in United Kingdom. According to Aston Business School Professor Mark Harth, the immigrants who were born and live in the United Kingdom but who have lived abroad for some time have a much higher rate than people who have always lived in the country, and the difference seems to have increased in 2015 compared to previous years (Yamoah and Johnson, 2020).

United Kingdom is a hub for start-ups and as per the market research of 2015, it has been found that almost 6 lacs new companies has started in that particular year. A survey conducted in 2014 found that one in every seven small and medium scale business ventures in United Kingdom was having an immigrant entrepreneur. That means the effectiveness of immigrant entrepreneurs is increasing, along with the total number of start-ups in the country (Falavigna *et al.* 2017). Studies have shown that United Kingdom is currently having a large number of immigrant entrepreneurs from 155 different countries, with some of them having more than one business ventures launched there. Surinder Arora was born in Punjab and came to United Kingdom at the age of 13. Now he is at his 50s and one of the most successful hoteliers in United Kingdom, with 16 hotels under the brands like Arora, Hilton, Radisson and Sofitel (Yamoah and Johnson, 2020). It makes it easier to understand that not just now; immigrant entrepreneurs have been part of the UK economy since a long time the names of a few well-known immigrant entrepreneurs of United Kingdom along with their native country are listed below:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Yamoah and Johnson, 2020.

Table 3: Immigrant Entrepreneurships (Source: Yamoah and Johnson, 2020)

Immigrant entrepreneurs not only fuel the economic growth of United Kingdom, but also according to the top entrepreneurs of United Kingdom, if the country implements plans to limit the skilled immigrants in United Kingdom, the chances are that the growth rate of the country will be hampered causing a drastic fall in the digital economy. Without immigrant entrepreneurs the number of start-up companies will be less, reducing the employment opportunities provided by those firms. Also, the country will be deprived of some unique services or products provided by those firms.

According to the surveys conducted in the year 2014, it was found that most of the immigrant entrepreneurs of United Kingdom, which was around 48,854 in total, were from Ireland. India, with 32,593 immigrant entrepreneurs, was in second position (Gonzalez, 2017). The third place was occupied by Germany with their 30,755 immigrant entrepreneurs in United Kingdom. Immigrant entrepreneurs from America and China were also responsible for launching a significant number of new businesses in United Kingdom. Apart from these 5, another 150

countries had their people as entrepreneurs in different entrepreneurial ventures in United Kingdom (Gonzalez, 2017).

Immigrant entrepreneurs are being benefitted by the large market of United Kingdom, which is true, but another important fact is that the country is equally being benefitted by these immigrant entrepreneurs (Gonzalez, 2017). With more immigrants setting up new business in the country, the number of companies is increasing day by day. In turn, the total revenue earned by the United Kingdom business industry altogether is also rising. Thus, the country is getting a vast amount of taxes for the betterment of other important aspects. As we all know companies donate a part of their earnings to non-profit organisations working for betterment of the society, with a greater number of companies the social infrastructure of the country is being positively affected. Moreover, a company is not only beneficial for the entrepreneur, a company provides bread-butter to a large amount of people working there from technical to non-technical staff, labours as well as managers (Zhang and Reay, 2018).

With the establishment of a new company, recruitment process also starts, opening employment opportunity to a large group of unemployed people residing in United Kingdom. Unemployment being an important issue of almost every country, the rise of new business ventures is providing immense employment opportunities, improving the employment condition of United Kingdom (Zhang and Reay, 2018). Hence, immigrant entrepreneurs are majorly responsible of such increasing number of start-ups growing each year in United Kingdom. With such flow of immigrant entrepreneurs in United Kingdom, the country is expected to witness a higher economic growth rate in upcoming years.

2.10 Challenges faced by immigrant entrepreneurs in UK

Entering a foreign market is not an easy task, a lot of research, analysis and determination is required to implement a successful business venture in a foreign country having relatively larger market. United Kingdom is currently one of the most popular start-up hubs, having a huge number of start-ups growing in the favourable business environment of the country. When an immigrant entrepreneur plans a new business in United Kingdom, that individual needs to think a lot of extra factors compared to a UK-born entrepreneur setting up a new business in home country. While starting off a new venture, there are two important factors related to it; challenges or threats and opportunities or scope. To succeed as an entrepreneur in a foreign land, the entrepreneur must identify the opportunities and challenges; and then should explore the opportunities after

overcoming the challenges (Miller and Le Breton-Miller, 2017). A new business, that too in a larger market of foreign country, has several crucial risk factors involved with it. With skilful actions the entrepreneur must identify the risk factors and eliminate or reduce those to a greater extent. An immigrant entrepreneur faces a number of challenges while entering a foreign market, especially when it is as large as the market of United Kingdom (Falavigna *et al.* 2017). Some major challenges faced by immigrant entrepreneurs in United Kingdom are discussed hereby:

Lack of networks and contacts:

Networking is an important business tool in business industry. While setting up a new business an immigrant entrepreneur is supposed to have a good number of networks in order to carry out the business operation related issues. A new business has various aspects to cover, such as marketing, manufacturing, planning etc. For successful completion of all these aspects an entrepreneur must have deeper understanding in each of these sectors (Omisakin, 2017). And to obtain that understanding an entrepreneur is supposed to interact to maximum amount of people. With the increasing amount of work pressure, professionals are often deprived from socializing. The line between work colleagues and social friends is almost eliminated now for lack of time. After spending tiring office hours, individuals are often reluctant to go for social gatherings which can be a great networking platform. Thus, the immigrant entrepreneurs fail to implement their ideas within pre-decided time span.

Again, language barrier is also a major reason behind lack of contacts and social networking. Language barriers make socializing difficult and hence become a huge obstacle even if an immigrant entrepreneur wants to socialize and be vocal about the start-up idea. Another important reason can be shyness (Falavigna *et al.* 2017). A shy or introvert person will avoid socializing and also tends to bottle up the start-up idea. This keeps that individual from implementing a possibly unique plan which could have immensely affected the economic growth of United Kingdom. According to an online survey, 92% immigrant entrepreneurs have agreed upon the fact that networking helped them setting up their business in United Kingdom. An effective interaction among two people or a group of people having business mind can promote a business and also helps to grow social circle. Thus, building contacts and more networking leads to setting up a new business successfully in a foreign country.

Assessment of finance:

Finance is the backbone of every business. An entrepreneur always thinks about finances before setting up a new business. This is one of the key challenges faced by immigrant entrepreneurs while setting up their business in United Kingdom. Lack of funding can be a major reason behind the decision of shutting down of business operations taken by a firm (Nel and Abdullah, 2017). Immigrant entrepreneurs consider a number of sources while looking for financial resources to start their business; such as, self-funding, venture capital, bank loans, angel investing, equity financing, and loans from family or friends. According to a survey, 37% of the immigrant entrepreneurs started their business by investing their own money. On being interviewed regarding the same, the immigrant entrepreneurs replied that going for other option were difficult for them for certain reasons that is why they chose self-funding as it is easier and hassle-free. Getting a bank loan was impossible for them as they could not transfer their credit history to United Kingdom as a result the bank loan procedure could never be fulfilled (Moghaddamet *al.* 2017). Also, for this same reason, the immigrant entrepreneurs cannot get credit cards which are very much important for a new business, especially in their early stages. Government of United Kingdom should work along with the financial organisations to make this process less complicated and less time consuming in order to provide an effective funding option to the immigrant entrepreneurs (Bhachu, 2017).

United Kingdom is also having government grants for the entrepreneurs in order to make funding easier and build up more start-ups in the country. But immigrant entrepreneurs are not being helped as according to them those government grants aim to facilitate the entrepreneurs who belongs from United Kingdom. As only the UK citizens can avail the facilities of the government grants or government loans, immigrant entrepreneurs are finding it hard to fund their new business, especially when they do not have enough money to go for self-funding (Griffin-El and Olabisi, 2018). There are a handful of immigrant entrepreneurs who finally accessed the government funding scheme, but the process came out as a time-consuming one and for business world time is money. For entrepreneurs, every second is priceless. It is high time for the government of immigrant entrepreneurs to think about funding issues raised by immigrant entrepreneurs as a large portion of the finance of the country is being generated from the revenues harvested by the start-ups.

Knowledge:

For an immigrant entrepreneur, starting a business shortly after migrating in United Kingdom is near to impossible. Setting up a business requires study of several internal as well as external factors related to the business environment. An immigrant entrepreneur is required to perform a thorough research on the planned business idea, current business environment, market demand of the product or service to be launched, prospective customers, level of market competition etc (Chavan and Taksa, 2017). Performing this research and analysing it in the context of a new country is tough for an immigrant entrepreneur. Moreover, business ecosystem of United Kingdom is having a network groups and organisations, which is easily recognised by a UK-born entrepreneur. But immigrant entrepreneurs have no idea about the same, which works as a major disadvantage for them while setting up a new business in United Kingdom.

Knowledge about taxation, government schemes and government grants are also important for an immigrant entrepreneur to enter the global market. Most importantly, the Government of United Kingdom, business groups and certain community groups should work together to promote the various government policies for entrepreneurial ventures (Yong and Martin, 2017). Advertising is a much important business tool as with the help of it the immigrant entrepreneurs can access the knowledge regarding different government policies. The government should make sure that the effective government policies implemented for the benefits of immigrant entrepreneurs should not go by unnoticed by those who are in need of it.

The above-mentioned challenges are major ones and should be considered with utmost care and attention in order to ensure seamless functions of businesses in United Kingdom founded by immigrant entrepreneurs (Moghaddam *et al.* 2017). The immigrant entrepreneurs are fuelling the country with their innovative ideas, unique services and increased revenue. So, the country should also look after its responsibility of implementing policies and schemes in support of the immigrant entrepreneurs and make sure they are equally facilitated by the policies and schemes just as a citizen of United Kingdom.

2.11 Nepalese Community in the UK

It has been historically observed that all the retired Gurkhas in 2009 won the fundamental right to live in the UK, which led the current estimated population of Nepali people residing in the UK, to around 80,000 to 100,000. The charity named Gurkha Welfare Trust, duly compiles the figures annually and estimates the numbers of the retired population of 'ex-Gurkhas, who have been settled in the UK (Hazarika *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, almost 16,000 Heads of Family have been recorded to have settled in the UK, as suggested by the latest data. The Gurkha Welfare Trust (GWT) is a registered UK charity that duly and collectively offers advice and support to the veterans of Gurkha along with their family members, who reside both in Nepal and in the UK. The charity works and performs closely with the government bodies as well as the service charities like the Soldiers, Sailors, Airmen and Families Association (SSAFA), the Associated British Foods (ABF) and the Royal British Legion, in order to provide necessary and statutory support to the ex-Gurkhas (Simkhada *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, as recorded by the Office for National Statistics, approximately 65,000 people of Nepali origin have been found to be residing in England and Wales. Furthermore, in 2012, the Centre for Nepal Studies had estimated the total number of Nepali residents in the UK to be 80,000, whereas, in 2019, the UK Nepal Friendship Society (UKNFS) along with the Nepali community organisations had estimated the number to be much higher (Simkhada *et al.*, 2020; Pokharel, 2016).

The Nepalese in the Britain are said to be one of the most recent diaspora populations of the UK. They are well considered to be younger and less visible ones, than the better-known and more established minorities from South Asia such as Pakistan (1.2 million population), Indians (1.4 million), Bangladeshis (450,000 approx.) etc. According to the 2001 census of the UK, approximately 5943 people from Nepali origin to be residing in the UK. However, the beginning of 2004, faced a greater number of Nepali origins to arrive in the UK, and therefore, became the fastest growing groups or community to inhabit in the UK (Sapkota *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, the 2011 census of the UK, recorded 60,202 Nepalese in England and Wales. Therefore, the Centre for Nepal Studies UK, after a rigorous survey, estimated that had been a record of 72,173 Nepalese in the UK as per 2008, from which the vast majority used to live in Southeast England. The Nepali community had been widely unaware of the general information about how the UK health and social care system work. Therefore, there have been

Quite a limited number of studies that provide the understanding of the health and well-being of the Nepali population as well as their utilisation of care services in the UK (Pariyar, 2020).

2.11.1 Categories of Nepalese Migration

Wide ranges of immigration routes have been followed by the Nepali population residing in the UK. There has been a significant and increasing number of Nepali origin and citizens residing in the UK that mainly includes the Gurkhas along with their families, professionals, students, refugees as well as their asylum seekers etc. The Nepalese people have been segregated into three immigration categories namely, Gurkhas, students and the Economic migrants (Onta, 2016). The Gurkhas migration to the UK has been extensively beneficial for creating and developing a critical mass of Nepali people and their families, which collectively forms a community itself. However, the majority of the Nepali students have been seen or have migrated to the UK in order to receive and achieve higher studies for a better economic purpose. Therefore, focusing on the students and economic migrants will provide a vast and predominant approach and understanding of the Nepalese migration categories at large (Adhikari *et al.*, 2012).

➤ Students:

The students from Nepal origin, who are seen to migrate to the UK for higher studies, face major financial problems, as recorded in several surveys. The students moreover, as recorded, have managed their basic needs and necessities on an average of around £325 every month; however, the estimated amount for the tuition has been seen to be £3850, which is extremely high as compared to Nepal, where it is \$270 per capita income. Furthermore, most of the Nepali students have financed their tour to the UK either by selling their hereditary properties or other valuable assets (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Since ages, Nepal has gradually expanded its education system to a better approach for their students; however, the utility of the education provided has been seen to be extremely low as compared to the international standards. The higher education sectors in the UK are seen to be statistically expanded, due to the growing demand of the enrolments of foreign students (Dhaliwal, 2004). The foreign students are required to pay higher tuition and enrolment fees in the universities and educational institutions in the UK. Therefore, the foreign students are said to be widely contributing in the improvement of the international dimensions as well as the global reputation of schools, colleges and universities of the UK. Henceforth, it can be strategically concluded with a diabolical fact that, the Nepali

Students provide a great contribution towards the flexibility of the higher education sectors in the UK, along with enabling it to expand at large (Chen *et al.*, 2019).

Moreover, the Nepali students are widely observed to be lured to the education system of the UK because of better and erudite opportunities for learning and earning wisely. (Abramson, 2019) In regard to the earning process for the students, they are duly informed that the immigration rules and regulations for the foreign students allow them to work 20 hours per week, with a minimum wage of at least £5.80 per hour, that make the Nepali students eligible to earn up to £460 per month, that is considered to be enough in order to cover their living expenses (Silwal, 2019).

There have been several students from Nepali origin in the UK for higher educational purposes, who deliberately share accommodations. In this way, they need to manage their stay at around £50 per week in a posh place like London. Moreover, the expense of a ticket for their underground train approximately covers £60 per month (Delaplace and Dobruszkes, 2015). These students are therefore seen to cook by their own sharing kitchen with 3-4 roommates. Their average food bill can be estimated at around £51 per month, where the other expenses might cover their phone bills, entertainment expenses, educational materials etc. (Gilliam, 2017).

The Nepalese students have been accustomed with leading a hard life, adapted from their origin and therefore, £325 per month is considered to be extremely essential for the Nepalese students for achieving their basic needs in the UK. Education has been the immediate cause that makes the Nepalese people and students migrate to different places of the UK, which can be topped by the long-term cause i.e., the economic condition. Around 13.5 million people in the UK have been duly reported to live below the minimum income (60%) and also a number of people have been unemployed (Sah, 2017). Therefore, it can be said that the expectations of the Nepali students in the UK, have not been met and fulfilled. Also, further problems like late starting of the programmes enrolled for, no existence of certain programmes that have already been enrolled by students etc., are faced by the Nepali students at large, as they remain unaware of the particularities of the universities and educational institutions.

➤ **Economic Migrants:**

Certain Nepalese have also been seen to have come as the economic migrants in the UK, under the work categories. These groups of migrants fall under the category of spouse visa, domestic visa and dependent visa. Moreover, the highly skilled and talented migrants, the domestic workers in the UK along with the work-permit holders are collectively compromised by the current economic Nepalese immigration. Therefore, these are said to be the first-generation migrants, that might show a similar trend like the other Asian first-generation entrepreneurs (Adhikari *et al.*, 2012). These migrants and entrepreneurs might be seen to be heavily interwoven with their cultures, values and beliefs as well as very much limited with their co-ethnic group, bereft of migration in the UK. Therefore, it has been increasingly observed that the migrant categories can skilfully provide opportunities in order to differentiate the entrepreneurial behaviours at large.

2.12 Interpretation of previous research findings

Despite of facing loads of challenges or threats, the small and medium scale business ventures keep rising high, contributing enormous amount of financial support to the economy of the particular country. The size and tenure for which the venture is established, mainly responsible for determining the growth rate and performance rate of a new small and medium size business in a larger and highly competitive market. Many companies try to envisage the variables of size and performance in order to come up with best-suited solutions. The number of employees is considered as crucial aspect to maintain a smooth flow of business operations within the organisation. It is found that service departments are having higher rate of shutdowns than that of the manufacturing departments. The manpower is the main driving force behind the success of small or large sized enterprises.

It is also found that proper training and education in the business environment can prevent the small and medium sized enterprises from incurring losses. Experience in practical business environment makes the employees more efficient than adoption of business ideas and concepts from textbooks (Saguy and Sirotinskaya, 2014). Conduction of effective training programs is much helpful to overcome lower profit margin and operational errors. Working on a new market

is unpredictable and uncertain, it involves a certain number of risk factors, with implementation of suitable measures using relevant business tools these risk factors can be eliminated or reduced to a greater extent. As per as the given context is concerned, if the economy of United Kingdom is anyhow affected, the newly established small enterprises will fall prey for it at first.

As the research process heads to the conclusion, it can be said that the Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs face a lot of trouble while entering a larger market like that of United Kingdom. The Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs are interested in expanding their business and yielding more profits from their business operations, thus, they target bigger markets having higher market demand, for example, the market of United Kingdom (Jorge *et al.* 2015). As the small entrepreneurs from developing countries like Nepal tend to achieve global recognition through eminent market like that of United States. But bigger markets have their own share of business challenges which the small and medium scale entrepreneurs tend to face while entering such a market. A study reveals that United Kingdom has more than 90% small and medium sized enterprises in their business industry, with a handful of large entrepreneurial ventures. It may seem like the small and medium scale entrepreneurial ventures are being flourished by United Kingdom, but the fact is the economy of United Kingdom is being flourished by the revenues harvested by those small and medium sized enterprises. Thus, it can be said that both the economy of United Kingdom and the small and medium scale enterprises are beneficial for each other. In accordance to the new business environment of larger countries like United Kingdom, the Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs are changing their business strategies and entrepreneurial methods in order to adapt to the changing business scenario.

There are two important aspects of a business, opportunities or scope and challenges or threats. An entrepreneur should be intelligent enough to explore the opportunities or scopes of the new business and eliminate the challenges or threats or at least reduce it to greater extent (Cecelja *et al.* 2015). Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs try to enter the market of United Kingdom to maximize their profit and give their product or service the global recognition. But they should always keep in mind that larger countries are a hub of other business giants as well which might be a tough competition. Moreover, adapting to internal and external factors affecting the new business in a country like United Kingdom is difficult indeed (Pant,2015). Hence, most of the Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs do not make it to the success list. But with undivided determination and hard work a Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneur can set up a new business in United Kingdom successfully. Attaining sustainable growth in the market of

United Kingdom is tough for a new business from a Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneur. But with the use of proper business tools and appropriate strategies the objective can be achieved. Proper business environment and positive influential factors can be helpful for new business to leave its mark in a bigger business market. Assessment of the research findings and analysis of the present situation can draw out desired results, leading a Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneur starting a new business successfully in the competitive market of United Kingdom.

Conclusion:

The literature is critically reviewed by this chapter. The several theories and studies has been discussed in this chapter which will help to know the Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK. The initial framework of this research has been developed after critical review of the literature shown in (fig 2; below). The literature shows that there are various factors and challenges influencing Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK which can also be restated by research objectives of the studies:

- To explore the reason for Nepalese Entrepreneur to start business in the UK.
- To understand the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs for the growth and development of their business in the UK.
- To find out if Nepalese Entrepreneurs are obtaining significant help and support for start up and the smooth operations of their business in the UK.

Fig 2: The Conceptual Framework

(Source: Researcher)

The conceptual framework for this research has been developed after the critical literature review of the previous existing theories, model, and research. According to Adom, Hussein and Joe (2018), the conceptual frameworks can be in a narrative or graphical form explaining the essential variables, concepts or factors to be studied. This framework demonstrates the main variable, concepts or ideas which are vital for the study Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK. This conceptual framework has been created from collecting and arranging the applicable concepts from the previous literature. Hence, this framework directs the interview questions. The necessity and opportunity factors help in finding motivational factors for the start-up businesses. The variables such as cultural factors, education, opportunity, the role of family and motives exist in the host country are classified as opportunity factors whereas and language barriers, unemployment and discrimination are necessity factors. The identity of entrepreneurial Nepalese entrepreneurs could be identified with the help of the classic entrepreneurial storylines. Additionally, to investigate the strategies for obtaining and using resources and to attain the research objective two. The study seeks out to identify the source of labour, source of finance, source of advice and support. In order to investigate the objective three which is the challenges facing by Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK, the potential challenges are put down, which are gathered from the previous research. This conceptual framework will be redeveloped and revisited established on the findings.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The very purpose of a research is to gain an in-depth understanding of the chosen research context which eventually helps the researcher to provide a concrete conclusion about the research context by appropriately addressing the formulated research questions. Research methodology hence, provides the researcher with the structural framework depending on which the entire research needs to be carried out. Research methodology also comprises of structural elements that help the researchers to identify the basic elements those need to be considered while conducting the research in order to impart validity, credibility and proper transferability to the conducted research (Daniel and Harland, 2017). Promising research usually comprises of multiple elements or components such as research background, significance of the research, rationale behind the conduction of the research, aim, objectives and research questions; critical analysis of the previous research studies, gaps in previous research, data collection and analysis techniques, sample size and sampling technique, research strategy, and ethical consideration to name a few (Kumar, 2019). There are various research methodology frameworks out of which Saunder's research onion has been found to be the most appropriate and is widely used by researchers all over the world for both academic as well as professional graded research studies (Igwenagu, 2016).

According to Mackey and Gass, (2015), the principal aim of carry out a research study is to solve problems and to extend the level of understandings and knowledge regarding any topic of investigation or research content. While carrying out any research work, this particular section owns the highest level of importance. More specifically, it can be said that it should be a primary responsibility of a researcher to select the most appropriate methods and approaches. The section enables the researcher to develop a concrete conclusion on the basis of the research content (Engwa and Ozofor, 2015). Any research work includes several stages, which starts from identification of the research problem and continues through analysis of literature review and end with the development of a comprehensive conclusion. The research methodology is that crucial and significant aspect of the research project which constructs the pivotal structure of the research. In order to create a concrete research project, the structure on the basis of which the research analysis shall be placed needs to be prepared (Kumar, 2018).

Fig 3: Synthesis of the methodological approaches in the study

(source: Developed by Author)

The methodological section forms that framework where each of the elements contributing towards a proper research work is discussed and specified (Sinha *et al.* 2018). There are essential determinants such as research philosophy, research approach, justification of the research issue chosen; research design, sampling technique and sample size, collection of data which help design the research project. As the present research deals with the fact of analysing the various factors affecting the conducts of SMEs in UK certain specific determinants need to be taken while carrying out the research. The Nepalese SMEs are likely to get affected with a number of challenges, risks and threats in their way to establish business conducts while operating in the

UK (Solman and Henderson, 2018). However, the selection of suitable methodological elements and conducting the research following them shall enable the researcher to understand the exact factors having implications upon the Nepalese SMEs. Hence the present research methodology section discusses selected appropriate determinants which shall assist the researcher to decipher adequate results for the present issue raised. The research philosophy helps to provide an appropriate ideology and conceptualisation on the basis of which the research gets its dimension (Mayer, 2015).

It is on the basis of the correct selection of the research approach that the study can be progressed following proper dimension. It is through the incorporation of the research approach that one gets the appropriate direction to achieve the desired results. A proper justification of the issue considered is to be specified within the methods section. In this study only qualitative data has been collected through the direct involvement of human subjects and thus it has been quite essential to discuss the sample size and the sampling technique implemented. This has been important because application of appropriate sampling technique and consideration of a suitable sample results in ensuring transferability of the specific study (Collins, 2018). For collecting the data and relevant information a definite means needs to be adopted using which the researcher shall acquire necessary data. The ethical considerations also need to be simultaneously kept in mind so that each of the step adhering to the research conducts is taken following the norms and ethical basis. Each of the determinants has a crucial contribution to make towards the research process hence needs to be chosen very consciously and carefully so that the aims and objectives of the research get fulfilled. These steps are considered to be important; a selection of research methods depend on these steps to a large extent. Research methods include several parameters, like research design, research approach, and allocation of relevant data and information from a diverse range of sources, analysis and evaluation of those data and information in accordance to the research aim and objectives and finally construction of a meticulous conclusion. According to Taylor *et al.* (2015, pp.256), “selection of research methods is an important decision-making process, on which progression of a research work depends to a large extent”. In this context, it can be said that the success of a research project depends upon the type of data and relevance of the data and information with the research content, therefore, selection of the methods should be carried out vigilantly.

Further, the relevance and validity of allocated data and information and collection procedure are depending upon the selection of the research philosophy, research strategy and research

approach- therefore these three parameters are considered to be important while it comes to meet the research aim and proposed objectives to formulate a comprehensive conclusion (Sinha *et al.* 2018). The basic purpose of this chapter is to make a brief description about the different methodological approaches which have been selected and employed by the researcher for the purpose to meet the proposed aim and objectives of this particular research study (Lewis, 2015).

The principal aim of this particular research study is to evaluate the challenges and factors which may influence the Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurship to penetrate the UK market. In order to meet this proposed aim, primary qualitative research method has been used by the researcher. Furthermore, in order to meet the research objectives, the researcher has taken different methodological approaches into consideration, like research philosophy, research design, sampling techniques, data findings procedures and so on. Brief and concise descriptions about these parameters have been included in this chapter along with proper justification. Thus, it can be said that research methodology is a supportive framework to continue a study with proper precision and in accordance with the proposed aim and objectives.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy, as defined above is the nature of the belief pertained by the researcher associated with data collection, analysis and interpretation (Nayak and Singh, 2021). These three parameters are extremely crucial for the successful conduction of a research. The researcher receives specific knowledge about the protocols to be followed for collecting the raw data followed by the frameworks to be followed for analysing and interpreting the collected raw data (Silverman, 2016). Refining the raw data in response to the framed research questions so that the latter can be addressed at the end of the research is very much necessary. These undertaking can be successfully carried out only if the research philosophy is considered appropriately (Thomas, 2021).

The research philosophy renders the study with a definite conceptualisation adhering to an appropriate ideation. It is through the philosophy of the research that different earlier researches in the similar paradigm are incorporated within the study. Before conceptualising any research project, a definite ideology needs to be framed (Daniel and Harland, 2017). It is addressing that ideology that one needs to drive their research study to accomplish the stipulated course of the project. The research philosophy enables the researcher to perform the researcher from a certain perspective. The research gets to progress following that particular dimension to reach the

answers to the aims formulated. Research philosophy can be typically categorised into positivism, realism and interpretive paradigms (Kuratko, 2016). Positivist research philosophy is one where a scientific, as well as an objective outlook, is established for the research issue considered. This philosophy allows the research to develop a concrete relationship between the variables of the study. The realism philosophy is one where the research is based on certain realities that exist in and around the environment. The concept of independent reality which is free from any subjective outlook gets emphasised while using the realism philosophy. However, interpretive philosophy is much in contrast to that where the subjective point of view is given much significance. The perspectives of the people are taken into consideration for interpreting their viewpoint upon the issue raised in the research (Creswell and Clark, 2017).

3.2.1 Interpretivism

In case of the particular study interpretivism philosophy has been taken into account. In order to opt for the interpretivist philosophy, it is essential that the research data is dominated by qualitative mode (Terjesen *et al.* 2016). For carrying out the study data has been collected from the conduction of interviews. Thus, it can be stated that a form of qualitative theoretical data has been collected for fulfilling the purpose of the research work. The entire study has been based on interpreting the influence of the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs while doing business from UK. For supporting the interpretation of the researcher an interpretivist philosophy has proven to be greatly useful. Like the competition, challenges and risks faced by the entrepreneurs require subjective interpretation. Subjective evaluation has helped in proper identification of the factors which are influencing the business ventures of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in UK. It has already been discussed that interpretivist philosophy considers perspectives of the people for interpreting the issues related with a research area (Thomas, 2021). Similarly, considering of interpretivism philosophy has resulted in evaluating and interpreting the viewpoints of the respondents in relation to the challenges, competitions and risks faced by their businesses in UK. As per the statement of (Scarborough, 2016), it is essential to have a proper understanding of the research methodology/ paradigm. Comprehension of the factor would enable the researcher to determine the particular way of portrayal of the research content (Igwenagu, 2016). This, in turn, would be helpful for the readers or audience to have a clear idea about the study. In other words, the methodology/ paradigm of the study helps to conduct the study in an organized and systematic manner. There are certain theoretical perspectives and opinions which support the importance of

methodology. It is important to mention that as per theoretical orientations, two major schools of thoughts are present (Engwa and Ozofor, 2015).

According to (Alvesson and Sköldbberg, 2017), the research paradigm is considered a research model. Its key objective is to conduct the study in a proper way with minimal scopes of confusion and error. The rule of employing a research paradigm has been present for a long time. It is crucial to consider that there are two key research approaches, the interpretivism and positivist approaches (Kumar, 2018). The other research approaches have come from these two major approaches. Research enthusiasts tend to employ one of the research approaches to develop as a proper research methodology.

The particular research paradigm has enabled the researcher to employ many methods included in it. For example, the research method supports descriptive research as well as experimental research. Descriptive research stresses the variables present in the research topic. Considering the Nepalese entrepreneur, it has been observed that there are various factors which affect the business in the UK (Fellows and Liu, 2015). Political issue, technical factor, sociological aspect, environmental consideration, ethical and legal issues and such. On the other aspect, there are several internal factors such as marketing capacity, strategic strength, manufacturing and production aspect, funds, labours and employees and such (Coles *et al.* 2015).

Depending on the analysis of the emergent themes from the evaluation of the qualitative data it will be possible to determine the factors influencing the business operations of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in UK. The Nepal entrepreneurs would be able to conduct good business if the economy of the UK shows enough stability. Positive attitude and behaviour of the UK consumers toward the Nepalese SMEs would show the latter the opportunities and scopes to do business in the particular market. Interpretivist paradigm stresses on the perceptions and viewpoints of the people who are associated with the elements or aspects of the research area. On the basis of these perceptions the actual data and information can be uphold. With the help of the relevant information, the researcher will be able to conduct the research study with sufficient accuracy (Creswell and Clark, 2017).

Interpretivist research design helps in supporting analysis and identification of different trends, factors, influences, perceptions, impacts, etc. by considering the perceptions of the individuals. This kind of paradigm supports interviews, focus group discussions, case studies, systematic reviews, etc (Sahay, 2016). Through the application of interpretivism philosophy the researcher

has been able to critically analyse, assess and evaluate the different dimensions of the research topic in a subjective manner. For example, the researcher by applying the particular approach has been able to carry out interviews of individuals who are closely related with the Nepalese entrepreneurial community operating in UK (Fayolle and Liñán, 2014). The conduction of extensive study has enabled the researcher to identify the various challenges and problems which are being continuously experienced by the Nepalese entrepreneurs while trying to do their business from a foreign market. The findings of the subjective study will be helpful in highlighting the environmental factors impacting the Nepalese individuals as well as business ventures within a foreign market.

For carrying out the particular study the researcher has used vast resources to acquire relevant information and evidence for the investigation. The resources have been gathered from reliable data sources, such as Google Scholar and various books, articles and journals; however, these pieces of resources have been used in the literature review which has been contrasted in the discussion part with the primary data that has been collected through the semi-structured interview. The utilisation of adequate resources as evidence has been effectively supported through the application of interpretivism research philosophy. The interpretations and perceptions of wide range of professionals and experts could be incorporated in the study for supporting the addressing of the research questions (Mishra and Alok, 2017). Along with the existing materials, the researcher has conducted an interview to get primary information concerning the study topic. Current investigation content would enable the researcher to demonstrate the issue which is observed in the contemporary UK market. It is important to note that the methodology helps to introduce the key research question or problem. Identifying the research issue is crucial as the audience needs to understand the reason for doing the research. The methodology section further helps the researcher to perform and present the research study accordingly. In other words, planning is necessary to manage the research issue, methodology helps to do the planning. As per the statement of (Winkler *et al.* 2018), it gives a work plan, it mentions the activities required for successful completion of the project.

3.3 Research approach

One of the most crucial as well as essential elements to be considered while constructing the methodology section is that of the research approach. It is with the help of the research

approach that a particular research project gets a definite direction. It enables the researcher to carry the conducts of the research following in a particular dimension. The understanding of the entire methodology is integrated within the approach. The research approach can be typically categorised into two significant parts, the inductive and the deductive types. It is through the inductive research approach that various findings and observation lead to creating constructive research concepts and theories. The research gets directed from a specific orientation towards a more generalised position (Winkler *et al.* 2018). This is also known as the bottom-up approach where the theoretical conceptualisation and models get created as the course of the project progresses. On the other hand, the deductive research approach is just the opposite of what the inductive approach stands for. Research studies often adhere to a deductive approach to conduct both of the qualitative as well as the quantitative processes. This approach is also known as the top-down process of the research project. It is following the deductive research approach that one conducts the analysis on the basis of the theories and models which are considered as the fundamental point of the study. The entire course of research is designed and carried out on the basis of the theories and models (McMullen *et al.* 2016).

Research approach has been defined as the plan or procedure that usually comprises of the inherent steps or phases associated with the broad assumptions to detailed methods of collecting, analysing and interpreting the raw data. Henceforth, research approach is mainly dependent on the nature of the problem statement of the undertaken research that needs to be addressed throughout the research. The research approach is basically categorised into two classes; the approach of data collection and the approach of data analysis or reasoning (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015).

It can be stated that the deductive approach is the exact opposite of the inductive approach. In case of deductive approach, the research questions or hypotheses are developed in association with the research area. After these relevant sources are searched and identified for the collection of the research data. Existing theories, models and concepts are collected and applied as theoretical frameworks. The data is then analysed to accumulate useful information (Bairagi and Munot, 2019). The accumulated information is then used for addressing the research questions or testing the research hypotheses. Through this process required inferences and conclusions are drawn by the researcher. For inductive approach the initial stage is same that is the formulation of research questions or hypotheses. However, the difference is that mostly new concepts and theories are identified from the analysis of the data and accumulation of the

information. Inductive is related with inducing certain ideas and viewpoints of the researchers. When paradigms are considered then certain approaches are meant to be used along with specific research paradigm. For example, positivist paradigm primarily goes with quantitative research and deductive approach is used for analysing the numerical values (Mishra and Alok, 2017). Thus, the selection of approach is dependent on the method of data collection and analysis to be conducted. Statistical analysis is better represented when deductive approach is implemented. This is because such analysis is mainly related with deductions supporting the research questions or hypotheses developed for the study. Narrative synthesis or thematic analysis is more suitable to go along with inductive approach (Kumar, 2018). Subjective evaluation or extensive analysis supports the inducing of the viewpoints of the researcher through the conduction of the study.

3.3.1 Qualitative approach

Qualitative and quantitative are widely used two research approaches in the study of management and social and sciences. According to Bryman (2012), quantitative approach is the strategy of distinctive research which focuses on numerical data collection and demonstrates the relationship between research and theory. It is involved theory testing by means of appropriate modes of measurement and analysis is established upon statistical or mathematical techniques (Owojori, 2005). Quantitative methods will not be appropriate approach for this research as this research is not trying to quantify any value or numbers from the research findings. The limited and strict methods along with unrealistic theories often restrict the quantitative approach; thus it can "*miss a real interpretation of actual-world behaviours in extraterrestrial cultures*" (Pasquero, 1988, pp.184).

After thorough review, the qualitative approach is used by this research which aims to examine a more detailed and in-depth understanding of vague concepts by studying the why, what,

and how questions (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). A qualitative approach would be more suitable to examine the factors influencing ethnic Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK for start-ups and the development of business because this method emphasizes on in-depth research and delivers an understanding of the experiences lived by Nepalese entrepreneurs (Maxwell, 2012).

The rationale for choosing Qualitative Research:

The qualitative research approach is adopted by this research which is based on the necessity of a particular population to enter the subjective reality in order to develop in-depth broader understanding. This approach is related to interactions, personal observations of individuals, document analysis (including quantitative data), open-ended interviews in examining in-depth understanding, events, oral testimonies, and situations (Dana & Dana, 2005, pp.82).

The qualitative research helps in developing ideas which develop the social understanding phenomena by highlighting on the views, meaning and experiences of the participants (Holt, 2007). However, the meaning of people's behaviour, words and attitude should not be taken for granted by the researchers (Dana & Dana, 2005). According to Snape and Spencer (2003), that this method is especially well suitable to know issues which hold the entire picture of human or social problems and complexity from various perspectives. The qualitative method used in this study will focus on research questions which need the Nepalese contexts understanding and the social experiences to enlighten Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK. A qualitative method is used to create the any entities qualities along with the meaning that cannot be measured in terms of amounts, numbers and quantity (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). The qualitative data can be well explained as highly and rich descriptive, which highlights the reality of social construction. Denzin and Lincoln (1994) states qualitative research as "*multi research method which applies naturalistic and an interpretive approach to its matter of subject*". Likewise, Gephart (2004 p.454-455) explains "*focus on questions about how social involvement is given and created meaning*". This research process is more receptive to the research requirements because of the fewer structured approach in nature.

In the entrepreneurship field research, a qualitative method has achieved substantial popularity (Bygrave, 1989; Hindle, 2004). Hindle (2004) states that implementing qualitative research for

subjects such as entrepreneurship makes understanding in-depth and facilitates directly learning from certain subjects. According to Dana & Dana (2005 pp. 81), the efficient future research in the entrepreneurship field should emphasis on 'how' questions such as; how others can be persuaded to succeed and "how they do it, as well. How do people from various cultures understand opportunity? How entrepreneurship can be promoted in a diverse environment?" How is business organized in the different environment? These questions cannot be performed using mail and surveys questionnaires. The main objective of this research is to examine the challenges and opportunity for the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. To examine the challenges and opportunity, it has to in-depth study. The unique tool is provided by qualitative method to in-depth study what rests behind, attitude, a decision, behaviour and phenomena. Thus, qualitative research approach will be more suitable as it is a adaptable method which can accumulate information using various qualitative sources such as attitudes, expression, behaviour, and non-verbal and verbal communication. (Dana & Dana, 2005). And this technique is suitable for explanatory research which is considered for why phenomena appear studying, and the influencing factors to drive that occurrence.

3.4 Research Strategy

Research designs is also a blueprint which identifies the methods and procedures to analyse and collect the specific information. The research design choice is basically related to how a researcher will intend to get the research question and its answer. According to Creswell (2007), *“researchers should commence their investigation process with theoretical conventions about the how they identify what is known (epistemology), reality nature (ontology), the nature in which emerges their research (methodology), the enclosure of their values (axiology), and structure of their writing”*

Dana and Dana (2005) states that qualitative research strategy is adaptable, and a research plan is continuously modified as per the constraints and opportunities confronted in the environment. The authors also emphasize *"Non-quantitative research strategy is collaborative, as in the relationship between an firm environment and the entrepreneur."* Creswell (2007) has explained the five prevalent qualitative research designs: case studies, narrative research, grounded theory, participatory action research (PAR) and phenomenology. Whereas, According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005), there are various forms of research designs such as grounded theory, case studies, ethnography, life history, interpretive practices and narratives.

3.5 Sampling strategy

Sampling procedures in qualitative research are not fixed and systematically set as in quantitative research. According to Coyne (1997), there can be a confusion if there is a lack of clarity on the sampling strategy procedure. (Davidsson, 2016 pp.117) states that "*Social science research is not like polls on opinion, and theories are not created by independent vote*" which means that all the cases given in the sample are not equally significant. '*Theoretical representativeness*' comes after social science, the case which is analysed in the research should be important for the theory which requires to be tested or developed (Davidsson, 2016). Maxwell (2005) states the term "sampling" which implies the purpose "representing" of the sampled population, which is challenging for qualitative research. Strategy selection requires vast knowledge of the requirement and setting of the study. A non-random sampling strategy is chosen in this research for the theoretically applicable Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK.

The interviewees were contacted firstly through personal contacts. According to Dhaliwal (2004), to attain trust in order to achieve information in depth, personal contacts are the best approach. The reality that the researcher being belongs to the same community offers an advantage to utilize the personal recommendations. The trust and networking with interviewee play a vital role to obtain in-depth and rich information required for this research. The researcher take part in different Nepalese community programmes and functions such as ", "Nepali Mela", "Mha Puja and others which lets the researcher to develop networks with Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. The participants showed enthusiasm to share their experiences and demonstrated high interest to participate for this research. Snowball sampling is the next method which is a chain recommendation technique and is used to detect potential participants determined by referral of other participants. This technique lets the researcher to sample a people of small group at the beginning (Altinay and Wang, 2009, Daliwal, 2004). Other participants was referred by these participants with experience and relevant characteristics, and so on continues the process.

3.5.1 Sample Population

A total sampling population is 20 for this research. The procedure of sampling is done until saturation of data is reached. According to Boddy (2016), Data saturation refers to "*the situation at*

which no new themes or information are detected in the data from the additional completion of interviews". The first generation of Nepalese entrepreneurs are the particular participants sample in the UK. The rationale for aiming on the first generation is; firstly, there is not very old migration history amongst Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK. Between the year 2001-2015, the majority of participants came in the UK. The majority of the interviewees of Nepalese entrepreneurs' are ranged from 30 to 50 years in the UK. Most of them said that when they started their business, they were of 25-35 years old. Whereas, Dhaliwal (2008) states that other Asian community (including Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan), the first generation entrepreneurs migrated in the early 1970s and late 1960s. This differentiates other Asian ethnic groups from Nepalese entrepreneurs. It is important to know that Nepalese entrepreneurs are young entrepreneurs and being first- generation mainly migrated for attaining higher studies in the UK.

3.6 Interviews

The interview is one of the widely used and most popular research methods in research. However, this method can be costly and very time-consuming i.e. interviewing, the interviews transcription and those transcriptions analysis. (Saunders, et al. 2009, p318) states an interview as "*a persistent discussion between more or two people*". Interviews in a qualitative method is a way of investigating and discovering in-depth information that underpins people's feelings, lives and behaviours (Rubin and Rubin, 2005).

A total semi-structured interviews of 20 Nepalese entrepreneur were performed. Semi-structure interviews consist of open-ended questions and are performed based on a loose structure along with a topic guide. The researcher believes that semi-structured interviews are more suitable than unstructured interviews and structured interviews in terms of its effectiveness. A list of questions and issues to be covered in the semi-structured interview. Depending on the direction of the interview, the order of asking questions may vary. Besides, the researcher can ask further extra questions as probing to expand where it is necessary (Gary, 2018). An open-ended question lets participants more choice for responding. Creswell (2012) states that closed question may push respondents to answer in a certain way whereas, open-ended questions are asked hoping to achieve independent answers. The researcher can remember and ask the core questions and the topic which have to be explored with the help of topic guide (Patton and Cochran, 2002). Likewise, According to Yin (2018, p.118), "Case study interviews will seem

like guided conversations instead of structured questions". This technique is valuable in order to collect data deeply and also create an interactive and useful conversation between interviewee and interviewer because they allow elasticity for using various words, time duration and its order. However, semi-structured interviews take huge cost, time and energy.

In-depth information is looked by this research. Thus, much more detailed information is gained by conducting face-to-face interview than the other existing data collection methods such as surveys, questionnaires, etc. (Boyce and Neale, 2006). The emotions and facial expression of the participants will help researchers to explain and understand the findings more efficiently. According to Bryman and Bell (2007 p. 474), the interviewer can change or modify the questions to make an interview comfortable and friendly and analysed later. Interview techniques are often considered as the most successful and powerful tools for collection of data as they also offer a more comfortable and relaxed atmosphere. Nevertheless, they are not as simple as it looks like due to presence of some limitations and pitfalls (Ghauri and Gronhaug, 2005; Boyce and Neale, 2006). For instance, this technique can be time-intensive, prone to bias, in regard to transcription of interviews, the analysis of the transcripts and the interviewing process, and can be inescapably time-consuming. Besides, the interviewer must totally know the research topics, the aims and objectives of the research study and also be aware with an interviewee, must be properly trained in techniques of interviews and also interviews are not generalizable due to the small sample are selected where random sampling is not used (Boyce and Neale, 2006). Sampling was done up until achieved the theoretical saturation where "minimal is *incremental learning*" (Eisenhardt, 1989, p.545).

3.6.1 Interview Contents

Robson (1993) offered the key elements of guide to an interview which covers the list of the topic area, introductory comments, the questions under each topic along with the probable closing comments and probes. The key topics areas which have been covered in this research are nature of the business, personal background information, a reason to choose to start own business, education, motivation, experience and training, family and cultural background, strategies-access to finance, access to information and challenges, competition, and staffing. The preparation of interview guide started with the requirement of the literature review and research questions. The interview guide implemented in this study has been inspired and follows the structure of the National Panel Study of the US start-ups (Reynolds, 2000). The interviews were face-to-face and

semi-structured which were operated at their business premises. The face-to-face interview allows the researcher to examine the business premises environment and achieve deeper understandings. Each interview took about approximately thirty minutes to forty-five minutes. A summary of the major topic area with the basis for incorporation in the interview guide is described below:

Business activities

The nature of the business is covered in this section. The services and product of the business and the information of relating customers and clients was sought. The questions were asked relating the reason behind choosing a specific geographical location to operate their business. This topic offers information about the structure of opportunity in the UK. It enables the proper insight of the market condition for the Nepalese entrepreneurship. It is interesting to find whether the Nepalese entrepreneurs are following ethnic entrepreneurship of stereotypical line of just being 'a corner shop' dependent on co-ethnic business or are splitting out into the open market.

Start-up reasons and motivation

This section is created by the researcher in order to examine the reason for operating their own business. This section granted for identifying their own business starting motivation in the UK. It is important to find out are Nepalese entrepreneur are necessity entrepreneurs or opportunist entrepreneurs. The researcher comprises questions asking about the reasons behind starting and choosing their own business, motivational factors and their journey along with the challenges. This section consist of questions family background of the participants, which includes their their family characteristics, parent's occupation, where they had brought up in the family environment. This section also highlights on the Nepalese entrepreneurial activities. It helped to represent them on various types of storylines of entrepreneurial activities (Smith, 2005). It also contained their religion and caste along with cultural values and tradition. The researcher intended to examine to what extent their current business has been influenced by their cultural values. Questions were asked on the support from friends and family they obtained in the business start- up, again to highlighting the support on social capital (Dyer and Handler, 1994). Also, the researcher aimed to know the personal characteristics and psychological factors of entrepreneur that influenced start-ups and development of business. There were also questions associated to any families and friends' parties who are supporting and encouraging to start the businesses. The social capital role for the start- ups can be examined in this section.

Strategies for the accumulation of resources and capital

This section aimed to gather knowledge about how Nepalese entrepreneurs utilized and acquired their capital and resources. This section aimed on the background of education and its role in their existing business along with the training and skills obtaining strategies. It contained the question about their training, education, and work experience. Entrepreneurs were asked about past experiences on their work and their experience role for the existing business. The researcher intended to understand the finance source obtained for Nepalese entrepreneurs' start-up business (Basu, 1998; Basu and Altinay, 2000; Ram et al., 2002). This section also included the obstacles they faced while the start-ups of the business financing and consist of the support they obtained from friends, families, any professional bodies and any institutional agency. This section let the researcher to know the Nepalese entrepreneurs' social interactions and to what extent social networking assisted them in the success of their start- up business. Therefore, this section intended to investigate and the successful Nepalese entrepreneurs and their involved strategies in the UK regarding access to financial capital, information, recruitment of staffs, skills and training, competitive dynamism and managing suppliers and customers.

Challenges and issues

This topic area aimed to examine the key issues and challenges that Nepalese entrepreneur are facing and have faced. It is one of the important topics which offered useful implication to the new and potential entrepreneurs and policymakers and other. This section included the questions on challenges in accessing resources, cultural barriers in the labour market and language.

3.6.2 Fieldwork experience

Cresswell (2013) suggested the steps which was followed by the researchers to perform the interviews in this study. Initially, a few interviewees were identified by the interviewer through the personal contacts. An invitation of participation was sent by researcher for an interview to those interviewees identified through personal contacts, outlining the objectives and aims of the research. The interview consent and guide form attachment were sent the via mail to them. Most of the entrepreneurs invited accepted and showed an enthusiasm to participate in the study. Research participants selection was made using sampling through personal networking and the snowball method sampling. The first generation of Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK was taken as the participants as the young phenomenon of Nepalese migration to the UK.

The interviews took in between 45 mins up to one hours. Face-to-face twenty interviews were performed mostly at the participant's workplace and the quiet environment and their home. Compared to the other available data collection methods such as surveys and questionnaires, face-to- face interviews offer much more thorough information. It has help out the researcher to gain an effective understanding by allowing their facial expressions sight and the participants emotions. According to Bryman & Bell (2007 p. 474), the interviewer can modify and change the questions to make comfortable and friendly interview which was analysed later. Due to the participant time constraint, one interview was taken by telephone. The participants consent to participate in the research was obtained from the researcher. Most of the interviews were audiotaped with the participants consent, but some responded refused top be taped due to which some interviews were not recorded. A brief note was taken by the researcher during all the interviews. In order to get additional information, the researcher used the probes wherever required. The researcher engaged on maintaining participant rapport by spending time and staying with them for a while after an interview completion wherever possible, as explained by (Dickson-Swift et al., 2007). The researcher was able to develop relationship and rapport with the participants by spending time in having lunch and tea. It offered an opportunity to discover in-depth information even after the interview completion. The places such as Reading, and South East London was frequently visited by researcher to have an understanding into the residential application of Nepalese community.

3.7 Pilot Study:

Pilot studies have been characterised as small scale and preliminary studies aiming to investigate whether crucial components of the main research study, especially a randomised controlled trial (RCT), is feasible or not. For instance, these may also be utilised for the prediction of the most relevant sample size for the full-scale project and/or to improve the multiple aspects of the study design as a whole. This has also been seen that most of times RCTs are not at all time and cost-effective (Flick, 2015). So, this is very much necessary that the researchers have complete confidence on the key stages that they shall be undertaking while performing the research so as to avoid time and resources. Pilot studies are basically conducted for the overall evaluation of the feasibility of some of the crucial components of the full-scale study. On a typical note, these can be divided into three distinctive aspects. The first being the **process** where the feasibility of the key stages associated with the primary research gets evaluated. Instances of this aspect mainly comprises of recruitment rate, retention levels and eligibility criteria. The 2nd aspect of a pilot study is **resources** that helps in the assessment of issues or concerns associated with time and resources that might occur during the conduction of the primary research. The 3rd and the final aspect in this case is termed as **management** that is associated with issues related to data management and with the team engaged in the study (Walliman, 2017). There are also necessary and valid reasons for not carrying out a pilot study. Research should not be generically labelled as a “pilot study” by researchers with intent to justify a small sample size. Pilot studies should always possess their objectives associated with the feasibility and need to inform the researchers about the most promising and effective way for the conduction of future prospected and full-scale project.

One of the most essential requirements of any undertaken research is to ensure that appropriate research results are derived that would conclude the relevance of any study. However, it may be one of the most difficult tasks to be sure that the research is progressed in a proper direction and the results are consistent. Therefore, in order to focus on the effectiveness of the undertaken study, one of the steps that many researchers undertake is to indulge in a pilot study. The pilot study refers to the small-scale test of the methods selected for the study. This is done for determining whether the finalized methods are feasible in the current context and the standards which are being followed are suiting the purpose of fulfilling the research objectives or not.

In this specific study as well, the researcher turned to conduction of a pilot study in order to

identify any potential issues with the chosen methodology and make appropriate and essential alterations as per requirement for obtaining more value out of the collected data and ensuring that the research process is on the proper track. The primary aim of the pilot study conduction for this study has been to ensure effectiveness of the questionnaire which will be used for the interview. The researcher has wanted to test whether the questionnaire designed is sufficient for the main study or any other modifications are required to be made. The pilot study has been conducted considering a small number of entrepreneurs from the Nepalese community residing in UK. Five interested individuals have been selected for the purpose of the pilot study. The interviews have been conducted with these five individuals and different aspects have been observed for analysing the effectiveness and clarity of the questionnaire used. Firstly, it has been observed whether the respondents during the pilot study are able to understand the questions asked to them. Secondly, the time required for each of the five sessions is recorded and the average time has been calculated. This time calculation helped in understanding the amount of time which can be taken up by the respondents while conducting the main interview. Thirdly, the participants have been asked to provide feedbacks regarding the interview sessions. The researcher has asked the respondents whether any questions could be added to the questionnaire or any modifications can be made. The participants have been chosen on the basis of non-probability purposive sampling technique. It has helped the researcher to select interviewees on the basis of the purpose of the research by considering the convenience of both the researcher and the participants. From a list generated from the internet in terms of Nepalese entrepreneurs, some had been chosen on the basis of their informed consent and agreed upon time of both the parties. The researcher developed the questions on the basis of data gathered earlier for the literature review. The knowledge and information in terms of the gathered article, the questions have been formed by the researcher.

The carrying out of the pilot study helped in understanding the compatibility of the respondents with the questionnaire. The feedbacks of the participants have proven to be valuable since certain modifications in the questions helped in attaining detailed and more subjective answers from the main respondents. This approach contributed towards enhancing the reliability and viability of the study findings (De Costa *et al.*, 2019). Poor and improper research instruments can result in collection of inappropriate and useless information which can result in deviation from the scope of the study. Therefore, it is essential to make sure and test the reliability of the instruments in obtaining relevant information (Engwa and Ozofor, 2015). The pilot study helped in highlighting the areas of improvement. The respondents who have been approached

for the pilot study have not been included in the list of the respondents approached for the main interview conduction. This has been done to avoid any manipulation with the responses of the participants (Sahay, 2016). Fresh set of participants have been included in the main study after modification and finalisation of the interview instruments.

The particular pilot study helped a lot in understanding the weak points of the interview questionnaire. Also, it portrayed out the way the interviews can happen or take place. It has been possible to make certain assumptions in relation to what kind of reactions can be received from the primary participants. The researcher has been able to get the chance to prepare adequately before carrying out the main study. The feedbacks from the five interviewees helped in further strengthening of the interview questions. The pilot study provided the opportunity to properly stage and plan the time of the interview sessions. The preparation positively contributed in effectively managing the overall time allocated for the research study.

3.9 Procedure of Data Analysis

Qualitative research data analysis is one of the most exciting processes and yet challenging which require systematic study and creativity to see developing patterns and should be able to write the discussion with significant conclusions (Patton and Cochran, 2002). There are no agreed and strict procedures for analysing qualitative data as in the quantitative data analysis. It about the nature of the enquiry depending upon the epistemological theories. The thematic analysis is adopted by the study where the researcher looks across information of all the data to distinguish the common patterns that persist then the main theme is identified, where all the collected data is reflected.

The data analysis initial steps begins with audio recorded transcripts then all of the transcripts and observational notes and field notes during fieldwork is reviewed (Maxwell, 2012). As per the comfortability of the participants, twelve interviews were performed in the Nepalese language. The researcher is fluent in both English and Nepalese. Thus, the researcher translates all twelve Nepalese interviews in English and confirm with an interpreter. All the file transcribed was printed out and made a preliminary observation along with through reading. Three types of coding were used- selective coding, axial coding and open coding (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). Open coding is the method of initial concepts noting down, breaking down and several themes development. Axial coding is done by open coding grouping into concepts and categorizing. The Selective coding is the third process which incorporates the concepts and categories. The

selective coding was commenced to allow gaining of knowledge of the relationship between codes and contrasting and comparing them with literature review and the theory (Dickson-Swift et al., 2007). The three steps of coding list are shown in Appendix 2

Table 3. 5: Procedure of the data analysis (Source: Dickson-Swift et al., 2007).

3.8 Ethical Considerations

In order to conduct research work with proper precision, the foremost necessity of a researcher should be to follow the ethical consideration with proper manner. The word "ethics" signifies to a set of principles which may help the researcher to conduct any work in a corrective manner. According to Bryman and Bell, (2015), "ethics can be described by level of appropriateness in the behavioural approaches of the researcher towards the work". More specifically, it can be said that to maintain the success of a research study, the foremost responsibility of a researcher will be to proceed with the work in an ethical manner. Especially when it comes to carrying out primary research, researcher should consider research ethics and other liabilities with proper precision.

According to Silverman (2016), there is a huge scope to practice ethical misconduct with the usage of the primary data and information as the primary data and information are mostly comprised with the anonymity and the confidentiality. As the principal objectives of this proposed work are to emphasise upon the factors which may facilitate the Nepalese small and medium scale entrepreneurs to enter to the UK market. And in order to carry out this proposed research work, both the primary qualitative and quantitative research methods have been carried out by the researcher. In order to conduct the survey, the researcher has taken consents from the Nepalese SMEs and similarly, in order to carry out interview, proper approvals have been taken by the researcher from the respondents. According to the Data Protection Act, 1998, the researcher has confirmed that the confidentiality of those data and information should be managed and those data will only be used for academic purposes (Taylor *et al.* 2015).

The researcher has ensured the Nepalese entrepreneurs that the personal information which has been obtained would not be used for any other purpose, it would not be employed to gain personal benefits. No third party would have access to the particular information. Careful attention would be taken to ensure safety and security of the information. The selected respondents and sample population would receive prior information concerning the motive and purpose for doing the research. It is important to state that transparency would be maintained between the researcher and selected participants. Care would be taken to prevent any kind of harm (emotional, physical, financial and so on (Mackey and Gass, 2015).

3.9 Limitations

From the context of academic research work, it can be said that there are several obstacles like time, budget and resources, which can hinder the successful progression of a research study to a greater extent. For this proposed research work, time and resources are two important obstacles which have the potentiality to restrict the research work from reaching to its ultimate conclusion.

Time: Time as a resource has been a constraint in relation to this particular study. This is because of the Covid-19 pandemic situations it has not been possible to access maximum number of individuals. The restrictions implemented in association with Covid-19 pandemic made it quite difficult to travel across different regions where Nepalese communities reside in UK. Only a few regions could be accessed in order to record the responses of the participants. Face-to-face interviews have not been possible. Therefore, telephonic interviews have been relied upon for the conduction of the study. Both time and access constraints have to an extent limited the possibility of gathering more responses for supporting the study (Smith, 2015).

Scarcity in resource allocation: The current study has focused on analysing the influence of challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating their businesses from UK market. Interviews have been conducted by the researcher for understanding the impacts of the risks, competitions and challenges faced by Nepalese SMEs operating in UK. However, during the coursework, research faced various problems when he approached the participants to take part in the survey and interview process. Moreover, the entrepreneurs were not enthusiastic enough to convey their internal information with the researcher. So, scarcity of proper and adequate information can be considered as one of the main limitations while it comes to construct a comprehensive conclusion on the basis of proposed research aim and objectives (Flick, 2015). It, in turn, impact the overall outcome of the research study to a greater extent.

3.10 Conclusion:

In order to conclude this chapter, it can be said that research methodology is an important and essential section of a research work, on which progression of research work depends to a greater

extent. The principal aim of this particular research work is to find out the factors and the threats which may influence the entry of Nepalese SMEs to UK market. So, the methods and tools should be selected by the researcher in such a manner, by which a comprehensive conclusion can be formulated. In order to meet the research, aim and objectives, positivism research philosophy has been selected by the researcher. Positivistic research philosophy is suitable for this proposed work, as it can give proper scope to the researcher to develop a concrete conclusion on the basis of the research content. Deductive research approach has been selected by the researcher for this proposed work. In order to make a justification regarding the selection of deductive research approach for this particular work, it can be said that every research is based upon certain generic conception. Those concepts are necessary to be relevant to the present research content to yield a productive outcome. Deductive research approach, which is also known as top-down approach relies upon accepting theories which are relevant to the research topic (Engwa and Ozofor, 2015).

So, in order to evaluate the factors which may influence the entry of Nepalese entrepreneurs in UK market, the foremost responsibility of researcher should be to develop some theories and concepts which can easily emphasise upon the proposed content. Descriptive research design has been selected by the researcher to analyse the content thoroughly for the purpose of developing a concrete conclusion. This proposed research work is based upon primary qualitative research method and thus both the survey and interview have been conducted by the researcher. In order to conduct the primary research method, Nepalese SMEs entrepreneurs have been selected as respondents. In order to conclude this chapter, it can be said that the success of any research work depends upon the proper selection of research methods, considerable, so researcher should provide proper attention while selecting methods for developing a comprehensive conclusion.

Chapter Four-Interview Finding:

The results from 20 semi-structured interviews with Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK is explained. In this study, the common characteristics of Nepalese respondents in the UK are described showing the Nepalese entrepreneurs various attributes. The results of abundant data evidence of the true experiences of ethnic Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK is revealed in this study. This is observed by presenting the study into three key themes: reasons to startup their own business challenges and issues, strategies for utilizing and acquiring finance and human resources.

4.1 Demographic profile of interviewees

The 20 interviewees of varied attributes, who contributed in this study are shown in this section (see also Table 4 below). The unique acronym is used to code each interviewee and is used in analysis and findings. For example, Int-01 signifies interviewee number. The significant fact out in the 20 interviews is that, only one respondent were women in the study. Therefore, this information indicates that Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK is male entrepreneurs predominant compared to female who reflect the effect of Nepalese social structure in the UK as well. First-generation migrants were all the interviewees. In this study, it is unique and interesting to find that the participants are very new migrants. Between the year 2001-2015, most participants came in the UK (see table 4 below). The Nepalese entrepreneurs' interviewees in the UK majority is ranged from 30 to 50 years. When they started their business, most of them were of 25-35 years old. Also, majority of the interviewees migrated in the UK for getting the higher studies. It is important to know that being first-generation Nepalese entrepreneurs, however, are young entrepreneurs and mostly migrated for attaining higher studies in the UK. This is an interesting finding which will be developed further and connected in the discussion chapter.

In this study, regarding the respondents, most of the participants had academic qualifications in higher level - Six respondents held a postgraduate degree in various subjects such as IT, management, hospitality and marketing. One was a qualified accountant and other was an aircraft engineer. Among them, nine interviewees had achieved higher education in the UK. Five had done Intermediate, eight had an undergraduate degree, and only two participants had school leaving certificates.

The data reveals primarily two types of migrants: economic and student migrants. Usually, most of

the interviewees joined their family who was already in the UK or came with their family. It is examined from the finding that the student migrants have involved in high- tech or service sector, whereas the economic migrants who came majority with a work permit have started their businesses in the restaurant sector. There is diverse sectors interviewees (Table 4 below) such as HR, care home, retail, college, restaurant, marketing, dental, beauty salon, but most of them are engaged in the restaurant sector. The interviewees majority, though few numbers of young firms were comparatively well established in the UK market, were also covered in this study. Few participants entirely depended upon their ethnic services and products. These entrepreneurs are involved in selling Nepalese cuisine and Nepalese handicrafts. The firms were selling ethnic services and products; nevertheless, open market was targeted by them. All the interviewees were married except one. In this study, the majority of interviewees were settled down in the UK in terms of the bought houses, permanent resident card, had relatives and were families. The interviewees observed that permanent residency obtaining in the UK was an important factor which offered an opportunity and made visa issues relief. Also, in this study, Nepalese entrepreneurs had families along with other close relatives such as sisters, brothers, aunties, uncle, sister-in-law who had been the substantial factor for utilising resources to start the business.

No.	Gender	Age	Migration purpose	Year of stay in the UK	Education	Types of business	No of businesses
Int-1	Male	47	Study	21 years	Project manager	Project management & Education Sector	2
Int-2	Female	30	Parent visa	3 years	Undergraduate in music and art	Dance and Music Institute	1
Int-3	Male	50	Work Permit	21 years	Undergraduate in Commerce	Off licence & grocery	1
Int-4	Male	30	Study	10 years	Postgraduate	Marketing and food company	2
Int-5	Male	42	Study	8 years	Postgraduate in Law	Solicitors and co	1
Int-6	Male	47	Dependent	12 years	Postgraduate	Cash & Carry	1
Int-7	Male	31	Parent visa	19 years	Undergraduate in film making	Film and Photography Studio	1
Int-8	Male	48	Study	25 years	Postgraduate in IT	Care Home	2
Int-9	Male	42	Study	11 years	Undergraduate in Marketing	Wine Wholesaler	1
Int-10	Male	44	Study	17 years	Postgraduate in Business management	Cash and Carry and Wholesaler	1
Int-11	Male	47	Economic	27 years	Undergraduate in Banking	Beer Company & Distributer	Many
Int-12	Male	50	Business	26 years	Postgraduate	Mexican Restaurant and bar	2
Int-13	Male	49	Study	20 years	Undergraduate in Business management	Gurkha club and Restaurant	1
Int-14	Male	43	Business	11 years	Postgraduate in Business Studies	Cargo and Money Transfer	2
Int-15	Male	43	Dependent	19 years	Postgraduate in E-Commerce	Online E- Commerce Business	1
Int-16	Male	43	Study	21 years	Undergraduate in gas safe engineer	Builder Company	1
Int-17	Male	37	Dependent	10 years	Higher secondary school	Printing, web-developer	1
Int-18	Male	40	Study	20 years	Postgraduate in Account and Finance	Accountancy Firm	2
Int-19	Male	47	Study	18 years	MBA	Catering Business	2
Int-20	Male	37	Spouse	13 years	Postgraduate in hotel management	Restaurants	3

Table 4: Interviewees Demographic Representation

4.2 Reasons to start own Business

The motivational factors diversity among the Nepalese entrepreneurs is showed by the fieldwork data in this research study which indicated that the motivational factors of the businesses could not be shown by a single factor but needed a various factors mixture (Basu and Altinay, 2002). The respondent's majority stated they had various motivations, thus supporting preceding research (Kirkwood, 2009; Deakins et al., 2009).

4.2.1 Cultural beliefs and values:

The study shows a substantial finding that Nepalese entrepreneurs are adaptable in a way that they are freeing themselves from certain cultural traditions and values which limit them in entrepreneurial behaviour. Nevertheless, they still have strong religious beliefs and cultural values and adhere these in their personal lives. For example, Int-7 and Int-20 who are of higher caste, i.e. argues that business is not tradition of their family. The tradition of their family is to depends on daily rituals and worship for livelihood. Below is stated on his own words:

"I am a Brahmin as my parents are Brahmin, and so 'Puja path" is done by my family. Every morning, we do "karma", "puja" and "dharma". We must earn money through "puja path" as per my religion. They didn't like me doing engaged in catering field. I totally choose the different profession" (Int-7)

As Int-4 states:

"I handle the pork, beef and everything though I still do not eat beef. As a person, It has not done any psychological effect but I still have that values in me. It's not that something will happen to me if I eat or I cannot eat, but it's just I don't feel like eating and I have not done it, and it's not superstition I just don't want to do it. but it's just my way of life I live".

Int-11 also mentions:

“Religion and cultural values do not influence me at all. We should not mix the culture and the business. If we mix our business and culture, then we cannot operate the business. For example, we are not allowed to cut meat as per my Buddhist religion, so I can't run my business, if I stop meat in my business by following Buddhist values. So, it is different. We have to separate our cultural, family, caste site and business site. I have not been inspired that much by religion and caste in the business. Maybe because from my young age, I have been in abroad. so that is why I do not discriminate and differentiate due to caste levels. These things may be present among other people but not in terms of my case.”

These repeated statements suggest that Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK are freeing up themselves from some religious norms and cultural values. The caste group in Nepalese society act as a barrier and restrict to entrepreneurial behaviour. In addition, as per hindu religion, majority of interviewees from restaurant businesses argue that, they are not allowed to touch and eat beef. The higher caste interviewee is not allowed to even touch any meat. However, the evidence demonstrates that their businesses are not influenced by these religious values. Some interviewees also stated that after coming to this country, they had started to eat beef. However, some argue that they were handling beef in their restaurants though they don't eat the beef. The few respondents were Buddhist and majority of respondents were Hindu, and many of their social network established based on the religious foundations and temple. Many of them also established small temples and religious shrines on their houses and the business properties but considerably businesses of the respondents are less influenced by their religion. Only a small number of interviewees have quoted the similar answers for the reason of their own business start-up which is "Business is in our blood..." (Int- 4, Int-16, Int-10). These same caste interviewees i.e. Newari, argue that they being Newari caste motivate them automatically to start or come into their own business. Newari is part of Vaisyas also termed as sub caste. The Vaisyas are the farmers, traders and money lenders. Most of the participants often mentioned a strong work ethic, which came out from the ethnic background of the respondents. Most of the interviewees stated the values of working long hours and hard work. The majority of interviewees statement represented the theme long hours work and hard work. For example, from interviewees own words as follows:

" We had to depend on our farm and field to get our dinner and lunch as we come from a poor farmer's background. Hardworking is the most essential. Those are my cultural values. We would be hungry, if we did not do hard work so from childhood, we learnt to do hard work. I used

to do paid job working for 16/17 hours a day so it came into my mind that if I can do such hard work for others for long hours, why not do to this hard work for my own and start my own job?"
(Int-5)

" Other people get surprised to find out that big shop and buy a house, I have done alone. But it's all my hard work. It is all due to my hard work. In a day, I used to work a minimum of 16/17 hours. I never think any job as small or big. I do not feel ashamed about doing any jobs I have also joined two jobs for 7 to 8 years. If anyone thinks that they cannot earn money in in abroad, I came to earn money in abroad. Why would I come to this country? If I was rich in back home."
(Int 11)

Most of the respondents associated with the environment in which they were brought up and the background with strong work ethic they came from and This environment made up the hard working tendency. The voices of most respondents in this study has same this kind of statement. Fascinatingly, all of the interviewees mentioned that they came from a poor middle class family and their main occupation was agriculture. Some interviewees described having a previous business in the family. On the other hand, some stated that their fathers were generally in the British army and the service sector. It is detected from the statement of participants that the source of inspiration comes from the values and attitudes of parents and family and their entrepreneurial behaviour. Many interviewees stated that they had a family background business and highlighted that their family has act as role model passing on the entrepreneurial values. The participants emphasized on the family context importance in which they had been brought up, which had taught them the values, experience, skills and guidance and established the imprint of the significance of operating their own business. The interviewee also mentioned that how they have been motivated to involve in entrepreneurial activities due to certain family backgrounds.

"I think that the background of family plays a significant role as well in running own business. So, Even if I was going to college for study, I have to look after my family business side by side to help my family as my father had his own business'' (Int-3)

Contrariwise, in some of the cases, the finding from doing the fieldwork shows that there is negative impact on entrepreneurial behaviour due to family background. For example, in the case of Int-13 and Int- 4, the background of Army family had constrained them to some level from involving in entrepreneurship. As Int-4 states below:

"I am from an Army family background as my dad, my brother and my granddad are in the army. Whenever, was I asked by somebody about what you want to be in the future? Then I had to say I want to be an Army officer I didn't want to be inside. I have to say it because my dad always wanted me to be a commission officer or an Army officer. Other than being Army, I wanted to study further. I always wanted to study and travel more because being army in 18 years old have restricted my study and I won't get a chance to see the real world. Just because my family background was from Army, I do not want to join Army as I wanted to do something different from that."

Moreover, the findings also illustrates that the interviewee decided to help in their family business so that they can have better future for their family. For example, the key inspiring factor for Int-13 is given below-

"The key motivational factor in operating my own business or running family business is for my daughter's and son's good future. There will be secure future as they don't have to struggle or work hard in the future".

These interviewees mentioned that they take the responsibility to support and help their family in the back home as well as in the UK. Mostly, the female Nepalese entrepreneurs says that they can have flexible time when their children are not well and sick and can fulfil their dual responsibilities such as the business and household tasks if they start their own business. In this study interviewees get influenced and encouraged from the relatives and friends who are already running their own business. The relatives and friends who are running their own business were one of the motivations for the interviewees such as Int-6, Int-8, Int- 11 and Int-17. These interviewees mentioned that as their relatives and friends were running their business which has encouraged them to select the similar sector and their relatives and family also helped them to operate or start-up the same business. As Int- 7 mention below:

“My friends who used to share and live in a same flat with us, they were operating the similar business and running the business very good. They are doing handicraft business and another paid job also which has encouraged me. They are having various sources of income has motivated me that I can also do the same as them.

He also mentions that:

“My other friend from my back home has encouraged me to do this business as he supplies and sells the handicrafts.”

4.2.2 Market Condition and Entrepreneurial opportunities and in the UK

This study identifies that all of the interviewees who has studied here to target the broader British market than the co-ethnic consumers. This outcome has distinguished the entrepreneurship behaviour of Nepalese from other ethnic groups (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990) which is discussed and explained in the next chapter. Both categories of interviewees i.e., economic migrants and students are involved due to the existing opportunity within the UK is demonstrated by the evidence. The studied entrepreneurs here are not restrictive to helping their ethnic and cultural niche, but they are aiming the conventional market by recognizing and addressing its opportunities. Amongst all the interviewees, the finding also discloses that the interviewees who have gained higher studies in the UK are more unified with the conventional support and are in high- tech and diverse sectors. For example, Int-19 who gained higher studies in IT in the UK, attempted to professionalize in order to operate the business operation portfolio with various business activities and opportunities and his business activities. He is expanding into various businesses such as publication, pharmacies, and restaurant (the Australia and UK), colleges in Nepal, E-works UK and real estate. He has been tremendously successful in global business. Similarly, some other interviewees also determine same entrepreneurial behaviour.

The study shows that most of the interviewees doing related non-ethnic services and products aiming the conventional market. Most of the participants addressing the British society needs and aimed at entirely non-ethnic services and products. These entrepreneurs are mostly operating care homes, liquor wholesaler, engaged in Japanese restaurants, online business, beauty salon and laundry. Most of interviewees running this type of business intentionally aiming to attract mainstream host community of non-ethnic clientele. Some participants entirely depended upon

their ethnic services and products. These entrepreneurs are involved in selling Nepalese cuisine and Nepalese handicrafts. The businesses are vending ethnic services and products; nonetheless, with open market target.

Additionally, the finding illustrates that some interviewees were running a business and living with entrepreneurship visas. These interviewees got an opportunity to leave to remain in the UK due to entrepreneurship visa. The study shows that Nepalese entrepreneurs was encouraged to live and settle in the UK and pulled to operate their own business due to visa and immigration policy in the UK. Int-20 has said that:

"To be honest, I have spent many years in the UK with the student visa and adopted the lifestyle here. Then tier-1 entrepreneurship visa provided me with the chance to live and settle here."

The visa and immigration policies can be a pull factor for Nepalese entrepreneurs as it aims to attract investors and migrant entrepreneurs. The study shows that few interviewees were encouraged to live and settle in the UK and pulled to operate their own business due to visa and immigration policy in the UK. Nevertheless, primarily, all the participants acknowledged that they have migrated in the UK via various migration schemes such as being dependent on a family, employment and study.

4.3 Utilisation and Acquisition of capital forms:

This section delivers an outline of how Nepalese entrepreneurs utilized and acquired various form of capital required for starting and running business in the UK. Various types of capital are classified into three forms such as social capital, human capital and financial capital.

4.3.1 Education Level:

The study shows that Nepalese entrepreneurs not essentially look in their field of study but look for chances in the UK market, For example, Int-1, Int-2, and Int-19 had an theoretical background in IT field and engineering which shows that they have comparatively low avoidance uncertainty and are not scared to come out from their comfort zone. This is a remarkable finding which is further explained in the discussion chapter. Additionally, the finding shows that the most of the interviewees are and priorities their education as they are very well educated (see table 4.1). The interviewees mainly migrated to UK to gain higher studies in this country because it has a high status for the education. Although there are the first- generation Nepalese entrepreneurs in the

UK, they are young generation remarkable number of interviewees are highly educated. The table 4.1 clearly shows that the participants majority were of 25-35 years old when they operated their business and most of them came in the UK between the year 2002-2016. The finding also shows that the interviewees gain education irrespective of their caste and ethnicity. In other words, the educational allocation does not show much variation between caste and sub-ethnicity among Nepalese entrepreneurs.

Most of interviewees who had gained higher education from other developed countries and in the UK are acquiring competitive advantage by exploiting the host country cultural capital. The finding illustrates that the interviewees with higher education, particularly who have gained higher education in the UK rely on the ethnic network in lesser amount compared to using the conventional support and they are in high-tech and diverse sectors. For example, Int-3, int-13, Int-15, Int-19 and Int-20 have similar opinion who acquired higher studies in IT in the UK. For example- *“I use advisory strategy and I use outside networking contacts as I don’t trust on the Nepalese community for support and advice. I have a personal mentor and I have a consultant who provides suggestions on different aspects.”* (Int-19).

“I do not go to Nepalese community shows rather I go to many trade union shows and international shows.” (Int-3)

The substantial interviewees number in this study speak out related views that their life has been easier acquiring higher degree associated to their business. The interviewees reveals that education has helped to gain confidence by developing communication skills with conventional stakeholders and given reliability although education has not directly involved in their businesses. It has provided a professional method and they did not need to depend on upon somebody. Most of the participants stated that education facilitated them to improve analytical and managerial skills such as making strategies, forecasting, and planning to maintain accounts. The participant associated the education role in improving other managerial skill and communication skills for their business. Most of the participants studied here have no language barrier as they have achieved fluency in English. These respondents stated that their communication skills have been improved and confidence has built up with conventional stakeholders and offered credibility due to education. For example, Int-2 mainly emphasizes his linguistic skills to acquire integrity in his field.

“I wanted to improve my accents and I really worked on my English accent. Working in education sector really requires to have the proper English and it gives you confidence if you could speak proper English.” (Int-2).

On the contrary, the participants who studied in Nepal with a low level of education have stated that they are still confronting a language barrier regardless of living in this country for many years which is constraining them to develop and operate their business.

“We are the first generation in this country and there is a gap. Anyhow I cannot be like Whites as we are brought up and born in Nepal. So, it constrains us to join in other conventional sectors such as property business due to which I still feel a gap in there. Sometimes, I cannot understand certain things when I go to the seminar. So, even though I am living here for 25 years, I still feel a gap in the language.” (Int- 20).

“I also must work in front and deal with big clients and companies as I was running my own business. Working in back office is not a challenge for me. But I have to rely upon others for official writing things as I feel less confident and little uncomfortable while writing formal stuff and communicating which negative impacts on my business.” (Int-13)

The participants who had studied back home mentioned that they have to manage to continue their education regardless of the hardship life. Most of entrepreneurs illustrated that there were limited courses due to the restricted education facilities access in the distant places and even in the capital city of Nepal. Due to the scarcity of good universities and colleges in the villages, respondents had to go to India or come in the capital city (Kathmandu) for acquiring higher education and had to pay huge amount of money for tuition fees, daily expenses and accommodation. This evidence reveals that the most of the participants had managed to acquire an education and prioritised the education regardless of less infrastructure and the difficulties. Most of the participants have achieved education related to the business, which has become the very motivating factor for achieving the human capital and resources needed for their business.

4.3.2 Use of prior skills and experience

The vast number of interviewees have mentioned that the most significant learning method to gain knowledge and skills is the previous experience. In this study, almost all the participants have acquired experience either with some professional bodies, or in non-family organization or in the family business. Most of these respondents achieved experience by working for certain time for

others to acquire the cultural capital and resources of this country, such as lifestyle, culture and language. Participants such as Int-2, Int-3, Int-4, Int-10, Int-12, Int-15, held up a better positioned job by migrating for higher studies in the UK. For instance, the Int-2 is an aeronautical engineer build a mainstream network by working full time in the office where he gets a chance to learn the corporate system as well, and he also looks after his restaurant in the evening. Likewise, Int-4 was an IT manager in the UK in the big company and states that:

“Even if you belong to different sector, you can manage the people as it is the same people they have different factors but same expectation that encourage them. So, that is transferable skills regardless of you are managing people in one place.”

Some respondents had previous experience in the business. These participants states that they have gained a lot of knowledge from the prior business experiences which has helped to deal with the opportunity of the market.

“I had some prior businesses did not run well, but I have moved into this business by learning from the mistake.” (Int-10)

4.3.3 Depending on informal sources:

The study finding illustrates that the respondents are using social networks intensely to acquire information access for business development and operating the business. It is stated that all the participants in this study relied on professionals intensely such as solicitors and accountants within own communities of Nepalese. The participants in this study acquire and seek information and advice from their own social networks such as seniors and friends from Nepalese communities. There are various ethnic communities gather for cultural programs, ritual occasions which offer good platform and opportunities for gaining information.

“We have many of meetings of communities, and some meetings are after we have dinner meetings which get an importance and then you may get some help or business advice from them as well if needed.” (Int-15)

“It is very comfortable to collect all information and communicate with a Nepalese Solicitor and Nepalese Accountant. It is more comfortable to clarify my issues with them and I do not want to misunderstand anything or miss any information.” (Int-12)

However, the participants who had studied here and are highly educated do not solely depend on social networks for acquiring advice and information. They mostly use formal sources for information and advice. For instance, Int-1, 6, 16 and 17 states that the communities are all about celebrating festivals, cultural occasions, and ceremonies due to which there is a paucity of supportive workshops in the Nepalese communities.

In this study most of the participants inclined to live in nuclear families. They also stated the substantial family role either indirectly or directly. Most of the participants stated the importance of family role for business development and start-up. In this study, the family members have been working as the primary workers for their own business where many businesses are managed and operated by family members. For example, Int-14, Int-15, Int-20 mentioned that venture of their business is a wife- husband partnership where his wife plays an important role in the decision making and management. Similarly, Participants of women in this study have emphasized on the significance of husband's support being marketer and a handyman and for operating their business. For example, Int-14 says:

“My husband has helped me to fix and set up everything in the business. He is a handyman and very supportive for operating the business. That's why family is very essential”

Likewise, Int-16 says:

“My business is running well and growing due to help from my family members. My brother-in-law and my wife are a chef, and the frontline of the business is managed by my daughter as a manager who also looks after the accounts. We work hard as everybody in the family is working for ourselves. I think this is the primary cause of the success of my business.”

Though Int-16 is employing his family as the essential workforce immensely, he states that he considers them as other employees related to other entitlements and wages. Also, some participants mentioned that their partners have given financial support and moral support by covering expenses of the family by working during the starting period of their business. Participants such as Int-3 and Int-5 remembers how their wives have covered the expenses of the family by working full time during the beginning phase of the business when they could not get any revenues from their business. Int- 10 also states that his wife has been running charity organization actively which has provided him good recognition rather than her working in his

organization directly. It can be observed that many participants have been hiring potential staffs through the social networks. Nepalese Facebook page has been used for job vacancies post from where they were taking the advantage. Nevertheless, only some participants desire to employ staffs from their ethnic group or community. Most of respondents likes to employ from diverse communities' group.

4.3.4 Finance

It is surprising and remarkable to identify that most of the respondents had less challenges in acquiring financial capital. However, the prior studies have indicated that financing is a substantial obstacle for the most of ethnic entrepreneurs (Deakins et al., 2004). This is further explained in the discussion chapter later. The proof provided by the entrepreneurs shows that they depend on the informal sources of finance heavily. The table below (4.2) shows that even the respondents with a higher level of education are not utilizing a formal source of finance. The result illustrates that most of the respondents used their savings to operate and run their business. The vast participants has depend on their savings totally either from previous business in terms of Int-2 or accessing finance through working paid job. Normally, respondents have saved a huge amount of personal savings from a paid job for long hours working hard, and then utilized those savings as the finance source to operate their business, which indicates high saving mindset among them. Likewise, the respondents accessed financial sources through many sources such as borrowing, own savings from families and friends, credits from different party, bank loan, credit rotating association and micro-credit association. These sources are interconnected, and even the majority of the participants were retrieving the finance by combining these sources or using various sources. The high tendency of borrowings from families and friends shows a high level of ties and trust among their families and friends which helped to collect informal sources of finance clearly which is a related finding to the prior studies (Basu & Altiney, 2000; Fraser, 2004). Some respondents had finance access using microcredit associations and credit rotating associations. Most of the participants denied going to banks for getting financial help.

“My father lent me £55000 which he happily gave me and that was usually I got 50 percent from back home from my father.” Int-9

" It was hard to start the business as the start- up phase because the bank over here charge high interest for the first borrowers. Why would I go for the banks if I can borrow money from friends and relatives for interest free for a certain time. ” (Int-19)

None of the respondents depend on only on conventional sources for retrieving the financial capital to operate their business. Some participants have utilized informal source along with a formal source i.e. bank. These respondents have stated that they have considered from the bank loans at the beginning phase, as they were able to make and present a good business plan along with good credit history. However, some respondents refused taking a bank loan, stated that it was not easy to get bank loan being a student. Additionally, in this study, it was revealed that some entrepreneurs started their business as a partnership with relatives and friends to share the capital, which helped them to put together resources to the business start-up. Here, the collaboration is a generic form for starting the business for Nepalese entrepreneurship. The evidence shows that the respondents inclined to depend on their families and families for accessing finance heavily for the start-up business. The high tendency of borrowings from families and friends indicates a high level of trust and integration amongst their families and friends. Therefore, this outcome has helped the theory of ethnic entrepreneurship which clarifies that the social network offers access to financial support and builds clientele network and businesses which facilitates in start-up and development of the business (Waldinger et al., 1990).

Interviewees	Forms	Own savings	Friends and Families, communal association	Bank loan
Int-1	Partnership	Partly own saving	Some financial help from family	No
Int-2	Partnership	Own savings	None	Bank loan(easier)
Int-3		Own savings from prior business	No	No
Int-4	Partnership	Some own saving	Partly borrowing from father in Nepal	Some credit from a different party
Int-5	Partnership	No	Micro credit association(NFF)	Bank loan
Int-6		No	Friend credit	No
Int-7	Partnership	Own savings	No	No
Int-8		Own saving	No	Bank loan
Int-9		No	Friends borrowing	Bank loan
Int-10	Partnership	Own saving	Friends borrowing	No idea in the beginning)
Int-11		Own savings	Dhukuti (credit rotating association) and friends borrowing	Bank loan (20000)
Int-12		Own savings	None	none
Int-13		Own savings	No	No
Int-14		Own savings	No, but have micro credit association	No
Int-15		No	Friends credit	No
Int-16		Own savings	Dhukuti (credit rotating association)	No
Int-17		Own savings		
Int-18		Own savings	Loan from friends	No
Int-19		Own savings	No	Bank loan
Int-20		Own savings	No	No

Table 4. 2: Sources of accessing financial capital: (Source: Fieldwork)

4.4 Issues and Challenges:

The findings mainly shows that the issues and challenges are related to the different levels such as macro, meso and micro aspects. The issues and challenges facing by the participants were common rather than to any particular ethnic influence.

4.4.1 Complexity of Regulatory in the UK

Most of Participants have emphasized on the complexity of regulatory bodies in the UK and difficulties in staffing which are connected to the problems such as restriction to the international students, the changing immigration rules and immigration status as discussed in the literature review (Bagwell, 2018; Ullah et al., 2016). Majority of participants have raised the challenges in start-ups and development of businesses due to huge barrier of immigration status. Most of respondents states that they were not sure when they will be kicked out, up until they have obtained a residency permit, rules for immigrants keeps on changing by the home office in The UK.

“I am in a dependent visa and my wife is a student due to which visa status is a huge barrier to live and operate the business. There is a high risk for my business as home office keep changing the immigration rules and my visa is not permanent.” Int-16.

Additionally, most of participants have stated the regulatory factors of this country is strict. They have described they have to follow the regulation and rules of the UK strictly. Even though most of the participant has stated the complexity of regulatory, they also consider that these regulations and rules are there for some useful reasons. Int-12 states:

“There are long procedures and many challenges in paperwork such as, home office, council. Like in Nepal, I cannot just open up a shop right away. There is lot of paperwork to do here such as health and safety certificate, certificate for butcher, and have to get a license to sell alcohol. Furthermore, I must complete the training and send CRV check to the council then council gives us a card which only allows to sell alcohol. After that, we have to also get closing and opening timetable from DPT.”

“You have to look after small-small things including hygienic, health and safety, employee's right, each and everything. So, it is very tough and there are lots of challenges.” (Int-8)

In this study, the impact of Brexit has appeared as a new challenge in operating the businesses. Brexit has created a market uncertainty which has reduced their confidence. Participants who depend more on buying products and raw materials from overseas were worried about the rise in the price and tax. Int-2 states that:

“Any business you run is extremely depends on the regulatory and government policies. For instance- rules and regulation or Brexit. So, government legislation has lot of impact on running the business because this is an extremely regulated industry, and everyone cannot execute the business due to lots of rules and regulation to follow and meet up.”

“The major existing challenge is the Brexit. Brexit has affected immensely in the business. And Many Europeans are gone back to their country from the UK due to Brexit.” (Int-11)

Similarly, although not many respondents had challenges in term competition, these competitions are due to other conventional competitors rather than increase in Nepalese businesses. Various issues and challenges encountered by these participants were common rather than to any particular ethnic influence.

4.4.2 Staffing Difficulty

The acquiring and handling to human resources such as staff has become the most challenging issue for the tremendous numbers of participants in the study. Primarily restaurant entrepreneurs were facing obstacles in managing acquiring the staff. They mentioned that the new generation of people is not much fascinated to involve in the restaurant sector. The respondents were anxious and even worry about the low possibility of staffing in the UK's environment. The below statements characterize the opinions of the majority of other respondents:

“Due to the strict rules of home office, the staffing has become more challenging now. Before we used to and are allowed to employ staff from work permit, so we used to do, but now it is tough due to changing rules and regulation. Before there used to be lots of students who have precedence to work as part-time worker in the restaurant sector, but it has stopped now due to the tightening rules of government day by day. So, it is very tough to employ the staffs.” (Int-20)

He further explains:

"We have to follow proper methods due to strict rule of HM revenue and its becoming more difficult to get the staff day by day."

"Nowadays to acquire staffs is becoming more challenging as lots of Nepalese restaurants has close down due to strict rules implementation for students by government causing a staffing problem. Lots of colleges has been close down by the government and people are no more coming to the doorstep of the restaurant to get the job as compared to old days." (Int-20)

4.4.3 Managerial knowledge and Communication gap

The limitations of skills of the participants, such as the knowledge gaps and communication barriers can be regarded as the micro factors. Most of the participants are within this research are still facing a communication gap though they are young and well-educated. They have raised up some of the communication issues despite of some of the participants have studied in the UK. Int-19 stated that:

"I used to struggle being an immigrant in operating the business in early days as English wasn't our first language. I did not use to get good response due to lack of confidence to speak and negotiate with the other party. I used to think that I'm not part of this community but now I have learned the accents and I prepared myself to go to various events with the help from a mentor."

"I understand and can speak the English, but was not confident enough to speak with banks, British customers and the suppliers due to difficulty in understanding the accent but I am adjusting into this environment slowly." (Int-12).

There are only a few participants who have achieved formal training related to their job. Many participants stated that due to lack of knowledge in business, they have faced difficulty in operating the business. The participant mentioned that operating the business without gaining related business knowledge and proper market research will leads to difficulties start-ups and development of the business.

As Int- 4 mentioned his challenges:

"I did not have any training, and ideas in running the new business which was the big challenge for me. So, I faced many difficulties for the first six months of opening even to survive."

The outcome shows that the Participants got the training were some sort of short courses such as Hygiene, and Health and Safety. Rare participants got formal training because of their business nature.

4.5 Conclusion:

This chapter describes the findings obtained from the interviews performed with 20 Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. The emerging themes and common themes from the data are now discussed further in successive chapter in details. The results are related to the literature review and conceptual framework discussed in chapters 1 and 2.

Chapter Five: Discussion

Introduction:

The research aims to investigate the influencing factors for the start-ups and development of ethnic Nepalese entrepreneurship in the UK. The prior chapters show the 20 interviewees findings. This chapter aims to offer informative understandings by linking finding to the literature review along with research objectives. Thus, this chapter demonstrate some of the central themes of the findings and provides its analysis. The developing themes are underlined and extended in for the discussion in this chapter in detail.

5.1 The first-generation young Nepalese entrepreneur

The finding demonstrates many participants arrival in the UK is in between the year 2001-2015. This finding clearly shows that Nepalese entrepreneurship still the first-generation in the UK. and Nepalese migration new phenomenon in the UK while the first generation entrepreneurs from other Asian community (including Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India) migrated early 1970s and in the late 1960s (Dhaliwal, 2008). This finding clearly distinguishes other Asian ethnic groups from Nepalese entrepreneurs. Education is considered to be important for employment opportunities has been the primacy among the Nepalese community in the UK(Laksamba, Dhakal and Holford, 2012). The Education in Nepal has huge reputation for UK education. As Dhungel (1999) says only the highly educated people travelled to the developed countries because ordinary and uneducated people in Nepal cannot meet requirement to get access to visa applications nor can they meet the arrangements of expenses for pre-departure. Now, it is vital to mention that the highly educated are migrated in the UK who can meet financial expenses. This trend has affected entrepreneurial behaviour. The participants are heavily intertwined with their own religious beliefs and cultural values. nevertheless, it is restricted to their private life. The interviewee has a tendency to be incorporated with the host society and willing to leave some of the values and tradition. This is an interesting finding which marginally undermines to the other Asian groups prior study (Dhaliwal, 2000; 2004); youthful Chinese entrepreneurs in the UK (Chen et al., 2019). According to Dhaliwal (2004) , the first generation entrepreneurs are tremendously interconnected with their own values and tradition and that they created an environment at home and work as per their security and comfort. Additionally, author states that the first generation does not incorporate with the host society whereas, Nepalese entrepreneurs

have enlightened themselves from certain religious beliefs and cultural values. The strong proof such as despite of being from higher caste and selling beef items in their restaurant, participants touching and eating meat. They are alright to give up certain religious beliefs and cultural values and are ready to integrate in the host country. This finding also validates previous study conducted by Dhaka, Laksamba, and Holford (2012) which explains that Nepalese are adapting to local context and adopting new skills trying themselves to reinvent in the new host society. This indicates Nepalese entrepreneurs' adaptability nature. This socio-economic form is associated to the pluralism melting pot also known as Culture Assimilation where the ethnic group are willing to embrace host society patterns, preserving private life from culture (Dana, 2008; Dhaliwal, 2004). Nepalese entrepreneurs educated and young have been inspired by UK culture and its education. Therefore, they tend to establish deliberate assimilation into the broader population. The freeing nature engaging in entrepreneurial behaviour are facilitated by certain cultural values. It is fascinating to emphasize that Nepal is the Hindu country slaughter of cow is forbidden by law and will be punished harshly. According to Hindu mythology, cow worship is an inherent part of Hinduism the cow being a symbol of the goddess Laxmi which symbolizes abundance and health, so this ritual is practiced by Nepalese from years and years ago. There are many proofs prevalent which show that there is harsh punishable act for cows slaughtering in Nepal (The New Indian Express, 2018). All Hindus in Nepal are prohibited to eat beef, and meat is considered as impure among high castes, which should not be touched as per the religious belief. These findings show less impact of caste and religion for encouraging the participants to operate their own business which seems contrary to the other studies findings (Basu and Altinay, 2002). According to Basu and Altinay (2002), religion does not impact as anticipated in the conducted study on different ethnic groups in London. Nevertheless, there were certain ethos and values were associated with their cultural values which are associated in their business (Morris and Schindehutte, 2005).

5.2 Challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs for growth and development of their business

The data analysis chapter highlights the several challenges that are faced by the Nepalese community in developing and running their business in the country. Some of the most highlighted challenges are *business finance, laws and regulations, language, competitive market,*

customer base, finding the right employee, etc. As has already been discussed, financial challenges are the most important challenges for the Nepalese Entrepreneurs since most of the respondents agreed that they did not receive any kind of financial help from the banks and financial institutions in the country (Veronica *et al.*, 2020). The financial institutes, they believe give easy loans to English entrepreneurs since they belong to the country and for immigrants, they have to show their loan credibility. However, some of the respondents had a different view towards these challenges as they believe that financial loans from banks in the country are for entrepreneurs who can show their loan credibility and also believe that with the right kind of credibility any one can get loan irrespective of their nationality.

Language barrier has been identified as another challenge in the growth and development of entrepreneurial projects in the country as a few strongly believed that language had been their greatest challenge in attracting and retaining customers in the country. It is believed that customers prefer visiting businesses where the communication is proper and for many Nepalese entrepreneur, communication is the greatest challenge (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2016).

Many responses during the interview also indicate that laws and regulations in the country are quite challenging for the growth and development of business. Mostly respondents agreed that despite of the strict rules and regulations business can flourish depending on the level of abundance of the set rules and regulations. The policies of the government are conducive for business development hence majority of the respondents have agreed that the business policies do not pose any challenge for business. However, on the other hand finding the right employee for the business and retaining the customer base in face of competition in the market has been seen as one of the most important challenges for the Nepalese entrepreneurs especially in the food and beverage industry. The entrepreneurs in the Nepalese community also shared important information that there is least help from community when one is involved in a business thus it could also be an important challenge for retaining customers whereas other Asian communities are better-knit and have the support of their community.

This study has successfully revealed the fact that immigrant entrepreneurs from Nepal had been facing way too many challenges in contrast to the native entrepreneurs in the UK. The former individuals face barriers for instance; they find it way more difficult to arrange for funds and resources to start off with their business ventures and to keep it going at the same time. Particularly the Nepali immigrant entrepreneurs tend to face many challenges such as difficulty to access finance; many of them are not too comfortable in speaking English and also face stiff

competition from large scale businesses (Okřęglicka *et al.*, 2015). In addition, other challenges also follow suit. These have also been identified through the responses gathered from the recruited respondents and the responses provided by them during the interview session. The other challenges which have been identified through the interview session are trust issues from locals and unfamiliarity with documentations related to tax, permission and other sorts of regulations. These issues faced by the Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs have been discussed in this chapter in detail.

5.3 Access to capital and resources

One of the foremost challenges that are being faced by Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs associated with the UK market and inhabitation is the lack of access to capital. Since these individuals do not possess or showcase a long credit history, collateral and guarantee, it has become way too difficult for these entrepreneurs to gain access to financial support from banks and other governmental agencies associated with funding the start-up ventures. As per the responses generated by the twenty recruited Nepalese entrepreneurs during the interview session, it has been found out that all these individuals had to use their own savings and also borrowed from their family members and friends for the overall establishment of their businesses. This has also been identified as one of the many reasons that many businesses remain operational under partnership. Because of the lack of operational finances, businesses fail to survive in the long run and this is one of the many fears that such immigrant entrepreneurs have reflected in their interview. Furthermore, it has also been identified from the respondents' interview responses that they have tried their level best to gather finance from funding agencies as well as from the fundraising events organized by the UK government and other charity agencies. On the contrary, this has also been mentioned by many that because of their low credit score and lack of formidable credit history, it becomes difficult for them acquire funds. With respect to the UK entrepreneurial field, it is literally difficult to acquire funds provided the individuals are immigrants or lack the awareness of mortgage liabilities (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2016). This has also been identified by the interviewees that UK governmental regulations are stringent enough towards ethnic entrepreneurship. The funding agencies provide funds depending on the evidential backup that the borrowers might reflect in regard to the loan. Under such circumstances, it becomes difficult for the entrepreneurs to gather fund because of their low credit history. Moreover, being immigrants is another

restricting factor these individuals face while collecting funds for their start-up. The findings from the data analysis (chapter 4) are in agreement with the findings obtained from the literature review. The reviewing of the existing studies showed that it often becomes difficult for the immigrants to transfer their credit history to UK. As a result of this it becomes difficult for the immigrants to prove their credibility in front of the UK banks (Moghaddam *et al.*, 2017). Failure to meet the bank requirements and loan policies is making it hard for the immigrants to request for bank loans. The review findings also stated that government grants are there however in this case also the process is full of loopholes and turns out to be time consuming. Those who have been able to access the grant they have stated that the process is difficult and takes up so much time that it is not at worth the effort. All these things are demotivating the Immigrant entrepreneurs to consider any financial assistance from the UK government.

5.4 English language proficiency

The 2nd biggest challenge faced by most of the respondents as stated in their interview session is their lack of proficiency with English language skills. Most of the participants in the interview indicated that being Nepali is itself a reason behind not knowing much English since they are mostly associated with speaking in their native language that is Nepali. Language barrier is a challenge that invokes most immigrant individuals in such developed economies and provided these individuals intend to open up their own business, then it becomes way more difficult for them attract and communicate with customers. Since the customers themselves are local people residing in the UK, it is quite expected that they would prefer to communicate in their own language. Lack of English language proficiency eventually results in severe gap of communication in between the owner of the business and their customers. Furthermore, it also becomes difficult for the sellers to understand the needs and demands of the customers with varied necessities. Although this research is not dedicated towards identifying the relationship between the type of business and types of products/services being sold by the start-up companies with that of the challenges acquired, but this is indeed a crucial indicator. One of the respondents did highlight this issue by stating that often customers wish to have products which are available in super markets but at an affordable rate. As per the interviewee, this is the reason for which customers tend to visit small stores rather than visiting the supermarket aisles. The interviewee has also suggested that it becomes difficult for them at times to even understand the type of products that the customers need. Because of the lack of availability of such products in the store, the number of customers keeps on decreasing at an alarming rate.

When asked how is it related to the language barrier that is supposed to be the main concern in this phase, the interviewees have suggested that it is impeccable and because of lack of proper awareness of the type of products that the customers intend to have in the aisles of the stores and the prevalence of miscommunication amongst the sellers and buyers, the growth has become stunted. If these findings from the data analysis are tallied with the findings of the literature review, then maximum similarity can be observed. Besides problem regarding communications with the customers difficulties in case of networking have also been identified from the statements of the other studies. The language barrier results in poor networking and contact development within the market (Falavigna *et al.* 2017). It is highly essential for entrepreneurs to have a stable and strong network in the market so that they are able to access materials and market finished goods in an effective manner. A reliable network and distribution system and retention of proper contacts significantly help in smooth functioning of the business and lowering of the business expenses. Therefore, it is analysed that not only Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs face difficulty in communicating with the consumers but also face challenges in building contacts and networks within the UK market.

5.5 Potential competition for Nepalese being immigrant entrepreneurs

Most of the businesses run by Nepali immigrant entrepreneurs are associated with service sector in the UK. For instance, there are more than 30 Nepalese restaurants present in London only. The competition is far too high in this sector, on the other hand. In addition to this, the market is rather pretty big as for the UK is concerned. It is a developed economy of the world and hence, the prospect for entrepreneurs is also pretty high. this is the reason almost every service sector in the UK have been penetrated by new entrants with heightened marketing strategies so as to gain as much profit and attract customers as possible. The large scale businesses from the similar sectors have also started to pose threats as they continue to influence the pricing strategy, marketing and suppliers. Some of the interviewees have also mentioned that large scale businesses continue to act as threat for their businesses to grow and proliferate further (Paul *et al.*, 2017). Similarly, competition comes from other fellow immigrant entrepreneurs associated with the same sector of business as well. Under such circumstances, it becomes difficult for the entrepreneurs to carry forward a dominant foothold in their sector. Moreover, fund lack and incapability of accessing of funds and lack of resources have also contributed to this challenge. This has been seen and understood by many that in

order to mitigate such competitive environment and dissolve the negative impact of potential competitors, it is very much necessary to invest further in stockpiling and inventory management so that more number of customers can be attracted by offering all varieties of products. Because of the incapability of such attribute, the Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs keep on facing such competitive hurdles. The findings also indicated that the growing number of new comers within the market is resulting in more competition for the existing entrepreneurs. This is associated with increasing population of immigrants in UK. The new comers like the existing ones are also coming up with potential business ventures and setting up start-ups within same or different sector. For example, the findings from the literature review showed that an increase in the number of new business ventures has been observed in sectors like grocery, retail, restaurant, food and beverage, etc (Saarinen and Nepal, 2016). There are growing restaurants within the UK market which is one of the most preferred business ventures by the immigrant entrepreneurs. As a result of these activities the competition is increasing for the immigrant entrepreneurs. The existing immigrant entrepreneurs are finding it difficult to cope with the growing competition. They have to come up with innovative and creative solutions and strategies for sustaining their business in the UK market.

5.6 Distrust from locals

This research study has also highlighted the fact of distrust being imparted from the locals upon the immigrant entrepreneurs at the beginning of their business that has also been found to be similar to various pre-existing research findings. One of the disadvantages for immigrant is the lack of social networks and friendly acquaintances alongside networking with relatives, schoolmates as local entrepreneurs do which acts as an important social capital for any start-up venture and helps with overall business growth. In this research too, all the respondents have agreed to the fact that locals doubt and distrust at the beginning of their businesses. For instance, the experience of one of the interviewees reflected the fact that young customers welcome such prospective growth in business environment around them but on the contrary, the same is not true in case of mature and elderly customers. Hence, many entrepreneurs have also thought of employing local individuals with a minimal pay so that the trust of local individuals acting as buyers and customers can be achieved. One of the respondents has also highlighted the importance of remaining associated with the local language in order to integrate

with locals and win their trust at the same time. According to his statement, it was not at all difficult for him to create a professional network as he was proficient in the English language.

5.7 Rules and Regulation

This study has also emphasized on the fact that Nepali immigrant entrepreneurs lack the proficient understanding of the British legislations and company acts and policies alongside the taxation system needed to run a business. Most of the interviewees have pointed out that paperwork related to regulations, taxation system and requirements for opening up a business is also a challenging aspect for them. These respondents have also reported during the interview session to the researcher that paper works are way too time consuming in the UK owing to immigrant entrepreneurs and is also bureaucratic at the same time. They have also stated that such is the case because of their societal background and the fact that they are immigrants in the UK owing to which there exists a trust issue in between them and the nation as a whole. However, they also have appreciated for the fair and transparent work of officials at the same time. In this case, having proper interpersonal communication skills with least miscommunication and language gap also seemed to be pretty much important.

5.8 To identify about undertaken steps by the immigrant Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK to deal with these challenges

The challenges as responded by the entrepreneurs are temporary which means that challenges like finances, communication, etc are temporary as they agreed these were challenges in the initial days but with time, they had overcome these challenges and are now well set in their business. The most important factor however is *time*, many agreed that time is the best factor that helps a business grow. Majority stressed on the importance of market research as market research helps an entrepreneur to understand the market in order to develop the products and services that he/she wants to bring in the market. Almost every one suggested that a successful entrepreneur would be the one who would follow the rules and regulations of the government. The rules and regulations are stringent in the country but when one follows these rules and regulations it would be easier for the entrepreneurs to develop and grow business. Each and every one has stressed that proper market research is must for growth and success of a new business. One who does not do a proper market research is not likely to succeed as this would lead to false information about the market. When there is proper information about any kind of

product in the market it is easier for a business to develop the products and services accordingly.

There are several steps and measures that the Nepali immigrant entrepreneurs have undertaken in order to resolve or to a certain extent dissolve the aforementioned and identified challenges in the way of their business growth and profitability. There is absolutely no doubt that immigrants investing time to learn and acclimatize to change are very much likely to overcome the barriers to succeed in the UK (Masood and Sonntag, 2020). Business is usually based on a trusted relationship and hence, adaptation to business customs and work culture of the UK is a key to success. As per the interviewees, the researcher understood that it is very much necessary to identify and be aware of these aspects as well as the strategies by which the business existence and its sense of prosperity amongst the customer forum can be entailed. Integration henceforth has been considered to be an on-going journey. Language is also stated to be a challenging scenario amongst immigrant entrepreneurs coming from Nepal in the UK. Immigrant entrepreneurs without language barriers are much more likely to learn, establish networks and understand business practices as compared to those associated with language barriers. Those with language barriers need to have the willingness to invest much more time to become acquainted with English otherwise, one may start off with a business to earn a living but to be successful, communication and proper interaction with customers is the key. Hence, the interviewees have also stated that they have tried their level best to have a proficiency in the language and not to impart Nepali trail while communicating with dealers, suppliers and customers. Because of the difference in culture amongst the Nepalese and British cultures and society as a whole, it also becomes tedious and difficult for the immigrants to acclimatize in the new environment. Hence, the interviewees have stated that it is upon the entrepreneurs to conduct a priority check. If one wishes to be successful in his/her business, then the cultural disparities need to be bridged up and resolved at the same time. At times, it is very much necessary to compromise with the new environment in order to become successful. Establishment of the community has also been reported to be another lucrative strategy that the entrepreneurs have implied for resolving the challenges. Immigrants who have an established community to welcome them have an obvious advantage over those who do not. These connections eventually help the entrepreneurs to increase their social connection and networking possibly through the *word-of-mouth* marketing strategy. Their acquaintances are also associated with various local individuals of the area who also come to know about the existence of such business thereby increasing the entry level consumer base. These connections

eventually help an entrepreneur to find translators, coaches or mentors, and keep one connected to resources which on the other hand provides a major advantage over those lacking this community.

Coaching and mentorship are another entry level strategy as reported by the interviewees during the interview session. Having associated with someone who has had practical experiences of acting as a role model, advisor and sometimes keeping one accountable that is also considered being invaluable. These individuals will not only help other avoid mistakes that they had went through during their tenures but will also open their network in front of the others and sometimes may also help to close significant business deals by giving good reference. Hence, the interviewees have also sought for such strategy and some of them have also harnessed success in the long-term growth trend of their start-ups. Finally, the interviewees have also mentioned that implying tailored support for meeting immigrant specific needs is also another considerable strategy that can help to resolve such issues (Kumar and Singh, 2017). This has also been accounted to be the role of the government, non-profit organisation and other service providers so as to ensure that immigrants gain complete accessibility to satisfy their specific

needs and to help them integrate the UK business community. The research studies undertaken by authors as stated in the previous segments of this study have also implied that immigrants who come to the UK from Nepal under the economic class that are especially those selected under the categories of self-employed, entrepreneurs and investors- immigrate the transnational borders with specific entrepreneurial goals and are most likely to start businesses with non-ethnic focus thereby targeting non-ethnic clientele. On the contrary, researchers have also focused on the fact that most immigrants entering the British border under other immigration categories without specific entrepreneurial objectives are more likely to turn their focus towards entrepreneurship out of necessity. Therefore, they start off with ethnic ventures such as restaurants and small businesses catering their ethnic community. Those who are associated with entrepreneurial goals are also found to be well prepared for overcoming challenges of starting and operating a successful business. This is particularly because they need to confront the local people and convince the non-ethnic clientele to do business with them. However, these individuals have been found to be a minority. On the other hand, most immigrant entrepreneurs start off with their businesses out of sheer necessity because they are incapable of finding a relevant job or any type of employment opportunities in their field. In the worst scenario, this has also been seen that most individuals opt for start-up ventures because of being

laid off from their previous employment. Immigrant entrepreneurs hailing from this category struggle a lot to overcome such challenges.

Another thing has been observed from the literature review and data analysis that majority of the measures and steps have been taken by the entrepreneurs by themselves for supporting and operating their businesses. The Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs have been identified to acquire required knowledge, experience, skills and contacts on their own by struggling and learning from practical situations. They had emphasised on learning on their own, refinancing their skills on their own and gaining knowledge about the different UK market rules and regulations on their own. They used their perspectives and ideas for setting up the businesses and continuing with the same. They have experienced from their failures and learned from them.

5.9 Help and support from the government or Agencies

The previous sections had identified the challenges faced by Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs in the UK and the measures implied by them to dissolve these issues. This section focuses on the supports and assistance received by the individuals through governmental intervention for expanding and marking their business dominance in the field. In the context of the United Kingdom, the legislations have supported the provision of start-up funds followed by associating the entrepreneurs with proper training, counselling, mentoring, development and grooming, and information and advice to mainstream as well as immigrant entrepreneurs. On a similar note, this has also been identified that there are several state-owned companies in the UK which also provides financial support to the small and medium sized enterprises as well as to large companies. Furthermore, there are other non-profit organisation associated within the UK territory as well which support small and medium sized enterprises with the help of financing, offering training and mentoring ad providing information. Likewise, the various multi-agency support systems are also available which offers business courses, seminars and business information to the potential entrepreneurs.

Even though the UK business service system offers support systems to the immigrant business owners, it is also plausibly true as being reported by the recruited interview participants that they had been completely unaware of the availability of such support systems. This had eventually resulted in their lack of utilization of such supports to survive and grow their business in those crucial times. Above all, all the interview participants had not even contacted

or sought support from service providers from the very beginning of their businesses. Most of the recruited respondents have stated that they were completely unaware of the presence and/or availability of such support systems. Almost six out of twenty participants mentioned that they were badly in search of financial support to survive and grow their business at the same time of this research. However, some of the interviewees have also supported their responses with the fact that they had sought financial support in the form of loans from neighbouring banks to support their start-up. Some of them have also been known to seek for personal loans (Bhachu, 2017). In a nut-shell, all the participants associated with this study had highlighted the needs of business information, financial supports, professional as well as personal networking system for the sake of growing their business. Findings from this research show that most of the Nepali immigrant entrepreneurs do not use support provided by the host country. However, this has also been reported that they use their own savings and social capital such as finance, business information and human resources from family members, friends and peers.

There is significant help and support from the government during the pandemic situation. The responses from many respondents signify that although there was no help from banks for financial support but during the pandemic the government has supported small businesses which highlight the attitude of the government towards the entrepreneurs in the country. The rules and policies are equal for everyone and there is no biased attitude towards any community doing business in the country. Thus, it could be said that although few challenges exist for Nepalese entrepreneurs in the country these challenges can be overcome with time. Most of the entrepreneurs from the community have overcome these challenges with time and proper planning and have grown their business significantly.

The findings have shown certain loopholes in the arrangement of the UK government for supporting the SMEs. The lack of awareness and difficulties faced by the immigrant entrepreneurs in attaining market information is showing that there is need to develop effective training programmes and workshops by the government. Currently there is no such provision for the immigrant entrepreneurs. These entrepreneurs till now have relied on personal savings, friends and relatives as contacts and community-based consumers for supporting their business ventures. They have not received any training from the government or any institutions meant to support the SMEs. The respondents have repeatedly reflected that they have to make arrangements and research on their own in order to operate in UK. The findings from the analysis and the review have not provided any evidence regarding the existence of training and

skills development assistance from responsible institutions. Therefore, there is requirement for the government to come up with strategies which can increase awareness among the immigrant entrepreneurs about the market opportunities. The government is also needed to address the loopholes in the present system for lowering the challenges faced by the immigrant entrepreneurs.

Conclusion:

This chapter aims to offer informative understandings by linking finding to the literature review along with research objectives. Thus, this chapter demonstrate some of the central themes of the findings and provides its analysis.

Chapter 6: Conclusion, Contribution, further research, and Recommendation:

The chapter is going to provide a summary of the study carried out. The discussions and evaluations in this chapter have considered addressing the objectives and research questions developed for the study. Along with these the chapter also include contributions of the study, further recommendations, and limitations of the research and further opportunities of research in this field.

The particular study has aimed at identifying and understanding the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating across different regions in UK. The reason behind conducting this study is the lack of literatures on the challenges faced by Nepalese migrants when they try to set up and run entrepreneurial ventures. The percentage of Nepalese migration has increased over the years and it is worthwhile to understand the scenario of entrepreneurial ventures carried out by the migrants. These entrepreneurial ventures are significantly contributing towards the positive economic growth in UK. Findings from the study can prove to be useful for the UK government and the Nepalese communities. Findings from the study can prove to be useful for the UK government and the Nepalese communities as it will help them improve so that the challenges can be mitigated.

6.1 Conclusion

The Nepalese communities will be able to deal with the challenges and facilitate their business. The UK government will be able to find opportunities for supporting the entrepreneurial ventures which are beneficial for the economic growth of the country. In total three objectives have been developed for the study. They are - 1) to understand the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs for the growth and development of their business in the UK, 2) to identify about the steps undertaken by the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK to deal with these challenges and 3) to find out if Nepalese Entrepreneurs getting any substantial help and support for the smooth operations of their business in the UK. Six research questions have been developed for fulfilling the research objectives. The answers obtained from the findings have been summarised in this chapter against each of the questions.

6.1.1 What are the main challenges faced by the Nepali community in conducting business in the UK?

Funding or finance has emerged as one of the primary challenges faced by the Nepalese

entrepreneurs while operating businesses in UK. From the analysis findings it has been observed that Nepalese entrepreneurs mostly depend on their savings and investments in order to start and continue with their business ventures. They do not consider taking loans from the banks for supporting their businesses. The business environment across UK has been regarded as easy and conducive by the respondents of the study but they are of the opinion that they have to arrange the funding by themselves. Accessing of loans from the UK banks depend on credibility and it is significantly difficult for the Nepalese entrepreneurs to retain the required credibility expected by the banks. The findings from the analysis further highlighted the fact that the entrepreneurs from the Nepalese communities being foreign nationals in certain cases do not match the credibility requirements of the UK banks while on the other hand the British nationals do not find it hard to avail the loans since they are natives of the country. The findings from the literature review have been found to be in agreement with the findings of this study. The review findings pointed out that finance is one of the primary challenges faced by the immigrant entrepreneurs in UK. Certain reasons have been identified which state that it becomes difficult for the foreign nationals to transfer their credit history to UK. This is a requirement for matching the bank credibility and as a result it becomes difficult to avail loans. The findings have also highlighted that the UK government grants exist only to the British nationals to start entrepreneurial ventures and if Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs try to access them then it turns out to be too time consuming and challenging. Discriminations it a great factor contributing towards funding challenges faced by the Nepalese entrepreneurs.

The second challenge which has been identified from the analysis is cultural discriminations or barriers. Language barriers has turned out to be a challenge for the Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating their business in UK. Most of the respondents have stated that they have faced language barriers and discriminations as they could not speak the local language which is English. Language has turned out to be a challenge for the Nepalese entrepreneurs while operating their business in UK. Majority of the respondents have stated that they have faced language barriers and discriminations because of not able to speak the local language of UK. Inability to speak fluently in English has often led in poor communication with the target audience which in turn has impacted growth of the business. Belonging from a different culture has also resulted in discrimination because of which the Nepalese entrepreneurs have found it hard to set up and run their business ventures successfully in UK. The findings from the literature review have also pointed out the language barriers make it difficult for the immigrant entrepreneurs to socialise with others in the market. Language barriers hindered the

opportunities of effective networking and sharing of ideas. The third primary challenge which can be understood from both analysis and literature review findings is that of competition. The number of new entrants in the UK business environment is increasing and it is becoming challenging for the existing entrepreneurs to sustain and continue with their ventures successfully. The existing business owners have to update and modify their services or products in order to ensure development of competitive advantages. Most of the entrepreneurs have been found to establish their business in the food and beverage sector within which the competition is increasing with passing time. The findings from the literature review have further stated that Nepalese entrepreneurs also facing competition from renowned UK based organisations. From the literature review section, it can be further stated that the Nepalese entrepreneurs also facing competition from renowned UK based organisations. Besides, they don't have good knowledge about technology which the British companies possess. As the world is stepping towards innovations, customers are expecting new technological change which the immigrants fail to provide due to low or no knowledge about the technology. They require support for learning new technology. This is a challenge for the immigrants' entrepreneurs.

In addition to the funding, cultural and competitive challenges the Nepalese entrepreneurs have also been observed to experience challenges due to rules and regulations of the UK business environment, inability to recruit suitable individuals, Covid crises, belonging from a different background, etc.

Cultural differences have been found to influence the success rate of the small and medium sized business owned by immigrants. Cultural factors like language, beliefs, values, viewpoints, etc. have been found to be impacting the networking, communication, promotion, and other processes carried out by the immigrant entrepreneurs. Cultural barriers have been found to limit the availability of financial resources for the immigrant entrepreneurs. The difference of cultural background facilitating one group of entrepreneurs and limiting the facilities for another group has been observed from the findings of both literature review and the data analysis. The entrepreneurs belonging from the White British groups and other native communities do not face that difficulty in availing loans from banks and government grants. However, the entrepreneurs from other cultural backgrounds especially those who are from immigrant communities face several barriers in availing the grants. Loans are not possible for the immigrant entrepreneurs as being foreign national they will not satisfy the credibility standards expected by the UK banks. Cultural discriminations existing within the system are delaying the process of availing grants

provided by government for supporting the business operations of the immigrant entrepreneurs. Language barriers in the context of cultural barriers are also restricting the capabilities of the immigrant entrepreneurs. The Nepalese entrepreneurs have to face difficulties in communicating and networking with others in the market. Poor communication and networking as per the respondents are harmful for the growth of the business. Both literature review and data analysis findings have pointed out that language barriers do slow down the development and expansion of the businesses. The immigrant entrepreneurs have to adapt with the UK culture, language and norms in order to support their business in the market. Though they are adapting UK norms and culture, but still they face discriminations and barrier for being foreigners.

6.1.2 Do the immigrants get substantial help and support from the government for smooth operations of their business in the UK?

The findings from the data analysis have reflected that the rules and regulations of the UK business environment are supportive towards helping entrepreneurs to set up businesses. It has been repetitively stated by the Nepalese entrepreneurs that if the rules and regulations of the market are followed effectively then it becomes easy to carry out the businesses. The literature review findings are in agreement with the findings of the data analysis. The review of the literatures highlighted that UK is one of the easiest markets to penetrate and set up businesses. The rules and regulations established and implemented by the UK government are in favour of assisting all sizes of entrepreneurial ventures. In relation to the entrepreneurial ventures UK government has arranged for various provisions and grants. The country emphasises on supporting the small and medium business ventures, since these businesses positively and significantly contribute towards the economic growth of the country. This shows that immigrant entrepreneurs are getting substantial support and help in terms of setting up and running business ventures. However, one aspect has come p which has questioned the flexibility of the support provided by the UK government. This is associated with the funding challenge faced by the foreign nationals. The government grants are not all the time accessible by the immigrant entrepreneurs. Either they are failing to meet the credibility standards or the entire process of availing government grants is proving to be time-consuming and unreliable. Discriminations are also there within the system which is preventing the availing of funds and other provisions by the immigrant entrepreneurs. In one scenario it can be inferred that the rules and regulations by the UK government are not that stringent. The business environment in UK is welcoming towards all kinds of business ventures. But discriminations are resulting

in the development of gaps within the financing system. Funding is a crucial element to be considered before starting and supporting the running of the business. The present arrangements by the UK government in this case are not proving to be supportive for smooth operation for the businesses by the Nepalese entrepreneurs.

6.1.3 What are the steps undertaken by the SMEs in the UK to deal with these challenges?

The SMES are following different measures to deal with the challenges identified and supporting business processes. Immigrant entrepreneurs to cope with the funding challenge depend on their own savings and investments. In order to support their businesses by depending on the savings or investments the immigrant entrepreneurs look for convenient places to set up their ventures. The respondents of the study have stated that they open up their businesses within areas where their community exists. This helps in getting support and also the places turn out to be cheaper in comparison to other areas in UK. The places which are the immigrant hubs are targeted by the Nepalese entrepreneurs for establishing their businesses and also the targeted customers are from the communities. The opportunities are more across the immigrant hubs. The number of immigrants is increasing more with time and as a result the Asian population is increasing within UK. Therefore, the immigrant entrepreneurs are targeting the Asian customers and coming up with varied business ideas. Besides carrying out careful investments and spending on business the Nepalese entrepreneurs also rely on detailed research and experience. Majority of the entrepreneurs establish business after gaining adequate knowledge, experience and skills. The literature review findings showed that immigrant entrepreneurs pay a great deal of attention in strengthening their knowledge, skills and competencies in order to conduct successful business in the UK market. From the responses of the participants, it has been inferred that most of the respondents came to UK for continuing higher studies. After completing their MBA or other management degrees they have realised that they have better opportunities to start in UK and therefore used their knowledge and experience to do so. For handling the challenges of a foreign business market, the Nepalese entrepreneurs have relied on extensive research and understanding of the UK market.

The immigrant entrepreneurs have been found to abide by all rules and regulations of UK. They are of the opinion that the rules and regulations are strict but are not that difficult to be followed. The entrepreneurs have been constantly following the rules and regulations for avoiding any

unwanted consequences. The findings showed that the immigrant entrepreneurs adapted themselves with the rules and regulations of the market as well as the culture of the market. Therefore, it can be stated that the Nepalese entrepreneurs have tried every possible measure for establishing and supporting their businesses in UK. They have been found to gain adequate knowledge and conduct market research. They have focused on selecting suitable locations for ensuring effective utilisation of their monetary resources and proper attracting of the customer segments. They have learnt and prepared themselves for surviving in the foreign land.

From the findings of the literature review and the data analysis it is noticed that no such programmes have been arranged by the UK government for the immigrant entrepreneurs for starting their business and continuing with it. In other words, it can be said that the immigrant entrepreneurs rely on their experience and self-acquired knowledge mostly for establishing their ventures and supporting them. The review of other studies has highlighted that knowledge can turn out to be a challenge for the immigrant people looking towards setting up their own business. A local or native of the UK will have no problem in accessing networks, funding and market information. In case of an immigrant, it is not possible to carry out such detailed market research. The immigrants mainly come to UK for completing higher studies and stay back in the country to establish their start-up and acquire the country visa. All they are receiving is University knowledge and academic skills and competencies. They are not receiving any practical training and awareness about the real market. While starting a business in a foreign land an entrepreneur needs to be aware about the regulations, taxation, ways of acquiring networks and contacts, understanding the needs of the market, procuring proper funds and so on. The Nepalese immigrants are found to come up with their own understanding, research, strategies and funding for setting up their businesses. In fact, they are locating their business in areas which are primarily the immigrant hubs. They are not trying to seek out areas outside the hubs since they will result in more challenges and difficulties. Also, the funds are limited for the immigrant entrepreneurs. Whatever the immigrant entrepreneurs are doing to support their business they are carrying it out on their own. The study did not show any assistance from the part of the UK government in the form of training programmes and campaigns.

6.1.4 What steps should be undertaken by the government of the UK in order to facilitate the growth and development of SMEs owned by Immigrants from other countries?

The findings from the literature review and data analysis highlighted many areas which are required to be addressed by the UK government for helping the immigrant entrepreneurs.

Firstly, it is necessary for the government to address the issues identified in relation to funding and financial support. There are no such loan systems which can be easily availed by the immigrant entrepreneurs for continuing with their business operations. Also, the grants provided are challenging to be accessed by the immigrant entrepreneurs. The UK government needs to identify the gaps and discriminations in the systems which are resulting in investing of more time for accessing the same and lastly resulting in the failure of the attempt. Strategies are required to be taken up for helping the entrepreneurs to access the grants easily. The government can also come up with effective loan systems which can help the immigrant entrepreneurs to support their business. Secondly, the UK government must come up with and arrange effective training programmes, campaigns and workshops for supporting and helping the immigrant entrepreneurs to gain necessary knowledge about the market. Through such programmes and workshops the entrepreneurs will get the opportunity of developing necessary skills and competencies. They will also get the chance of carrying out suitable networking. Thirdly, the government needs to create awareness among the market about the positive and crucial contribution of the SMEs towards the UK economy. In this way a large portion of the investors will get attracted towards investing in the business ventures by the immigrant entrepreneurs. There is need for investment, awareness, removal of discriminations, education, training and modification of the funding system which will further enhance the opportunities for the interested immigrants in operating their entrepreneurial ventures across UK and contribute towards the economic growth of the country.

The study concluded that presently Nepalese entrepreneurs are facing different challenges while operating their businesses in UK. The challenges include financial and funding problems, lack of training programmes and skills development programmes on the part of the government, cultural discriminations, language barriers, networking and contacts and increasing competition from new entrants. UK government is in need of focusing on all these challenges and consider taking up different measures for lowering the challenges. This is necessary since such entrepreneurial ventures form a significant part of the country's economic growth.

6.2 Contribution of the Research:

6.2.1 Contribution to the knowledge

The research potentially helps in identifying the major challenges faced by the Entrepreneurs belonging to the Nepalese community of the UK. It thus potentially helps by addition of the knowledge about the ethnic community in the UK. The findings of the study contributed towards inducing the fact that various challenges faced by the Nepalese entrepreneurs are influencing their business operations. The research is further ensuring enhancement of the perceptions of the readers regarding the challenges faced by immigrant entrepreneurs in UK and in what way the country is tackling the challenges. With the enhancement in their immigration in the UK, the interest in the community and various aspects related to their business activities has increased (Maharjan, 2018). The research would potentially support this by providing more information about the challenges faced by them. The study has aimed towards increasing the level of awareness of the readers about the characteristics, attitude and behaviour of the UK business environment towards the immigrant entrepreneurs. The effectiveness of the UK market rules and regulations, the influence of the regulations on the business ventures of the immigrant entrepreneurs, the challenges faced by immigrants in UK market while setting up businesses, the arrangements made by UK government for reducing the challenges and encouraging the SMEs, etc. have been focused upon in this study. These concepts will help in enhancing the level of knowledge of readers regarding the opportunities and difficulties of setting up business in UK. The differences in the challenges faced by the immigrant entrepreneurs and the British entrepreneurs will contribute by highlighting the cultural differences existing in this field of setting up and operating business ventures (Bhattarai, 2020).

The study has also contributed towards the awareness of the readers by highlighting the main problem which is discrimination that turned out to be challenges in setting up business in a foreign market. The interview findings have also pointed out that the British entrepreneurs can easily access financial grants provided by the government while the entire process is complex and time consuming for the study aids in identifying and understanding this issue and thus gaining knowledge about this aspect would help these individuals to address the challenge to be successful in the UK business market. The knowledge that is gained from the research potentially helps the individuals of Nepalese community to identify the areas of

communication that they need to strengthen and order to remove the challenge. The research also contributes to understand and gain knowledge about the government rules and regulations related to the business in UK. It also potentially helped in understanding the difficulty of these policies from the perspective of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. The research enabled in understanding the Conducive nature of the UK government policies. It helps in gaining a broad knowledge regarding these policies and helps in adding up to the theoretical perspectives of these policies. It also helped in understanding the extent of help that is received by the Nepalese entrepreneurs from their own community during setting up business and retaining customers. Thus, the research potentially adds up a broad theoretical knowledge that would help in identifying the challenges and addressing them substantially to support the Nepalese community to do the business in the UK.

The research study also enhances the knowledge of the readers by pointing out that immigrants form a minority community in foreign markets. The Nepalese community in UK turns out to be a minority community constantly facing challenges and differences while setting up and continuing with their business ventures. The findings from the review and interviews have represented that there is need of awareness among the immigrant communities regarding the opportunities and the arrangements provided by the UK government in supporting the running of SMEs. SMEs have been realised to be important sources of economic growth continuously supporting positive improvement of the country (Jones et al., 2014). A significant portion of the GDP is ensured through the contribution of the SMEs. UK government has addressed the importance of the SMEs towards improving country's economy and therefore has made the provisions of various grants which are meant to help the entrepreneurs to continue with their business ideas. But the study focusing on the influences of the challenges faced by Nepalese entrepreneurs have identified that immigrants forming minority communities in UK are deprived from many of the UK government provisions. The conduction of the study has helped in creating a foundation depending on which measures can be taken for further increasing awareness and helping in improving the business condition of the Nepalese entrepreneurs operating in UK (Connolly et al., 2014).

The research also helps in gaining knowledge about the steps that are taken by the Nepalese entrepreneurs in addressing the challenges and coping up with the issues. The research enabled to understand that all these challenges are not permanent and can be solved or eliminated with development and implementation of proper strategies. It says that these challenges are prevalent only during the initial days of business set up and once it is established and starts to

run efficiently these challenges significantly gets reduced. This thereby helps the new entrepreneurs to understand the ways through which the challenges can be solved. The research broadened up the knowledge about various factors such as time and market research that would help the business organizations to grow and drive the success of the Nepalese entrepreneurs. The study has highlighted some positive aspects of the UK government like supportive rules and regulations, an welcoming business environment and has also highlighted some gaps in the system like inability of the immigrant entrepreneurs to access financial help from the country (Anand, 2020). It also helped to understand that how the lack of proper market research would be disadvantageous for the business growth. The research also broadened up the literature regarding the help and support that the government provides to the entrepreneurs of the UK. It also helped to understand the take of the UK government in restoring and maintaining equality in the UK business market by implementing policies and rules.

6.2.2 Contribution to the practice:

This research has mainly focused on the investigation of the factors which influences the business start-ups as well as development of ethnic community Nepalese related to Entrepreneurship in the UK. This research has also provided the practical implication of the strategies related to entrepreneurship for the Nepalese community. Entrepreneurship has been contributing efficiently for the growth and development of the country as the entrepreneurs uses the creative as well as innovative ideas in order to develop the products which are meeting the demands of the customers and it leads to the higher income as well as reduction in the problem of unemployment. The Nepalese entrepreneurs who have successfully pursued their studies and got the skills in the country UK are having the knowledge related to the mainstream market. However, there is lack of attainment of practical knowledge among the Nepalese entrepreneurs. The study reflected that it often becomes difficult for immigrants to gather the right information for supporting and starting their businesses in a foreign market. Considering this fact, the institutions responsible for supporting the SMEs' growth in UK need to come up with workshops, campaigns, presentations, etc. which can provide the immigrant entrepreneurs with proper links and networks to run their businesses smoothly. The policy makers can focus on designing and implementing policies which can facilitate the attainment of financial assistance by the immigrant entrepreneurs. Also, the business managers working in different organisations across UK can arrange for training and development programmes which can help in enhancing the level of knowledge and skills of the immigrants seeking employment.

This research is immensely beneficial for the Nepalese entrepreneurs, and it has provided the visions for identifying the opportunities as well as the benefits from accepting the fact of existence of diverse cultures in the society. Diversity always leads to several benefits as people come to know about different cultures and with the help of the strong relationship among the different cultures the business can grow immensely. The Nepalese Entrepreneurs should try to expand their business contacts in order to get the support and the opportunities from different ethnic communities. For the development of business in the developed country UK it is equally important to obtain the experience and to get the information related to the business management from different ethnic groups (Yan *et al.*, 2021). The findings have shown that Nepalese entrepreneurs are not able to access contacts and build networks in the UK market easily. They mainly look for help within their communities since there is a scenario of language barrier. Also, an aspect of British and non-British exists within the market which hampers network development and contact building. This is an area which is required to be taken into account by Government for improving its support towards the SMEs' development. There is need on the part of the government to provide arrangements which can assist the Nepalese entrepreneurs further develop their skills. By developing the communication skills, the Nepalese entrepreneurs can overcome the barrier or issues related to the development of the company. If they can obtain the whole knowledge of English which is mostly spoken in the UK, it will be easier for them to communicate with stakeholders of the business which will also lead to gain the confidence for interacting related to the business. The business organisations have mainly focused on the cultural events instead of only the business workshops which have led to the development of the Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK. This research study has also provided the Nepalese community for implementing the strategies of growth in the practical life. They should also focus on the necessity of the developing the networks with various ethnic groups for understanding their point of views, thought process, innovative ideas etc (Bhattarai, 2020). Diverse culture helps in applying different ideas which eventually leads to the growth of the organisation. The most important thing based on this research study which has contributed to the practice is that the women of the Nepalese community are not being restricted for only doing the household work, but they are allowed to other work or activities which can be beneficial for the society as well as for them. It is extremely important for encouraging the women to work and for doing the things which they want to do. The significant role of the women entrepreneurs should be implemented in practice.

The Nepalese entrepreneurs had to face several challenges while starting their start-ups in the country such as the rules and regulations of UKBA have been quite complex in nature and it is also difficult for them to follow but with strong determination they have been able to sustain the business in the market (Zhao *et al.*, 2017). This particular study has also provided the in depth understanding as well as evaluation of the first-generation entrepreneurs for the policy makers. The first-generation entrepreneurs indicate that the young entrepreneurs who are well educated, they also have the ability to adapt within the different cultures and they also do not follow the stereotypes of the religious beliefs as well as the cultural values. The Nepalese entrepreneurs has only focused on the opportunities of growth and the development of the business in the UK and the policy makers should make the policies for helping such kind of businesses so that they do not suffer from problems due to the policies (Maharjan, 2019). It has also been observed that the entrepreneurs are unable to take the advantage of the business support or the advice due to the reason of high charges and these could not afford the high cost charges as they cannot afford it. In this context the research study has also provided the practical implication for the local governments and the local councils for the necessity of the support system which can help efficiently in resolving the issues for the small business of ethnic minority population. However, this research study has effectively contributed in the practice of Nepalese entrepreneurs in the UK (Pathak *et al.*, 2018).

6.3 Limitations and Areas for further research conduction:

Every research has certain limitations which can impact the generalizability or transferability of the study findings. The study relied on conducting interviews considering 20 participants from the Nepalese community in UK. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic situation it has not been possible to approach more entrepreneurs. For that reason, only 20 participants are considered due to lockdown in the UK. If the restrictions would not have been there then some more contributions could have been obtained which would be useful for the research work. Moreover, the study is limited to availability of data due to time as well as geographic constraints. The sample size is quite small. The sample is not representing the entire population of Nepalese community residing in UK. Time and access constraints have limited the participation of individuals. Therefore, the transferability of the findings can be at a questionable position. Further research can consider the participation of more respondents from the Nepalese community living in UK. In the future, studies can also focus on the role of Nepalese women in conducting business from the UK market along with changes seen in the business. Conduction of mixed research can result in the

attainment of alternative findings in comparison to the present study.

6.4 Recommendations

Based on the analysis section, recommendations are provided so that the problems faced by the Nepalese entrepreneurs can be mitigated to a great extent. Nepalese entrepreneurs should be provided opportunities to create their own business in the UK as they may have interesting ideas that can create monopoly business. Besides, allowing new entrants in the UK can create numerous jobs as they will hire local people for business purposes. Providing access to financial capital will help them conduct business easily and pay back banks easily. Globalisation has brought multicultural people together and Thai should be taken in a positive way so that they can further create something new and innovative that can be different from the existing business in the UK. Nepalese entrepreneurs have to learn diverse marketing strategies so that they can be capable of doing business without help from other business organisations. Besides, they need to hire local employees to get ideas from them about the business market. This is a useful initiative to hire local people and ask about the trending business. Local employees have good ideas about the trending business and this can save their precious time. In addition, before starting business Nepalese entrepreneurs have to learn the local British language so that they can communicate easily with people and discuss their ideas with them.

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Appendix:

1) Open Coding

- C1. Use of Nepalese art and architectures (cultural resources)
- C2. Desire for independence
- C3. Migration to study
- C4. Gained work experience in family business
- C5. Cultural gain in the host country
- C6. Cultural values and beliefs limited to personal life
- C7. Ethnic and non-ethnic products
- C8. Multiple businesses
- C9. Aware of good business location
- C10. Mainly non-ethnic market and small percentage of ethnic group
- C11. Difficult to sustain targeting only ethnic group
- C12. To have own identity
- C13. A social status
- C14. Family support
- C15. Financial support from family
- C16. Partnership for finance
- C17. Own savings
- C18. Challenges in staffing
- C19. Advice from Ethnic network
- C20. Moral support from ethnic social networks
- C21. Student migrant seek advice from formal sources/mainstream
- C22. Lack of supportive workshops within ethnic group
- C23. Close ties to co-ethnic
- C24. Active involvement in ethnic committees
- C25. Good team work and network (support system)

C66. Army background
C67. Don't want to follow family career tradition
C68. Priority to get education
C69. Enterprising and industrial childhood-engage in enterprising early age
C70. Went India for higher studies
C71. Had better job in Nepal
C72. Support due to prior business experience
C73. Change in immigration laws lead previous business shut down.
C74. Attend formal training and skills workshops
C75. Born and brought up in the village
C76. Childhood with limited access.
C77. Learnt good attitude from family values – brought up in well discipline in business
C78. Assets and Capital from prior business
C79. Wife involvement
C80. diverse staffs
C81. Good recognition through charity works
C82. No direct competition due to uniqueness of nature of business
C83. Mainstream networking
C84. Government laws and policies-Brexit influence
C85. Accountant from ethnic group.
C86. Lack of high level of employment support from co-ethnic.
C87. Barrier in English accent
C88..
C89. Remittance occasionally for family use
C90. Strong connection towards home country.
C91. Multi and diverse businesses
C92. High street location.
C93. Lower cost of product
C94. Caste influence to start own business-newari
C95. Previous business failure but learn at the cost of something
C96. Agriculture along with other occupation
C97. Ethnic residential and concentration
C98. Nepalese culture and tradition promoter
C99. Don't eat beef but sell it.
C100. Solidarity community
C101. Borrow from father from back home
C102. Wife support
C103. No formal advice
C104. Advice from seniors
C105. advice from partners

- C26. Hard work and long hours
- C27. Focus on Customer satisfaction
- C28. Network of supportive suppliers
- C29. Advice from co-ethnic Accountant and solicitor
- C30. To expand the business
- C31. Knowledge from experience/transferable skills of past experience
- C32. Knowledge and skills from education
- C33. Plan ahead
- C34. Education background different from current business
- C35. Non-ethnic product
- C36. Non-ethnic market
- C37. Gain work experience in same sector
- C38. Family have work experience in same sector
- C39. Education background in same field
- C40. Experience influence more than education
- C41. No formal training
- C42. Middle class family
- C43. Family background influence to start business
- C44. Culture does not influence
- C45. Recognition of opportunity
- C46. Difficult to get Bank loan
- C47. Easier to get bank loan
- C48. Advice from previous boss
- C49. Advice from ethnic social network
- C50. Low budget for accessing formal supports/mainstream
- C51. Challenge to compete with big companies
- C52. Lots of marketing promotions
- C53. No blocked mobility
- C54. Challenge to maintain health and safety
- C55. Challenge to maintain employees law
- C56. Diverse staffing
- C57. No Gender issues in the UK
- C58. Tier 2 entrepreneurship visa as an opportunity
- C59. Had better job
- C60. Prior business experience
- C61. Easier to recognise business opportunity having prior businesses
- C62. Research for business ownership
- C63. Easier in business ownership through right to operate under big organisation
- C64. Live near/ convenient location
- C65. Conduct market research for location

C187 establish good networking at work place
C188 location as per the nature of the Business-Big space
C189 Nepalese are in diverse sector of businesses at present
C190 to be independence/freedom working own
C191 good business opportunity in the UK

C106. Loyal and trust in business partner
C107. Difficulty in business ownership due to previous owner
C108. Happiness matters more than monetary value for success
C109. Stretch yourself to the fullest capacity
C110. Communication is a key
C111. government policies might restrict some extend
C112. let the money flow/invest once you get regular income from baseline business
C113. Keep updated the market.
C114. Remittance for personal and business investment in Nepal.
C115. Migration to work
C116. Gained work experience in many countries
C117. expensive business location in London
C118. Ethnic consumer on ethnic festival and occasion
C119 to work for myself
C120 to make money
C121 for betterment of family
C122 drive up and down to Kent everyday
C123 recognition with many awards
C124 limited access of education in Nepal
C125 learn from mistake
C126 poor family background
C127 agriculture occupation in family
C128 engaged in farming in kid
C129 personal savings as back up
C130 micro credit association
C131 challenge due jump in business without any idea
C132 learnt to speak fluent English
C133 hard work and patience
C134 hard working class culture
C135 honesty as a cultural value
C136 easy to do business in the UK
C137 influencing seeing relative doing business
C138 ethnic products/ selling exotic products
C139 don't need to have education in market business
C140 no past experience
C141 Newari caste family
C142 agriculture and business family
C143 financial support from friend
C144 ethnic competitors with same nature of business within the same market.
C145 liberation from caste division/religion and culture boundary

C146 good business opportunity in UK
C147 Honesty
C148 ethnic and mainstream networking
C149 import handicrafts
C150 choose out of London due to high competition in London
C151 non-ethnic spends more than ethnic group
C152 Boss encouraged to start the business
C153 migrate due to the economic problem
C154 trend to go India, learn work and go abroad
C155 trend to come in the UK in a student visa during 2009/10
C156 good job opportunity and good wages in the UK
C157 opportunity to live with family in the UK
C158 migrate as a dependent of a student (wife)
C159 Educated person is confident to speak with anybody
C160 Start business against religion
C161 tough competition in London
C162 huge demand for Gorkhali products among Whites
C163 work everything to save cost in the beginning
C164 Keep motivating staffs
C165 social network as work/life balance
C166 Good quality products and customer service
C167 Hard work is a key to be a successful entrepreneur
C168 easy access location
C169 Lack of market knowledge
C170 to create job
C171 Buddhist and Sherpa culture background
C172 Buddhist reflects as supporting and helping others.
C173 culture and religion guide our life
C174 migrate abroad due to moist period
C176 staffing through website
C177 lack of confidence being an immigrant to manage relationship with customers and suppliers.
C178 Different market policy to manage competition
C179 face-to-face customer feedback
C180 Remittance for charity
C181 brought up with joint family
C182 Difficult to get loan for students
C183 Self-research in internet
C184 easy to operate if you follow government policies
C185 struggling phase in the UK
C186 plan to open own business during working for others

2) Examples of Axial codes

Reasons for starting business	Strategies for acquiring and utilising resources	Challenges and issues
<p><u>Individual factors</u></p> <p>To have own identity</p> <p>A social status</p> <p>Recognition of opportunity</p> <p>To work for myself</p> <p>to make money</p> <p>to be independence/freedom working own</p> <p>Enterprising and industrial childhood-engage in enterprising early age</p> <p>self-confident & self-support/self-inspiring</p> <p><u>Skills and experience</u></p> <p>Knowledge from experience/transferable skills of past experience</p> <p>Knowledge and skills from education</p> <p>Education background different from current business</p> <p>Gain work experience in same sector</p> <p>Family have work experience in same sector</p> <p>Easier to recognise business opportunity having prior businesses</p> <p>Prior business experience</p> <p>Support due to prior business experience</p> <p><u>Social and cultural factor</u></p> <p>for betterment of family</p> <p>cultural values limited to personal life</p> <p>Priority to get education</p> <p>Hard work and long hours</p> <p>Education background in same field</p> <p>Experience influence more than education</p> <p>Middle class family</p> <p>Don't eat beef but sell it.</p> <p>Family background influence to start business</p> <p>Culture does not influence</p> <p>No blocked mobility</p> <p>No Gender issues in the UK</p> <p>Had better job</p> <p>Don't want to follow family career tradition</p>	<p><u>The role of family and friends</u></p> <p>Family support</p> <p>Financial support from family</p> <p>Finance with partner</p> <p>Migration for family reunion</p> <p><u>Human capital</u></p> <p>Went India for higher studies</p> <p>Learnt English accent</p> <p>Migrated for higher studies</p> <p><u>Informal source of finance</u></p> <p>Own savings</p> <p>Borrow from father from back home</p> <p>micro credit association</p> <p>personal savings as back up</p> <p><u>Source of advice</u></p> <p>Resources supply through ethnic social networks</p> <p>Moral support from ethnic social networks</p> <p>Advice from formal sources/mainstream</p> <p>Close ties to co-ethnic</p> <p>Active involvement in ethnic associations/ethnic</p> <p>Good team work and network (support system)</p> <p>Network of supportive suppliers</p> <p>Advice from co-ethnic Accountant and solicitor</p> <p>Advice from previous boss</p> <p>Advice from ethnic social network</p> <p>Attend formal training and skills workshops</p> <p>Mainstream networking by high-tech entrepreneurs</p> <p>Solidarity community</p> <p>Advice from seniors</p> <p>advice from partners</p> <p>Loyal and trust in business partner</p>	<p>Challenges in staffing</p> <p>Lack of supportive workshops within ethnic group</p> <p>Bank loan</p> <p>Easier to get bank loan</p> <p>Low budget for accessing formal supports/mainstream</p> <p>Challenge to compete with big companies</p> <p>Challenge to maintain health and safety</p> <p>Challenge to maintain employees law</p> <p>Change in immigration laws lead previous business shut down.</p> <p>Government laws and policies-Brexit influence</p> <p>Lack of high level of employment support from co-ethnic.</p> <p>Barrier in English accent</p> <p>Difficulty in business ownership due to previous owner</p> <p>government policies might restrict some extend</p>

<p>C77. Learnt good attitude from family values – brought up in well discipline in business</p> <p>Host country factors</p> <p>C35. Non-ethnic product</p> <p>C36. Non-ethnic market</p> <p>C58. Tier 2 entrepreneurship visa as an opportunity</p> <p>C63. Easier in business ownership through right to operate under big organisation</p> <p>C64. Live near/ convenient location</p> <p>C91. Multi and diverse businesses</p> <p>C95. Previous business failure but learn at the cost of something</p>		
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3: Help and Support

Interviewee	Priorities of education	Use of prior experience and skills	Access of informal sources	Sources of advice	source of finance
			Family support		
Int-1	<p>Aeronatical engineering</p> <p>past experience is definitely important but other than that and when I studied my degree I had to do lots of strategic</p> <p>so educational background has influence</p>	<p>I do have a full time job in the afternoon. So I do my engineering job. then I run this restaurant in the evening.</p> <p>the work I do in afternoon I take it as a college I go there and I learn a lot the corporate system</p>	<p>my family supported me they did not encourage me</p>	<p>not from Nepalese communities. I would love to but not from Nepalese community. I go to lots of shows trade union shows, and other international shows but not in Nepalese community and I don't think there has been many supportive kind of workshops from Nepalese community</p>	<p>First one was with help of my family a with partner. And second one this one also from the savin that we have made</p>
Int-2	<p>Bachelors in hospitality</p> <p>Masters in HR</p> <p>My initial background was hospitality so I did. I came here as to do the masters because I don't have a master's degree for hospitality in back home so after finishing that one I take HR which is comparatively related to the hospitality as well ya I can relate to them</p>	<p>It's all experience. It's all back previous experience</p> <p>experience is most ya rather than the studies because it's a small business, I don't need to deal with so many people so.</p>	<p>my husband and my brother-in law is working here. They used to work in a Japanese restaurant from a long time so they get more experience</p>		<p>We have got our own savings plus we ma to get some loans fr the bank</p>

Int-3	<p><i>Masters in IT</i></p> <p><i>Originally I came to study my masters and after completing that I took a job and I started a family and then business ya after finishing my studies I was hired by a company in Mayfair so I did as a manager there.</i></p>	<p><i>if you manage people regardless which sector you manage it's the same people they have same expectation different factors that motivate them so you managing people in one place that skills can be transferable regardless</i></p>	<p><i>my wife is always being there throughout the journey.</i></p> <p><i>she is not working directly but she runs the charity part which is more like a skills and care charity.</i></p>	<p><i>we invest lots of money in people so for ex myself have various trainings I still going its continuous like 360 leadership and coaching sort of trainings we have those kind of things we still do that coaching and mentoring</i></p>	<p><i>finance was not diff for me because I had other businesses, I had other assets where capital to start people who don't have money have to go to the bank</i></p> <p><i>It's my own saving</i></p>
	<p><i>It has helped me definitely. Not necessarily vital role if somebody wants to do business don't need to be masters or bachelors qualified but for me having studied IT make my life a lot easier if there is any problem I don't need to rely on somebody else so I have that knowledge. Even I studied part of the business part like business forecasting, business plan so it's easier for me so ya that contribute but I don't think it is necessary to be honest. But for me its been helpful.</i></p>	<p><i>because I am from business background so I now there is a problem, there is an opportunity yes somebody complain about the things and so I address that problem you have a business opportunity</i></p>			
Int-4	<p><i>BHM, BAHM (tourism and hospitality)</i></p> <p><i>(no English barrier)</i></p> <p><i>I did my bachelors in hospitality So I was in this area of line.</i></p> <p><i>my father is a retired teacher. So we were always to be in discipline and then do things at right time ah and my parents would always expect us to bring good grades in the school so education was very top of the priority of all things</i></p>	<p><i>I had few businesses prior but didn't do good but I have learned from the mistakes and moved into this business.</i></p>	<p><i>My wife has help me a lot whenever I need like assistance.</i></p>	<p><i>we have a lot of committees' meetings and sometimes the meetings are after meeting we have dinner it might get a priority that you might get some business from them as well or if need any help.</i></p> <p><i>we cannot live without the community even we are dealing in different sector in the business at the end of the day you still back to your own community so that's your home</i></p>	<p><i>I had some savings the job I was doing was saving some money to start my own. I had 35000 pounds had to borrow some money from my father which he happily let me and that was me ya 50 per cent I got from my father. An is a partnership business</i></p>
	<p><i>you don't need to use your certificate anywhere but the information and the studies you have done is helping directly and indirectly, it makes your personality as what I am. Like all those studies and time, I have given in my studies. It has influenced the way I am and the way I behave as a business person.</i></p>				
Int-5	<p><i>Hotel management</i></p>	<p><i>experience wise I have fifth country work and 15 years' work experience in</i></p>	<p><i>We all family we support each other. Before I supported my family for my</i></p>		<p><i>it was very easy because my credit score was very good when</i></p>

	<p>I did hotel management in Nepal.</p> <p>all the things I gain from my experience. Before there was not good type of education when I was like 20 years back but now there must be good educational centre.</p>	<p>pastry and bakery and I won 2 gold medal and two silver medal. Two gold medal in Bermuda and two silver medal in the hotel Olympia in excel and Birmingham in the chocolate petty for senior class. The hardest one is the London one because it's the world class chocolate competition</p>	<p>nephew's education and now he already started earning money when I asked and he helped me in just one word send next day in my account s</p> <p>some relatives said -oh you don't have salary right now your business is not good if you need money ask me any time, next we will happy to help this kind of encouragement I got it that's why I am standing today. If I don't have that support may be I closed the business and back to work that's the main thing my friends and families give me support.</p>	<p>friends who has already restaurant in the Scotland. I used to work with him for one year and he runs the business as well so he gives me advice. When I need him I just call him what to do and other friend who use to work in the London somewhere as a manager and he advise me as well like paperwork.</p> <p>we have 'NFF' as well – Nepal Friendship foundation and I am a chairman for this committee. We keep this one because we try to be together at least 4-6 times year together</p>	<p>used to work in Hotel had high salary. I left that job and the easily I got loan from bank. I got £20,000 easily just I clicked I got it</p>
Int-6	<p>Intermediate (no any barriers, and no growth after many years in business)</p> <p>I came here before I was a student</p>	<p>I don't have any past experience as well. this is my first and last.</p>		<p>Even if I need something like stock, they advised me to where to get it and how to get it and they always helping me so that's good.</p>	<p>When I started my business, I was lucky one of my friend, he gave me all the stock whatever I need I got in credit then slowly paid to him</p>
	<p>Here you don't need to have lots of education in the market.</p>				
Int-7	<p>A level I have done A level in Nepal. I was grown up in the village. I did SLC in the village, Baglung. So after school we have to come in city as there are no colleges in the village. So I went in Chitwan, Narayangath for studying intermediate level</p> <p>There were not any hotel management course that time</p>		<p>As I came here, I started to work in Yak and Yeti restaurant. The owners also my brothers (relatives) when they knew I was coming they asked me to work for them</p> <p>I felt easy because of the relatives in the UK. I got job straight away after coming here. I don't need to search job so didn't need to struggle much.</p>	<p>Whenever I have any problem related with business then I can share with friends there. There are so many businessmen involved in these committees so I can share with them. So these networking are really helpful. So for me and my business I find these social networks is influential.</p>	<p>I had my own savings and it was partnership</p>
	<p>As you have to tackle and speak in English everywhere. For ex-If you need to do some official work, need to go council for any work, deal with the health and safety team, communicate with supplier. Educated person is confident to speak with anybody. I have done at least intermediate so I don't need to face that much trouble but education is the most important.</p>				

		And 2006, I started running my college since then I am in education field and I am still going now		need to do these things first time until you do it no guidance will help you.	
Int-14	Intermediate I have just studied I.A. definitely, education guides and gives confidence. I studied in Nepali medium so my English writing is not that much good which is one of the barrier for me and my business	I worked for my previous Japanese boss for more than 20 years as a head chef. He got three restaurants so one of them I was a head chef and manage everything. whatever I have learnt, I learn from my work. I worked everything from my boss. So I am using same knowledge and experience.	My family are working and also my friends and relatives support me and provide me advice. One of my friend who also has a restaurant provide me the supplier details where I can buy food in very cheap price.	I have very strong relationship with families and friends who are from same community in Nepal. we are nearly 12 families and during the festivals and other celebrations. We celebrate festivals together. I take advice from my friends and previous boss.	I had own savings
		I have worked for more than 20 years for same company. I have very good experience and knowledge in Japanese restaurant. I got good opportunity given by my boss so I grab it		I did not take any external source of advice apart from solicitor and Accountant. I just call my friends if I get any problems. And also my previous boss is really helpful. He still frequently visits here and give me advices	
Int-15	Bachelors in Management Actually I have studied bachelor's degree in Nepal. so from that one for this business I manage my business very well because I don't need any accountant because of my bachelor's degree in management so it's very helpful to develop this business.	I get lots of knowledge experience and lots of training for development skills and managing the people and skills and training how to deal with customers from that job I am now better in this to establish	my friend from Nepal who do the handicraft business like he provides me all his handicraft things in a credit so I didn't need to pay in advance so it's helped me a lot to establish the business in London. my wife helps me a lot, like she got lots of friend and from her also I get lots of support plus my brother from Nepal and he also helped me a lot to establish this business.	I have good relationship with like we got like a Nepalese community like Nepal pasa Guthi where I do a marketing plus I get lots of support from senior people to establish my business and I got chance to do marketing over there like to sometime I do sell online from through the people.	it's not very difficult me. my family, friends supports a lots.
Int-16	Bachelors I was doing Bachelors in business management. But before finishing this I went in Japan and could not finish this so I did beautician course and I was the beautician teacher in back home but when I came in this country obviously that certificate is not valid. So I took another course and	When I used to work for others, my boss use to send me in trainings now since I got my own business I am going to different workshops and seminars. When I need to get new training for new thing which is expensive, first I research myself and the area weather I get customers for that service in that area so it depends.	I got emotional support and especially, my sister and her family is here and we live nearby which is being a great support for all of us. I think if we were not nearby then it was impossible for both of us to be in own business my husband and my sister family is supporting me indirectly. My husband is	The relationship with own people gives you happiness and also gives the identity of who you are and reflect the cultural background. It has helped me a lot. It balances my life, sense of belonging and I am getting emotional support.	Honestly not. Finar was not too difficult me. If you really have desire to achieve an have skill, then it is a barrier. My friend and family were as me if I need any financial help

	<p>spent money to get the certificate over here.</p>	<p>I worked as a beauty therapist initially then became a manager over there. worked almost 7 years there. I need to do everything. Handling customer's complaints, making rotas, treatments, maintaining stocks and other managerial works. I was sponsored for work permit in there so I felt like I was stuck there and could not leave as well. that phase was the most challenging for me. But ya that multitasking experience is helping in this current business. I can handle all type of customers, can tackle any complaints and much more confident.</p>	<p>always there to fix something. to change furniture etc. and my sister is also there whenever I need her help and ya as I said earlier, my sister family is a big supporter for me.</p>	<p>I used my skills and experience and also research a lot from websites and youtube. I attend seminars and workshops to be updated. And also I take training to learn any new trend as required.</p>	
Int-17	<p>SLC</p> <p>I have to work in front end have to deal with big companies at that time I fell little uneasy because of my education gap. The gap can come in terms of conversation, in terms of writing which have few effects in the Business. Generally in terms of work, customers will get as per their need.</p>	<p>I started from internet I had little knowledge on using internet. during my SLC examination - after I appeared my SLC examination, I started my own cyber café.</p> <p>At the age 15 I started business, at that time it was work related to garments not only that I was interested on skillful works like painting, we had a small business, a small grocery shop which I used to run when I was 15 years old</p>		<p>Network has definitely promoted my business. I worked in different communities which has helped me to support my business. Through these communities group, it also aided for marketing but in these communities ifu can speak well and convince them that's good marketing</p>	<p>Bank also doesn't do loans directly. I did have good job before my credit score was so good. The machines were expensive my credit card also could not afford it.</p>
Int-18	<p>Intermediate</p> <p>If I was not educated at all, I might not be that much ambitious or I might not be able to see dream to be independent. I have studied a bit so I am able to read and write paper works which is most important in day to day life. It helps me to communicate with people with confidence.</p>	<p>I learnt many things there. I build up my confidence working for others and learning from there as well. with those experiences I am able to do my own business</p>	<p>it was very challenging as I didn't have any idea from where to start. But my husband also helped me.</p>	<p>I started to build up my networks within my friends and got idea from friends who are already in this business.</p>	<p>I used own saving and both (husband and mine) and also I to some loan from my friends.</p> <p>We got some loan from the association where we have created among our friends in very interest.</p>
	<p>Language barrier- can speak and understand English still struggle to understand local accent, and not confident while speaking with suppliers, in bank, with customers etc but slowly adapt in the environment.</p>				
Int-19	<p>Bachelors</p>	<p>The person without any experience can start and run the business but need</p>	<p>My family members are working in my restaurant.</p>	<p>My business is more or like small family business so I have not</p>	<p>I had some personal saving and got some</p>

Int-8	<p><i>L.com</i></p> <p><i>we born in remote place. Our schools were also in remote place so from class 4 only we had chance to learn English.</i></p> <p><i>There is a difference in English language of speaking of ours and in here and mostly in countryside, it's more different. I learned a lot from there</i></p>	<p><i>I started to work in my own cousin's warehouse for 1 month then I worked in restaurant sector with motive for progress. Then I moved to countryside Oxfordshire because my wife was working there. And I worked at hotel there. I learned marketing support there.</i></p> <p><i>I have also done business in Nepal, hill region along with my studies. I always aim to create job for few people 2/4.</i></p>	<p><i>Me and my wife work in office to control and 3, 4 white girls are working in front.</i></p>	<p><i>Due to networking I am getting contracts. I got contract from London from many restaurants as well. so it does help</i></p>	<p><i>I used my own savi and also got person bank loan.</i></p>
	<p><i>I completed my SLC and L.com from my village paachthar. When I was going to do B.com, there was "Dwanda kalin" period – mouist period which was not the good situation to live in Nepal So I came abroad.</i></p>				
Int-9	<p><i>Bachlors in business mgmt. (no barrier)</i></p> <p><i>I came as a student in 2006.</i></p> <p><i>What I study in college that's the main thing I use in business so I can manage my accounts and everything you know and profit and loss everything it helps.</i></p>	<p><i>I worked with lots of like English people as well for this products that's why it makes me more easy to do my own business.</i></p> <p><i>they help me lots when I used to work with them. Ahh like how this products ahh like how I regulate this product and who is the main target customers like that. Ya I have learned from past experience.</i></p>		<p><i>Friends and family also support me to extend my business</i></p> <p><i>I don't have any consultants but sometime I use internet, google or some web searching research myself and it helps me quite good.</i></p>	<p><i>It is little bit hard to loan for students but after I finished my studies, then I tried work by myself then helps</i></p>
Int-10	<p><i>Masters in marketing</i></p> <p><i>I did bachelor in Nepal and done masters in here. I did online study in marketing. My interest field is marketing</i></p> <p><i>You will gain knowledge through education. When you get practical knowledge and add your educational knowledge, it will support a lot. Marketing strategy, sales strategy, how to introduce your product, demand and supply and so on we will get theoretical knowledge. Although, people are doing business without educational qualification but there will be a lot difference in between educated and</i></p>	<p><i>The place where I worked for 5 days in off license, there I learned a lot. I gained an experience working in cash and carry. That was my big achievement.</i></p> <p><i>I am one of the unsuccessful businessman in Nepal. I opened travel and tour, retail shop, pashmina business. I had an experience in different field. Although, I didn't gain financially but I had a good experience and which I am getting benefit and support in here.</i></p> <p><i>What I always think and suggest that if you work in any private organisation, shouldn't work only as an employee but with a</i></p>	<p><i>you need support which my wife has support me a lot. Family support is very important.</i></p>	<p><i>We 3 partners do everything with our mutual understanding. We sorted out all the things like staff management and everything. We have accountants and solicitors for legal support. We have accountant from Nepalese community</i></p>	<p><i>I borrowed from my friends. If a person honest then people definitely help and support.</i></p> <p><i>I didn't have any idea bank loan and nobo has advised me. So I suggest is that if someone wants to s own business, shou have knowledge on these stuffs.</i></p>

	<i>uneducated businessmen in terms of doing work, system.</i>	<i>motive to learn and start your own business</i>			
<i>Int-11</i>	<i>SLC joined college</i> <i>I did my education in Nepal. I just did high school level in Nepal. I completed SLC and had to join college but then I left my study. All other friends went abroad so I also wanted to go abroad. First I went to Saudi but did not stay longer then went to Singapore for 3 months and again went to Brunei and worked as a driver for Royal family there</i>	<i>I was in management position which has been fully helpful and supporting me in this current business. when I was just an employee, I did not have any responsibility but along with the promotion, it gave me more responsibility. I learnt to manage and do paperwork which makes me easier when I start my own business</i>	<i>all my friends help me networking and to find out different cash and carry</i> <i>My wife is working now. So we both work there</i>	<i>I got many help from friends plus I researched everything in internet. I did not consult with any professionals like solicitors. But I did all by myself. I just have an accountant who looks after my accounts.</i>	<i>I had the self-confidence so I borrowed from all family and manage collect £60000. I ph Dhukuti and collect money from Dhuku well and bought a house.</i> <i>I applied loan from bank and got appro about £20000</i>
	<i>education is a good thing but the most important is the experience. If the person has only educational qualification but he is not disciplined, hardworking and loyal then it's not useful.</i>				
<i>Int-12</i>	<i>Master 's degree in marketing</i> <i>I came for my master 's degree.</i> <i>education teach you something but here what I felt was it gives you that professional approach as well so going and speaking to somebody who is really busy giving you time and speak everything it builds confidence as well so the whole thing it's the part of the studies that actually taught you. Now obviously whoever it be I don't care, I just go and can talk. During the class, every single class we used to have a presentation in front of so many people which gives confidence. So it does, it adds up.</i>	<i>I was working for British gas I used to run market stall in Camden town. We used to sell ladies fashion clothes so by the time mon-fri I work and sat and sun</i> <i>when I worked there I met so many people so wherever I go I build up contacts</i>		<i>I love meeting people. different people. I learned from other person. This person is in manufacturing for 28 years and have lots if ideas so he gave me so many ideas and stuff and his whole factory in Bulgaria</i>	<i>I had enough savin use my own savings</i>
<i>Int-13</i>	<i>Qualified Accountant</i> <i>It helps a lot. You know like as I am a qualified Accountant when you deal the business, I know how the money is coming, what liabilities there, if I am making profit or loss. it helps a lot.</i>	<i>Ya I used to work in when I seven years back I used to work in large Accounting firm in London. And I gained experience from there. And two years I used to be consultant for the government council so it helps a lot. Ya past experience helps a lot.</i>	<i>It 's me and my wife we contact the people that we know, we post in the Facebook. We do all sort of marketing we talk to the people and the main thing is that we do what we say</i>	<i>I have got the relation with community in l they bring the students and they get the money so they always going out to get the students and they get the money</i> <i>I am an Accountant myself and the main</i>	<i>When I started this business I started w 250 pounds. It was much of investment 250 pounds. And it grew, grew and gre</i>
				<i>thing in business is you</i>	

	<p>Today's generation is like a digital world so if you can go with this you can achieve a lot. So to go with it, education is the most important.</p> <p>There is definitely a gap as we are the first generation in this country. We born and brought up in Nepal so anyhow I cannot be like Whites. So I still feel there is a gap which restricts us to enter in other mainstream sectors such as property business. when I go to the seminar, sometimes I can't understand certain things. So I still feel gap in the language even I am living here for 25 years.</p>	<p>to totally depends upon staffs whereas in my case, I had past experience and have been handling same problems related so I can handle myself. So I know how and by whom the task has to be done.</p>		<p>get advices from any consultants and agencies though I feel it is very important. But I usually go and attend trade fairs, search in internet as nowadays, we can get all the information in internet. So until now I am operating using my own skills and experience.</p>	<p>bank loan against collateral.</p>
Int-20	<p>Masters in IT</p> <p>I have completed masters in HR in the UK. I choose this business due to my educational background. I have some knowledge regarding recruitment.</p>	<p>academic knowledge and practical knowledge is different. Once you are in practical world, you need experience to deal problems in real world. When I started, I did not have any experience in this field, I just had my degree. It was challenging for me. I was not confident enough to deal with clients and other business stakeholders so I learn doing everyday gradually</p>	<p>I got emotional support and advices from my friends</p>	<p>I take information through websites and learn myself and also I take advice from my friends.</p>	<p>This business can be operated just by a laptop and a phone. It didn't need huge investment. I just rent a room for an office which is not much expensive</p>
Int-21	<p>Bachlors</p> <p>I have done college in back home. Then after due to the family reason and some problem I had to start my working life.</p> <p>Education is important but you also have to have experience for all sort of knowledge.</p>	<p>I used to work in hotel industry in Nepal, then after we moved abroad for few countries like Abu dabi, Qatar, Dubai, Bermuda, and UK. we worked in hotels industry and food business quite long time. So we just trying to utilise own experience on business.</p> <p>I was a chef there. I have experience working in big company where I learned high standard cuisine, good presentation skill and also managerial skills.</p>	<p>sometime my daughter will help me, when we get busy my wife helps me and sort of few people help me you know the friends and family.</p> <p>you have to have a family support to do a small business to get more success in the future and also if your current business is not running that means you need to have your family support and friends support to get business little</p>	<p>We have few friends working together as a business partners. We worked together in hotel industry before and we come together, sit down and we put our plan and we go from there and plus our family support of course.</p>	<p>Well if you have family and friends to support you don't get difficult. So I didn't have much family and friends support, then definitely it will be difficult.</p>
			<p>bit up and then you can put more staffs and give family little bit rest. That's what we do</p>		
Int-22	<p>undergraduate</p>	<p>Five years of experience in the same field.</p>	<p>Advice from friends circle and social network.</p>		

Int-23	Post-graduate from UK Education gives you more confident especially I am working in education sector myself so having that education gives you more credibility	Past experience in IT field.	I use mainstream support. I have a consultant and advisory team.		
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4) Challenges and Issues:

Interviewee	Staffing problem	Communication barriers and lack of knowledge	Regulatory complexity	competition	Finance	Work-life related
Int-1	we have lots of difficulties like human resources ahemm ya mainly human resources.					
Int-2			it's very very tough you have to look after each and everything, small things as well- health and safety, hygienic, rights of the employees everything. Each and everything ya there is lots of challenges	I need to compete with big companies because sushi is already grown in here so I need to compete with very big companies there are more fame sushi. They are already popular and we are very small in compare to them. I need to do a lot of marketing and everything.		
Int-3	the recruitment is the biggest challenge at the moment. To recruit the right person basically what we look for is people really want to work in industry, we are looking people who	I have not myself face any problem with the racial sort of discrimination but sometime	Any business that you regulated, it's very much depends upon the policies, the government policies for ex- Brexit can help or impact business a lot right where people are depending on lawful let's say every person has to be qualify level			

	<p>are really caring, really want to make things difference, may be not looking for 70/80 hrs a week, don't have a lot of commitments. You know specific people who can speak very good English, they can drive, they want to be in community, they want to help people, not worried about doing any little things a bit of cleaning which is the part of the job you know so it's really difficult to get people like that.</p>	<p>the language. I been living in this country for long time but ya we can't speak very good that kind of language but again people do respect you because they know you</p>	<p>3 tomorrow then it will make difference in business, if you say anyone who care for older person they need to have a certain level of qualification something that comes up that will impact. So ya the government legislation because this is very regulated industry, everybody can not commit to the business because lot of regulation to meet but again that does influence the business.</p>			
Int-4	<p>as in other restaurants sector, the new generation are not much ah attracted into this jobline like chef and waiter and waitress</p> <p>to get the new staffs is really challenge as well.so After this generation it will even will be struggling even more to get the staffs.</p>	<p>The main challenge doing the Chinese catering line is a lot of staffs I mean almost all staffs are Chinese so communication is main barrier</p>	<p>Ya we have a solicitor if its anything comes up. It can be public liabilities and things like that we had a case three years back one lady fell down in our parking we did not have the barrier she said she was not aware it was a private land there were not a visible barrier and she tripped into one of our parking stand so she said there was not enough lightings and so you always need a solicitor for the right suggestion it went well, I am not sure what happen with insurance but its ..you have some stress out of your mind if you have someone who take care of that side legal things like that.</p>			
Int-5		<p>the only problem was a language. My tone is not like English and the tone is different now you can feel that.</p> <p>the big challenge was first of all I did not had any training in this new business. I don't have any ideas in business, I just jumped in but I believe in my power and I believe in myself</p>				
Int-6				<p>there were not lots of Nepalese traders doing same products because I was two, three of them so that's why I didn't have too much</p>		

				difficulties in my time.		
Int-7	<p>Nowadays, it's very difficult for staffing. And it's more difficult to get Nepalese staffs</p>	<p>If somebody does not understand then somehow they manage to make them understandable like keeping interpreter as required. But in terms of self-difficulties- you won't be able to work as you need (vannebitikai) need interpreter.</p>				
Int-8		<p>There is a difference in English language of speaking of ours and in here and mostly in countryside, it's more different. I learned a lot from there</p> <p>In the beginning obviously it was difficult. It was a new place, investment, we were not sure about market, how to control regular expenditure and overall</p> <p>Firstly, I am a foreigner so I was not confident enough weather customers will trust me or not but I have shown my realness and</p>	<p>Brexit might be the challenge for the business at the present but after maybe there will be economic growth. However, it has not impact hugely but in future may be my business might get reduced by 5 to 10 per cent until 2 years then might get progress</p> <p>We have to follow all the rules and regulation such as health and safety but these are for our personal benefit and business benefit.</p>			

		<i>honesty to the customers</i>				
<i>Int-9</i>		<i>it is more challenging job like how to get customers first and its about the product as well what you are selling and first of all I studied about this and then I tried.</i>				
<i>Int-10</i>			<p><i>there are many responsibilities after starting business such as account update, VAT, taxes which you have to update on regular basis. So you have to be updated with accountability-buying and selling</i></p> <p><i>The main current challenge is Brexit. Brexit has impact hugely in the business. The other one is government cut down council benefits. Liquor is just the luxury spending so if government cut down benefits, people stops spending in liquor stuffs which has impact our business. the other one is Brexit. Due to Brexit, many Europeans are back from the UK. Other is due to the government policy, lots of students are back which reduce our sales. So the customers have been decreased in retail shops and they will buy less from us so it will impact in our business</i></p>	<p><i>When we opened in 2010, there was not any competitors in south east region. Now there are about 5 in this region only. So definitely there is a competition. but there is a same market and population. So lots of supplier and same market lead competition in pricing.</i></p>	<p><i>It was very tough. Honestly speaking, I had only £2000 cash. Where I had to invest £20000</i></p> <p><i>That time I didn't have any idea and nobody has advised me</i></p> <p><i>If your transaction is good, they will offer themselves. When starting it will be difficult because there will be good cash inflow now we have transaction on daily basis</i></p>	
<i>Int-11</i>		<p><i>It was new to me and didn't have fully experience as well but I did not lose my guts. That's how I go ahead.</i></p>	<p><i>There are lots of challenges in paperwork such as council, home office. There are long procedures. I cannot just open a shop straight away like in Nepal. there is paperwork to do here. Have to get license to sell alcohol, certificate for butcher, health and safety certificate. And for this I have to pass training, CRV check and send it to council then council provides us a card which only permit to sell alcohol. Then again we have to get opening and closing timetable from DPT.</i></p> <p><i>Brexit has impact in my business. Brexit has reduced my sales by 30-35 percent. Before Brexit, the sales were very good. it was easy for export and import from Europe but now the price has gone really high. For ex- before we can import fruits for free but now we can only import paying VAT. For the same product which we used to import for free,</i></p>	<p><i>There is a maximum competition in this area. In my view, there is a biggest competition mainly in the west Reading. There are 94 off incense shop within reading town to end of reading bottom which is of very big competition. it's not an easy</i></p>	<p><i>It was challenging and hard to manage in the beginning obviously. It was a huge investment of around 90000 to 100000.</i></p>	<p><i>I don't have any social life because as this is my own business you have to give all your time and can't leave the premises as you can't trust other staff.</i></p>

			<p>now it has cost higher due to VAT. So that's the big effect in my business.</p> <p>the government is implementing compulsory pension policy from this January. This policy was there from 16/17 but employers have choice but now it has been made compulsory. For ex- if they cut £10 from your wages, company also have to contribute £10 in the fund. And from 2020 Jan, company has to contribute three times for employees' pension fund for all companies. So the main difficult is to pay the fund and plus we have to pay extra fees to Accountant because he has to see another section as well. So employers have to bear extra cost.</p>			
Int-12			<p>The main thing is visa. I applied my visa in July 2017, I have still not heard anything back from them. So I am losing lots of opportunity in the international arena.</p>			<p>Because you are alone there are so many things you have to do. now at certain time I am working probably 18/19 hours a day because what happens is I finish everything a</p>
Int-13						
Int-14		<p>There is a gap in my knowledge as I have not studied much, there is a language barrier. I can handle and communicate in day to day but I feel less confident to handle with other from mainstream. I have to depend on others for doing formal paperwork and other advices</p>	<p>Ya due to the rules of immigration, I had to fire some of the best staffs here. My staff was a student so he was not allowed to work so I had to take out few staffs like that. I lost very good staffs which make me difficult phase.</p>			
Int-15		<p>I feel really difficult in the language barrier because people from the different</p>	<p>I feel really challenges because of the political situation in London and Nepal. sometime I Need to import the things from the Nepal so those like the pound rates goes down and up so which is really big challenging for me and it's like it</p>			

		<i>countries they use to visit in my shop so it's like really difficult to communicate</i>	<i>effects in my price for the handicraft so it's really challenging for me.</i>			
<i>Int-16</i>			<i>There was a big challenge for me which is my visa status. I was not settled properly which was a huge barrier.</i>			<i>Balancing my family life and my career is probably the biggest challenge.</i>
<i>Int-17</i>			<i>My visa status is a huge barrier as my wife is a student and I am in dependent visa. As the visa is not permanent, and home office keep changing rules so there is a high risk for my business.</i>		<i>I had difficulties relating to financing. This office setup and machineries was a subject of challenge. All the machineries were highly costly without good business one can't afford it. Bank also doesn't offer loans directly. I did not have good job before so my credit score was not so good</i> <i>We have approached bank many times. Even if we did everything and even having cash flow, they give us numerous reason. The banks has not been so supportive.</i>	
<i>Int-18</i>		<i>Language barrier- can speak and understand English still struggle to understand local accent, and not confident while speaking with suppliers, in bank, with customers etc but slowly adapt in the environment.</i>				<i>Definitely it is very challenging for me to balance family and my business. I had the long maternity gap so I felt out the loop. I wasn't up to date.</i>

Int-19			<p><i>It is more challenging now. Before we are allowed to get staff from work permit so we used to do but as immigration has strict the rules, it's very difficult. In addition, there used to be lots of students and they have priority to work in restaurant sector as part time like (cash in hand type) but government is tightening the rule day by day and close so it has stopped now. So we don't get staffs. Moreover, there used to be cash in hand type job but HM revenue has tightened the rule, so we have to go following proper rules so day by day it is being more difficult.</i></p>			
Int-20	<p><i>Ya it is the most challenging to recruit people. mainly we have huge demand of staffs from hospitality sector, but there are less people for recruitment. Before I used to get lots of Asian students for temporary jobs but now we are struggling.</i></p>		<p><i>I think due to the strict immigration rule of restricting work to students and stopping post study work scheme. And also due to Brexit, I think the situation will be worse than this</i></p> <p><i>The main problem for me is my visa status. The immigration is changing rules frequently and making stricter rules. Until I didn't get permanent residence, it will be a barrier for me</i></p>			
Int-21	<p><i>we had some problem for staffing before</i></p>	<p><i>Managing staffs, suppliers but now we have few Nepalese working with us plus some other people</i></p>				
Int-22	<p><i>It is very challenging to get staffs due to the recent changing rule in the UK.</i></p>					
Int-23		<p><i>Initial days, I had problem in English accent which I overcome by the help of a mentor and practicing a lot.</i></p>				

5) Transnational activities.

Respondents	Respondents' comments on Transnational activities
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Int-1	<i>I have strong connection with back home. I visit there frequently. Whenever I go there, I feel so close to my own identity and culture.</i>
Int-3	<i>I usually send some money to my mother and spoil them little bit. I go every six months at least. last time I went was on November so I am due soon.</i>
Int-4	<i>My father was happy to borrow £35,000 to start my business. I am mainly aiming and taking initiation for entrepreneurship opportunities in Nepal through different committees. We are focusing to encourage entrepreneurs to invest in Nepal so I am initiating many workshops to aware people about the opportunities in Nepal.</i>
Int-5	<i>I sold some of my land in Nepal and brought that money to start my business. My nephew in Australia also helped me sending some money. Now, I am making a nice house in Nepal which need huge money. It's nearly done. I spent nearly 2 millions.</i>
Int-6	<i>I import the Nepalese handicraft.</i>
Int-7	<i>I have imported the Nepalese art and architectures, paintings, sculptures etc. from Nepal to decorate my restaurant.</i>
Int-8	<i>I send to my father and mother plus for charity purpose. I send occasionally in two or three months. I do charity for making cultural and for community such as making temples, Gumbaa, orphanage. And also I intend to do some business in Nepal which can create some job. I really want to use both knowledge and finance from here and use in Nepal. I got British citizen. But I really want to do something where I was born and brought up. I am planning to make a big fund around 50 lakhs to 1 crore and with that interest, I would like to help to those people who are not able to get education and health service and also help my own village.</i>
Int-10	<i>all my family members have taken British citizenship except me. I will remain Nepali (laugh). In Nepal, we have opened Himalayan global company where we do share transaction, we have invested in film industry and we are in process to start hot air balloon in Nepal in Pokhara for the first time. We have transportation company there. my brother looks after there and stone business which my big brother looks after.</i>
Int-11	<i>I do some business of land there. My mother invests in land property from beginning and make some profit. I send 10 lakhs, 15 lakhs every 2/3 months. WI want to work for more 5/6 years and I will return back to Nepal. My future plan is to go back to Nepal. I have only one son who is 15 years old and he is doing very good in studies. I have already one house so I will buy one more house manage everything then I will go in Nepal. I have bought lots of properties in Nepal so I will definitely go back to Nepal after I become 45e are big family so we all brothers invest together.</i>
Int-12	<i>I have just launched 'Nepal Food'. I import our typical Nepalese food from Nepal and I got contract from big brands of Nepal (Wai Wai) which is a big privilege.</i>
Int-14	<i>I have invested huge money to build two houses in Nepal. Now I have rented both houses and I am getting return easily. Plus, with my saving, I usually buy land in Nepal and resell it. The profit is sometime more than double within short time period.</i>
Int-15	<i>I supply all the handicraft from Nepal. My brother and father is helping me to export the products. And in the beginning phase, my friend who is doing handicraft business in Nepal helped me to establish my business in London by giving advices and credit as well.</i>
Int-17	<i>I am planning to expand my business in Nepal. In fact, I outsource some of the designing job to some of my brothers. As Nepal is a developing country, there is a good scope these days.</i>
Int-18	<i>Me and my husband send all our saving two years back to build our house in back home.</i>

Int-19	<i>I have investment in Nepal as well. I have school and college there in Pokhara. My soul is always connected in Nepal</i>
Int-21	<i>Currently, I am building a house in Nepal so I am sending all the profit I earned from this business and invest for my house. And also I have invested to buy some land in Nepal.</i>

Appendix 7: Interview questions

- 1) Could you please give me your brief introduction?
- 2) Could you please tell me about the nature of business you are currently running in UK?
- 3) What was the reason to come to this country?
- 4) How long have you been in this country?
- 5) Where is the location of this business and why do you choose this location?
- 6) How long have you been running this business?
- 7) What is the main reason to start up this business in UK?
- 8) Could you please tell me about your educational qualification, and does it have any influence in running this business?
- 9) Have you received any training, or any experiences related on the business you are doing?
- 10) Did you face any challenges during start-up of this business? If yes, could you please elaborate it?
- 11) What other challenges are you facing to grow or sustain this business?
- 12) What are the challenges you faced as the foreign nationals to operate this business?
- 13) How did you finance your business?
- 14) As an emerging Nepalese national's entrepreneur, is there any easy access to finance to operate the business?
- 15) As a foreign national, do you know or heard about any support getting from agencies or government to operate the business?
- 16) Do you think easy finances are received by British nationals and thus it becomes easier for them to start up new business and why?
- 17) As a foreign national entrepreneur, did you face any challenges in terms of rules and regulations to operate this business?
- 18) Are the laws and policies in favor of startups by foreign nationals and how?
- 19) As UK is going out from the EU market due to BREXIT, Will there be any effect in your business?
- 20) Do you think changes in Visa regulations would help in startups for foreign nationals like Nepalese and Why?
- 21) Who is your targeted customer and why?
- 22) Did you face any challenges related to cultural difference, discrimination or language while operating the business?
- 23) Did you face any challenges related to competition in this business?

24) Which other factors do you think influencing Nepalese entrepreneurship in UK?

25) What do you suggest for the Nepalese entrepreneur as from your lesson learnt?